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Abstract

This Deliverable, D2.2 provides an overview of existing assessment frameworks for Digital Health Technologies (DHTs). Based on different methodologies (scoping review and survey HTA agencies) existing frameworks and methods for the assessment of DHT were analysed. Areas where further development is required have been identified and possible future approaches to address current challenges in the assessment of DHTs are outlined.

Statement of originality

This deliverable contains original unpublished work except where clearly indicated otherwise. Acknowledgement of previously published material and of the work of others has been made through appropriate citation, quotation or both. Views and opinions expressed are those of the author(s) only. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

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ABBREVIATIONS

AI	Artificial intelligence
DHT/DHTs	Digital health technology/ Digital health technologies
EU	European Union
EVA	Early value assessment
HTA	Health technology assessment
NICE	National Institute for Health and Care Excellence
RWE	Real-World Evidence
SaMD	Software as a Medical Device
WHO	World Health Organization

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Introduction

Health systems are facing urgent challenges that require transformation, with Digital Health Technologies (DHTs) offering potential solutions to improve access, quality and affordability. However, existing health technology assessment (HTA) frameworks often fail to do justice to the unique complexity of DHTs. The aim of this deliverable is to provide an overview of existing assessment frameworks for DHTs and to identify gaps and weaknesses in the methods available to HTA bodies for the assessment of DHTs.

Methods

A mixed methods design was used for the landscape and gap analysis of frameworks and methods for assessing DHT: (1) A scoping review was conducted to identify relevant frameworks in the literature. (2) A survey of HTA agencies was conducted to identify frameworks for assessing DHTs and perceived challenges from an HTA agency perspective. Data were analysed based on the domains of the HTA Core Model and an inductive categorization was formed.

Results

60 frameworks for the assessment of DHTs were identified with varying scopes. Most of them explicitly focussed on digital health applications (68%), while frameworks for artificial intelligence (2%) were rather limited. The frameworks primarily provided guidance on assessment, with varying focuses on evidence requirements, but rarely considering the lifecycle of DHTs. Assessment domains of the HTA Core Model were included in the frameworks, containing health problem, technical characteristics, safety, clinical effectiveness, costs, ethics, and organizational social aspects and legal aspects, but their inclusion varied between the frameworks.

Conclusion

The report highlights the diversity and inconsistency of DHT assessment frameworks, with limited focus on lifecycle approaches and classification methods. It highlights the usefulness for an internationally framework that considers methodological clarity, cost-benefit assessment and challenges such as data protection, privacy and interoperability.

1 Introduction

Given the challenges of a changing burden of disease, demographic transition, increasing expenditure, doubts about quality and value of many interventions, to name just a few, the urgency to transform healthcare systems is growing. The increasing development and use of digital health technologies (DHTs) is often expected to enhance accessibility, affordability, and quality of care^[1]. As with other technologies, the value of DHTs must be evaluated in a multidisciplinary, systematic process across their lifecycle^[2]. This process is known internationally as Health Technology Assessment. It informs decision-making to promote equitable, efficient, and high-quality healthcare systems by assessing factors such as clinical effectiveness, safety, costs, and broader social, ethical, and organizational impacts^[2].

However, DHTs may differ from traditional health technologies in terms of their technological features, the speed of their development, and the complexity of integrating them into routine care^[3]. To take these specific characteristics of DHTs into account, several frameworks and taxonomies have been developed – for different purposes, from regulatory frameworks to frameworks for coverage and reimbursement in publicly financed health systems. Many are risk-based, such as the concept of Software as a Medical Device (SaMD), which categorizes technologies into four risk classes^[4]. The Evidence Standards Framework for DHTs of the National Institute for Health and Care Excellence (NICE) aligns DHT types with corresponding tiers of required standards^[5,6]. Similarly, the World Health Organization (WHO) use a taxonomy based on how technologies address health system needs^[7].

Several additional generic or specialized assessment frameworks for technologies have been developed^[8] however, they often fail to adequately address the unique challenges posed by DHTs. For example, the HTA Core Model[®] is a well-known methodological framework for producing and sharing of HTA information. It describes different HTA domains and approaches for their methodological evaluation^[9]. In their systematic review, Moshi et al. (2018) come to the conclusion that many frameworks for mobile applications are not suitable for the HTA area, as they do not include all HTA domains^[10]. Existing classifications often follow different logics and may not fully address the latest innovations in DHTs. Another systematic literature review of published assessment guidelines for digital health interventions concludes that an analytical framework for calculating clinical and economic outcomes is still lacking^[11]. In addition, the current HTA frameworks are not sufficient for the assessment of specific DHTs, as those have different benefit and risk profiles^[12]. Therefore, special features in the assessment of DHTs must be taken into account, including challenges related to generating the required evidence for proper evaluation, the interactions between digital technologies and users, and the reliance of the technologies' effectiveness on these interactions, the organizational implications, the diagnostic potential of digital technologies, their potential influence on health outcomes, and issues concerning the determination of fair pricing for these technologies^[13].

The aim of this deliverable is to get an overview of existing frameworks and methods for the assessment of DHTs. Furthermore, potential gaps and areas in the methods available for assessing different types of technologies will be identified.

2 Methods

For the landscape and gap analysis of existing frameworks and methods for assessing DHTs a mixed methods design was used, incorporating:

- (1) a scoping review of frameworks for assessing DHTs and
- (2) a survey among HTA agencies.

2.1 Scoping Review

The scoping review was conducted following the guidance provided by the Joanna Briggs Institute Reviewer Manual^[14]. It also adheres to the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses Extension for Scoping Reviews guidelines (PRISMA-ScR)^[15]. This review aimed to identify and map existing frameworks for assessing DHTs. The overarching aim was to explore which frameworks are available for the assessment of DHTs. The purpose of the frameworks and any guidance related to the assessment of DHTs were analysed within the domains of the HTA Core Model^[9]. Additionally, we examined whether these frameworks distinguish between different groups/classifications of DHTs. The protocol was registered with the Open Science Framework (doi.org/10.17605/OSF.IO/43RZ5) on May 2, 2024. A literature search was performed in April 2024 using PubMed and Embase databases.

2.1.1 Search Strategy

The searches were conducted for the period from January 2015 to April 2024 using the defined search terms that related to two core topics: digital health technologies and frameworks for their assessment, included in the title or abstract. The full search strategy is summarized in Appendix 1. The identification of relevant studies was complemented with a non-systematic hand search and a snowballing search based on the references in the included studies, as well as citations of the included studies. Relevant reviews^[16,10,8,17] and frameworks of an analysis from the Evidence DEFINED project^[18,19] were also examined, as they pursued similar objectives. In addition, information on assessment frameworks from a survey of HTA agencies (see 2.2) was used.

2.1.2 Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria

The following inclusion and exclusion criteria were defined to select articles from the literature employing the Joanna Briggs Institute PICO (Research questions in Population/Problem, Interest/Phenomenon of Interest, Context and Design) categories.

Inclusion Criteria:

This review focuses on frameworks, scientific articles, and guidelines focusing on the assessment of DHTs (e.g., telemedicine, mobile health applications, or decision support systems based on artificial intelligence) that at least include one domain of the HTA Core Model. Eligible for inclusion were reviews, guidelines, HTA reports, qualitative and quantitative studies, published between January 2015 and April 2024. Articles in English and German language were included.

Exclusion Criteria:

Frameworks that did not focus on assessing DHTs were excluded. Frameworks in the following types of publications were excluded: Study registers, protocols, conference abstracts, editorials, letters to the editor, commentaries, commemorative publications, errata, dissertations.

2.1.3 Eligibility and Data Extraction

To manage the screening process and track agreement between reviewers the Covidence tool^[20] was used. Two reviewers screened a random 20% sample of all unique records based on their titles and abstracts and discussed their results until consensus on the inclusion was reached. Agreement between them was sufficiently high when at least 80% raw agreement was reached, so that the remaining records were screened by one reviewer only. Afterwards one reviewer screened all full-text articles included after title/abstract screening. A second reviewer screened all full-text articles excluded by the first reviewer during full-text screening.

The data extraction process was conducted with the Covidence tool and three researchers independently were involved. Always two reviewers equally shared data extraction from the studies, and any discrepancies were resolved. An extraction sheet was developed, tested by two persons and slightly adapted.

Data on the following items were extracted: Country, organisation/HTA agency, author(s), year of publication, title, version of the framework, purpose of the assessment framework, groups/types/tiers of DHTs, scope of assessments (clinical, non-clinical, technological aspects), evidence requirements for DHTs (e.g. choice of endpoints/outcomes, choice of comparator, study designs used for evidence generation).

2.1.4 Descriptive analysis of the data

Descriptive analyses of the data were performed on general information (e.g. the purpose of the frameworks), the grouping or classification of DHTs, and whether the framework targeted specific types of DHTs. Additionally, information on evidence requirements and life cycle stages were analysed.

The analysis of assessment guidance provided within the included frameworks, scientific articles, and guidelines was based on the structure of the HTA Core Model^{®[9]}. First, the content of the individual frameworks (hereinafter referred to as 'items') - including criteria, methods and requirements for assessing DHTs - was assigned to the nine HTA domains of the HTA Core Model[®]. Subsequently, one researcher inductively developed categories for these items. The results were then reviewed by at least another researcher. Through iterative discussions among all researchers and by moving items back and forth, items were refined and reallocated where necessary until consensus was achieved. Ultimately main categories and in many cases, subcategories were established. A narrative synthesis was performed by summarising the characteristics and results of included studies in both table and text formats.

2.2 Request to HTA Agencies

A survey was distributed to 30 countries, including the member states of the European Union (N=27), and Norway, Switzerland, as well as the UK, to collect information from HTA agencies and decision-making institutions. The numbers of HTA agencies and HTA-related organizations (decision-making institutions responsible for HTA appraisal) varied depending on the healthcare systems and autonomy of the regions in the countries, e.g., in Spain, eight agencies were contacted.

The questionnaire, developed by TUB and refined by AIHTA and NICE, covered four key areas. The questionnaire was also used as part of another deliverable of the ASSESS project (deliverable 2.1). Parts 1 and 3 were used for this deliverable. The entire questionnaire can be found in Appendix 2:

- (1) Availability of frameworks/guidance documents/ guidelines to assess Digital Health Technologies (DHTs)
- (2) Current status of assessed DHTs
- (3) Current gaps and weaknesses in assessing DHTs
- (4) Request for an expert specialized in artificial intelligence (AI)

To avoid overburdening HTA agencies, partners of ASSESS DHT provided part one of the questionnaire for review to partners of the EDIHTA^[21] project. In July 2024, ASSESS DHT agreed to share all results of the questionnaire with EDIHTA. ASSESS DHT and EDIHTA jointly sent some clarifying and follow-up questions to HTA agencies in August 2024.

3 Results

3.1 Scoping Review

3.1.1 Study Selection and Characteristics

After removal of duplicates, a total of 3,576 hits (titles and abstracts) of the two databases were screened and 90 articles were included in the full-text review. Of these, 75 articles were excluded, resulting in 15 articles that met the inclusion criteria. The manual search included 45 hits e.g. through websites, systematic reviews, or frameworks of the DEFINED study^[18]. In total, 60 articles were included in the synthesis. The list of included frameworks is in Appendix 3.

3.1.2 General information of identified frameworks

The 60 frameworks for HTA of DHTs were published between 2015 and 2024. The individual purposes of the frameworks were summarised in categories. The predominant purpose of the frameworks was 'Support & Guidance' (47%), followed by 'Evaluation and Evaluation standards' (28%) and 'Quality evaluation' (18%) (Table 1).

Purpose	Definition	No.	Percent (%)
Support & Guidance	Structured support to help users, clinicians, and developers to make informed decisions about DHTs	28	47%
Evaluation & evaluation standards	Evaluation standards for DHTs to determine e.g. their clinical relevance, usability, data security, and overall effectiveness	17	28%
Quality evaluation	Evaluation of the quality of DHTs	11	18%
Evidence requirements & evidence standards	Evidence standards to generate robust evidence of DHTs	6	10%
Promotion & facilitation of use	Development and use of high-quality, safe, and effective DHTs	3	5%
Gap analysis & Adaption	Identification of deficits in existing frameworks and modification of tools	3	3%

Note: multiple purposes possible

Table 1. Purpose of the assessment framework

Regarding the investigation into whether DHTs are classified into groups within the frameworks and whether this leads to different assessment requirements or methodologies, the analysis revealed that only three out of 60 frameworks included a classification or grouping of DHTs. The Evidence Standards Framework (ESF) for DHTs of the NICE^[6] classifies DHTs by intended purpose which allows them to be stratified into tiers based on the potential risk to service users and to the system. The Health Technology Assessment Framework of Segur-Ferrer et al.^[22] uses the ESF from NICE for the classification in their methodological framework. Lantzsch et al. (2022) classify digital health applications according to the following attributes: (i) application area, (ii) target group, (iii) function, and (iv) user and defines three levels of evidence requirements depending on the classification.

The analysed frameworks targeted various types of technologies. Most frameworks focused on ‘Digital health applications’ (68%) followed by ‘General digital health technologies’ (not further defined) (20%), ‘Telemedicine’ (3%), ‘Artificial intelligence’ (AI) (2%) and ‘Other’ digital technologies (e.g., precision health innovations or Sensor technologies) (7%) (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Specific DHT groups named in included frameworks

The frameworks rarely included information on the lifecycle approach. Out of the 60 frameworks analysed, only 10 provided information on lifecycle stages, with over half of these (70%) mentioning lifecycle stages in general terms^[22–28]. One framework addressed ongoing app evaluation requirements within the lifecycle approach^[29], another referred to early deployment standards for evidence-generation programmes^[6], and a third focused on post-market monitoring^[30].

In contrast, a greater number of frameworks (24) addressed evidence requirements. Regarding the specific evidence required for DHTs, 20% of the frameworks focused on evaluation criteria, testing and validation. Other frameworks discussed study design, the availability of evidence, and specific evidence tiers or requirements, each accounting for 16%. General levels of evidence (12%) were mentioned less frequently.

However, there is little information from the frameworks that the requirements vary depending on the type of DHT or its life cycle phase. The Evidence Standards Framework for DHTs by NICE^[6] stands out as a comprehensive framework containing 21 standards (evaluation requirements). It also includes 16 early deployment standards designed to support evidence generation programs, helping companies to develop the evidence base for DHTs at an early deployment stage.

3.1.3 Domains and dimensions being considered in identified frameworks

From the 60 frameworks, scientific articles, and guidelines related to the assessment of DHTs included in the analysis, the extent to which each framework addressed domains of the HTA Core Model^[9] was evaluated. The results showed that most frameworks provided information on the ‘Description and Technical Characteristics’ domain, followed by the ‘Patients and Social Aspects’ and ‘Clinical Effectiveness’ domains. In contrast, the ‘Organisational Aspects’, ‘Legal Aspects’, and ‘Ethical Analysis’ domains were less frequently covered (Figure 2). A summary of the coverage of the HTA domains for each framework is in Appendix 4.

Figure 2. Presence of HTA domains in included frameworks

A categorization of the included frameworks into main categories (with or without subcategories) per domain was established. Figure 3 shows the developed main categories and subcategories. There was

partial overlap between categories and subcategories, and it was not always clear which items could be assigned to which domain. The phenomenon, where some items are intertwined across domains, is also described in the EUnetHTA Core Model^[9].

Figure 3. Main categories and subcategories assigned to the HTA domains

Figure 4 shows the frequencies of the main categories derived from the included frameworks across all nine HTA domains. The frequency analysis of the HTA domains and associated items, is provided in the Appendix 5. Additionally, a comprehensive list of all HTA domains, categories, and associated items from the included frameworks can be found in Appendix 6.

Figure 4. Frequencies of Main Categories derived from the included frameworks

The domain ‘Health Problem and Current Use (CUR)’ addresses target conditions, affected groups, epidemiology, technology use, burden on individuals and society, alternative solutions, regulatory status, and usage requirements of the technology in question^[9]. This domain was mentioned in 21 frameworks (35%), with 41 items assigned to it. The items refer to information on the target user, the intended use, and product purpose, and credibility.

The domain ‘Description and technical characteristics (TEC)’ provides details about the technology, including its development, purpose, users, usage, conditions addressed, and healthcare level^[9]. This domain appeared in 45 frameworks (75%), with a total of 208 items assigned to it, making it one of the most frequently covered domains. Ultimately 15 subcategories were established, which relate to the three main categories ‘Features’, ‘Implementation’ and ‘Technical aspects’.

The domain ‘Safety (SAF)’ refers to any harmful effects resulting from the use of health technology. Safety assessments are critical for benefiting patients and informing policies, though methods can vary based on diverse safety concerns across technologies^[9]. This domain was mentioned in 27 frameworks (45%), with 70 items assigned to it. Three main categories were established:

- ▶ **Clinical Safety:** Assessing potential harms, conducting risk evaluations, and ensuring oversight by a Clinical Safety Officer.

- ▶ Technical Safety: Ensuring user protection, robust evidence from validated studies, and high-quality, evidence-based content.
- ▶ Regulatory Aspects: Compliance with regulations such as CE marking and FDA guidelines, proper documentation (e.g., conformity certificates), and mechanisms for managing incidents and recalls.

The 'Clinical Effectiveness (EFF)' domain in HTA evaluates whether a technology works under ideal conditions (efficacy) and in real-world healthcare settings (effectiveness). The focus is primarily on its practical application^[9]. This domain was mentioned in 42 frameworks (70%), with 81 items assigned to it. Two main categories (Clinical impact and Evidence) with 6 subcategories were established:

- ▶ Clinical Impact: Focuses on medical or behavioural outcomes, consistent content quality, and health benefits.
- ▶ Evidence: Covers evidence base, validity, and comparators, with emphasis on efficacy, accuracy, reliability, and comparison to clinical standards.

The 'Costs and Economic Evaluation (ECO)' domain in HTA informs value-for-money judgments by providing data on costs, and economic efficiency^[9]. This domain was mentioned in 32 frameworks (53%), with 65 items assigned to it. Two main categories, each with five subcategories, were identified:

- ▶ Cost: Includes the price of DHTs (e.g., purchase, subscriptions, in-app purchases), organizational costs (e.g., equipment, training, facility changes), costs to users, business models, and transparency regarding hidden or additional costs.
- ▶ Economic Assessment: Focuses on cost-effectiveness, budget impact, and return on investment.

The 'Ethical Analysis (ETH)' domain examines the social and moral norms and values relevant to the technology being assessed^[9]. This domain was mentioned in 15 frameworks (25%), with 24 items assigned to it and thus represents a domain that is not frequently covered in the frameworks. It includes five main categories:

- ▶ Transparency
- ▶ Justice and equity
- ▶ Legal obligations
- ▶ Conflict of interest
- ▶ Advertising

The 'Organisational Aspects (ORG)' domain examines how resources (e.g., materials, skills, money, attitudes) are organized for technology implementation and their impact on the organization and healthcare system^[9]. This domain was mentioned in 11 frameworks (18%), with 26 items assigned to it. The domain consists of four main categories:

- ▶ Impact on the organization
- ▶ Uptake of DHT
- ▶ Health delivery processes
- ▶ Digital literacy: Training, education, and guidance for users and healthcare professionals

The 'Patients and Social Aspects (SOC)' domain focuses on patients or individuals receiving care through the technology. Patient aspects address issues relevant to patients and caregivers, while social aspects

concern specific groups of patients or individuals of interest in an HTA^[9]. This domain was mentioned in 46 frameworks (77%), with 107 items assigned to it and thus represents a domain that often appeared in the frameworks. The whole domain encompasses three main categories:

- ▶ User experience: Further divided into subcategories, including usability, ease of use, user engagement, user inclusion, user feedback, patient empowerment, social aspects, and support.
- ▶ Accessibility
- ▶ Cultural

The 'Legal Aspects (LEG)' domain section is intended to help HTA practitioners to identify relevant rules and regulations, including those relating to patient rights, data protection and healthcare professionals^[9]. This domain was mentioned in 14 frameworks (23%), with 38 items assigned to it and thus represents a domain that is not often found in the frameworks. The domain includes five main categories:

- ▶ Data and privacy
- ▶ Security
- ▶ Transparency and disclosure
- ▶ Autonomy
- ▶ Responsibility

3.2 Request to HTA agencies

A total of 23 HTA agencies and HTA-related organizations (decision-making institutions responsible for HTA appraisal) completed the questionnaire. The countries that responded and took part in the survey were: Austria, Belgium, Croatia, Czech Republic, Finland, France, Germany, Ireland, Italy, Malta, Norway¹, Slovakia, Spain, Sweden, United Kingdom. Cyprus reported that no framework is available.

In the following chapters we will only use the term HTA agency, which includes HTA agencies and HTA-related organizations (decision-making institutions responsible for HTA appraisal).

3.2.1 Availability of frameworks/guidance documents/ guidelines to assess Digital Health Technologies

Over half of all agencies participating in the survey (61%) state that they do not have any classification or taxonomy that structures DHTs into specific groups or levels. About 35% state that their guidelines include a classification of DHTs and that they take this into account in their assessment (Figure 5). After categorizing the surveyed agencies by country, the number of statements that there is no classification regarding different groups of DHTs increases to 67%.

¹ The agency of this country did not fill out the questionnaire but answered a few questions via email.

Figure 5. Availability of frameworks/guidance/guidelines used for the assessment of DHTs in general or for specific groups of DHTs (by number of HTA agencies)

Over half (52%) of the HTA agencies stated using any frameworks/guidance documents/guidelines for assessing DHTs in general or for specific groups of DHTs. After own evaluation and review of the entire questionnaire according to countries, the number of statements that there are frameworks/guidance documents/guidelines for assessing DHTs decreased to 38%. Of the HTA agencies 52% have published or unpublished documents regarding evidence requirements or submission guidelines/templates for DHTs, while 39% do not possess such documents, and 9% find this question not applicable to their operations.

In another question, agencies were asked to indicate - if they have a framework/guidance document - what type of document it is and for which groups of DHTs and what purpose the document is intended. There is little information on the type of document, for which groups of DHTs and for what purpose the document is to be used. Only those agencies that perform an HTA of DHT themselves have responded and referred to it (i.e. Institutions responsible for appraisal did not respond).

Of all agencies 26% are currently developing a framework to be used for the assessment of DHTs. This is not the case for 26%, and 22% of the agencies did not provide any information. The question should only be answered if such a document does not yet exist. Nevertheless, another 26% stated that they already have a document².

When asked which frameworks/guidelines/guidelines the agency considers suitable for use in the HTA of DHTs, in cases where they do not yet have a specific framework of their own, the answers are very diverse. Examples include the 'GRADE evidence to decision framework' (2/23), the EUnetHTA Core Model (2/23) or 'national internal guidelines' (2/23).

3.2.2 Current gaps and weaknesses in assessing Digital Health Technologies

Regarding the question of whether the HTA agencies see any gaps and weaknesses in the methods available to HTA bodies for assessing DHTs, several respondents from the HTA agencies (5/23) point out

² The difference between these figures and the figure (52%) in the section above is because some agencies answered the question even though they should not have answered it, because they already have an assessment of DHTs. There are also some in the NAs that already have an HTA for DHTs.

that they are not in a position to provide information on HTA methodologies and their gaps and weaknesses due to a lack of knowledge and expertise.

Some agencies (4/23) stated that compliance with data protection, privacy and interoperability should be part the assessment, but currently they do not have the necessary knowledge and experience.

Furthermore, respondents (5/23) were divided on whether a single, general HTA framework should be developed and applied universally for all DHT, or whether separate HTAs should be tailored to specific groups of technologies. AI technologies were mentioned particularly frequently (7/23), also in connection with designing a separate HTA for AI applications.

The rapid technological advancement of digital health applications is highlighted by some HTA agencies (n=5/23) as one of the major weaknesses of the current HTA process. For example, an HTA agency representative noted that by the time the evaluation of a technology is completed, it may already be outdated, with a new version readily available.

Furthermore, for some of the respondents (3/23), the analysis of cost-effectiveness is an important part of the HTA for DHTs, which has not yet been sufficiently included in the assessment. However, this highlights the challenge of analysis, which is further complicated by the lack of clear guidance on assessing the cost-effectiveness of DHTs and the limited availability of clinical evidence for some technologies. In addition, the diversity of DHT in their use leads to the challenge of applying meaningful methods to assess cost-effectiveness.

Finally, some of the participating HTA agencies reported challenges in assessing clinical evidence of DHTs (4/23). Specifically, the various fields of application of DHTs, suitable comparison groups, adherence and attrition rates are mentioned (4/23). Inappropriate methodology in the studies leads to a lower and insufficient evidence base, without which no detailed cost-benefit analysis or real-world effectiveness can be calculated.

Regarding the question of how the agency addresses the challenges of assessing DHTs, international cooperation with other HTA organizations is a key approach to assessing DHTs (3/23). The survey showed that in addition to international cooperation, the HTA agencies form internal working groups to address the topic of DHT assessment, in which external experts are also consulted (3/23). Various approaches and key aspects are highlighted as areas that should receive additional attention or be more thoroughly integrated into future HTA methodologies (4/23). These include “Real-World Evidence” (RWE), “Sensitivity analyses”, and “Early value assessments” (EVA). It is also stated that various guidelines and frameworks that already exist or are under development remain one of the most important methods for assessing DHTs (6/23).

The most frequently requested addition to the HTA methods concerns the assessment of cost-effectiveness (3/23). Further analyses of the technologies, including clinical value, relative effectiveness and RCTs, are also desired (2/23). Additionally, it is mentioned that interoperability must be considered (1/23) and the requirements must remain feasible for the companies (1/23). Data protection is perceived as a gap/weakness in the current assessments. However, it was not taken up as a specific topic that should be addressed in the near future.

Overall, 11 out of 23 respondents (4 out of 10 were from the same country) tended to agree that different methods should be used at each stage of the life cycle of a DHT. Overall, 8 out of 22 respondents chose 'not applicable' because they felt they lacked sufficient knowledge on the topic to answer the question.

Most agencies (15/23) do not use different methodological requirements for HTAs depending on the life cycle, while only a few (5/23) already implement such distinctions, and a smaller portion (3/23) are considering it.

3.3 Discussion

The results of the scoping review provide an overview of the existing frameworks for the assessment of DHTs. Most frameworks relate to targeted digital health applications. The frameworks primarily aim to provide support and guidance, with varying emphases on evaluation, quality, and evidence requirements. Overall, a lifecycle approach is rarely considered, and classification schemes for DHTs were rare. Evidence requirements (referred to as “standards” in NICE terminology of) are addressed slightly more often, though the information provided is generally broad and rarely specific to different groups of DHTs.

The assessment domains covered included health problems, technical characteristics, safety, clinical effectiveness, costs, ethics, and organizational, social and legal aspects, though the depth of coverage varied. The HTA Core Model[®] is structured into nine domains, which include 51 topics addressing 145 specific issues. The present analysis identified 31 main categories and 49 subcategories, with a total of 660 assigned items. The items include repeated items across the frameworks; therefore, the number should not be interpreted as reflective of their overall importance or compared directly with the HTA Core Model. It is not always clear which items could be assigned to which domain, and duplication among domains is possible in some cases. Some of the domains are intertwined, which is also described in the EUnetHTA Core Model^[9]. Certain domains, such as technical characteristics (TEC), are frequently and comprehensively addressed in the frameworks, while others, like the ethical (ETH) and legal (LEG) domains, receive less attention. This may reflect the perceived importance of the domains in HTA, highlighting the need to give greater attention to the ELSI domains (ethical, social, and legal) ^[31]. In further steps, the categories of this analysis could be compared in detail with those of the EUnetHTA core model and supplemented so that items are as comprehensive as possible and at the same time suitable for DHT HTA.

The results of this scoping review reveal a variety of different frameworks for assessing DHTs. At the same time, it becomes clear that HTA Core Model domains are relevant, but also vary in scope. The review emphasises the need for a framework that can be used across countries.

Regarding the HTA agency survey, most of the participating agencies do not currently use a classification system for DHTs. While some agencies have frameworks or guidelines for assessing DHTs, details about the specific groups of DHTs they target remains limited. Some agencies are currently in the process of developing frameworks, while others rely on existing documents or do not provide information. Recommendations for appropriate frameworks vary, reflecting differing approaches and priorities. The

absence of comprehensive frameworks, guidelines, or guidance documents for assessing DHTs among many participating agencies highlights the opportunity to implement increased standardisation. This gap also reflects uncertainties regarding the adjustments needed in the HTA process to appropriately assess DHT.

HTA agencies report gaps in their ability to assess DHTs due to limited knowledge and expertise, particularly in areas such as data protection, privacy, and interoperability. There is also debate about whether a universal HTA approach should be applied to all DHTs or if assessments are needed for specific types of technologies. Key challenges include the rapid technological progress, the lack of guidance on methods for sufficient cost-effectiveness analysis, and difficulties in developing suitable study designs. Many agencies emphasize the need for international cooperation and harmonization of guidelines, as well as the consideration of real-world evidence and early value assessments. Additionally, there is a call for methodologies to remain practical and feasible for companies to implement. The practice of adapting methodological approaches based on the life cycle of a technology is still not widespread among agencies, though there is some emerging consideration of this approach.

3.3.1 Limitations

Although this Scoping Review was conducted following the guidance provided by the Joanna Briggs Institute Reviewer Manual ^[14] in accordance with the PRISMA-ScR guidelines^[15], some limitations should be acknowledged.

Firstly, a limitation of the work is probably the time constraints in the search for relevant literature. Relevant frameworks may have been excluded if frameworks were published before or after the search period. There was also a language restriction in the search for frameworks. On the other hand, some of the frameworks identified in this review also date back to the early part of the specified time period and may no longer reflect current developments. Secondly, the scoping review had a specific perspective and included studies related to explicit frameworks that are related to the HTA domains of the EUnetHTA Core Model^[9]. The use of keywords such as ‘framework’ in the search strategy may have been limiting, but on the other hand, this limitation was compensated by a comprehensive hand search. Another potential limitation of the work is that much of the literature was identified by hand search, which may mean that the search strategy was not comprehensive enough. However, some of the frameworks are only accessible on websites of the HTA agencies and could not have been identified via the databases. The use of numerous sources can also be considered a strength of this analysis. Lastly, a methodological limitation could be that the categorisation was not entirely objective. This is an inherent limitation of qualitative reviews and synthesis. To address this, all categorizations were cross-checked by at least one additional reviewer, and discussions within the team were conducted to ensure balance and accuracy.

In summary, while these limitations highlight areas for improvement, they are counterbalanced by measures taken to enhance the robustness of the review, such as the use of diverse sources and rigorous cross-checking procedures.

3.4 Conclusion

The review highlights several frameworks for assessing DHTs, most of which focus on the type of digital health applications and vary in their emphasis on evidence requirements. The life cycle approach is rarely mentioned in frameworks and classification methods for DHTs are rare. The HTA agency survey identifies a need for a standardized, internationally applicable framework, as current frameworks are diverse and inconsistent across agencies. However, gaps in expertise and challenges related to data protection, privacy, and interoperability remain. Agencies emphasize the need for international cooperation and adaptable methodologies. Agencies also see potential regarding HTA methods for assessing cost-effectiveness. The review reveals considerable variability among the frameworks, which address HTA domains to differing extents. A future standardised framework with explanations on the methodological approach to the assessment of DHT is relevant, as this is currently also desired by many agencies.

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APPENDIX

Appendix 1 Search String

PubMed

#		Results (25 Apr 2024)
1	"telemedicine"[MeSH Terms] OR "digital technology"[MeSH Terms] OR "mobile applications"[MeSH Terms] OR "monitoring, ambulatory" [MeSH Terms] OR "digital health"[tiab] OR "digital therapeutic"[tiab] OR "digital health application*"[tiab] OR "DiHA"[tiab] OR "mobile health" [tiab] OR "mHealth"[tiab] OR "telehealth"[tiab] OR "telecare"[tiab] OR "web based intervention*"[tiab] OR "internet based intervention*"[tiab] OR "artificial intelligence"[tiab] OR "medical artificial intelligence"[tiab] OR "medical AI"[tiab]	160,953
2	(technology assessment, biomedical [MeSH Terms] OR "evaluat*"[tiab] OR "apprais*"[tiab] OR "appraisal"[tiab] OR "health technology assessment"[tiab] OR HTA [tiab] OR "technology assessment*"[tiab] OR "technology evaluation*"[tiab])	4,706,876
3	("framework*"[tiab] OR "guideline*" [tiab] OR "guidance*" [tiab])	1,081,521
4	("health" [MeSH Terms] OR "medicine" [MeSH Terms] OR "therapeutics" [MeSH Terms])	6,549,808
	((1 AND (2 AND 3)) AND 4) and 2015-2024	1,976

Embase

No.	Query	Results	Results Date
#35.	#33 NOT #34	2,931	25 Apr 2024
#34.	#33 AND 'conference abstract'/it	1,283	25 Apr 2024
#33.	#32 AND [2015-2024]/py	4,214	25 Apr 2024
#32.	#17 AND #23 AND #27 AND #31	4,872	25 Apr 2024
#31.	#28 OR #29 OR #30	14,623,066	25 Apr 2024
#30.	'therapy'/exp	11,118,470	25 Apr 2024
#29.	'medicine'/exp	4,344,613	25 Apr 2024

#28.	'health'/exp	945,962	25 Apr 2024
#27.	#24 OR #25 OR #26	1,441,475	25 Apr 2024
#26.	'guidance*':ti,ab	243,995	25 Apr 2024
#25.	'guideline*':ti,ab	783,688	25 Apr 2024
#24.	'framework*':ti,ab	473,657	25 Apr 2024
#23.	#18 OR #19 OR #20 OR #21 OR #22	6,580,276	25 Apr 2024
#22.	'technology assessment*':ti,ab	12,407	25 Apr 2024
#21.	hta:ti,ab	9,870	25 Apr 2024
#20.	'apprais*':ti,ab	91,878	25 Apr 2024
#19.	'evaluat*':ti,ab	6,498,514	25 Apr 2024
#18.	'biomedical technology assessment'/exp	18,176	25 Apr 2024
#17.	#1 OR #2 OR #3 OR #4 OR #5 OR #6 OR #7 OR #8 OR #9 OR #10 OR #11 OR #12 OR #13 OR #14 OR #15 OR #16	184,752	25 Apr 2024
#16.	'medical ai':ti,ab	233	25 Apr 2024
#15.	'artificial intelligence':ti,ab	49,173	25 Apr 2024
#14.	'internet based intervention*':ti,ab	980	25 Apr 2024
#13.	'web based intervention*':ti,ab	1,671	25 Apr 2024
#12.	'telecare':ti,ab	1,024	25 Apr 2024
#11.	'telehealth':ti,ab	16,865	25 Apr 2024
#10.	'mhealth':ti,ab	6,990	25 Apr 2024
#9.	'mobile health':ti,ab	7,465	25 Apr 2024
#8.	diha:ti,ab	64	25 Apr 2024
#7.	'digital health application*':ti,ab	327	25 Apr 2024
#6.	'digital therapeutic':ti,ab	347	25 Apr 2024

#5.	'digital health':ti,ab	7,142	25 Apr 2024
#4.	'ambulatory monitoring'/exp	12,359	25 Apr 2024
#3.	'mobile application'/exp	28,033	25 Apr 2024
#2.	'digital technology'/exp	5,754	25 Apr 2024
#1.	'telemedicine'/exp	76,005	25 Apr 2024

Appendix 2 Questionnaire

Part 1 – Availability of frameworks/guidance documents/ guidelines to assess Digital Health Technologies (DHTs)

Question	Answer	Reference (link)
Does your agency use a classification/grouping system or a taxonomy to assign specific DHTs to groups/levels/tiers within the framework (guidance document/guideline) to determine specific assessment or evidence requirements/standards? If yes, please provide a reference/link and/or attach a copy of any unpublished document.		
Does your agency have any frameworks/guidance documents/guidelines that are used for assessing DHTs in general or for specific groups of DHTs?		
If yes, please briefly specify what document type it is and for which groups of DHTs and purpose the document is intended to use. If unpublished, please attach a copy of the document with your responses.	Document type:	
	Types/groups/tiers of DHT addressed:	
	Purpose of the document:	
Does your agency have any published or unpublished documents on evidence requirements or submission guidelines/templates for DHTs? If yes, please provide a link or attach with your responses.		
If no such document already exists: is your organization currently developing or adapting a framework (guidance document/guideline) to be used for assessing DHTs?		
If no DHT-specific framework/guidance document/guideline is available, what frameworks/guidance documents/guidelines does your agency consider appropriate for use in Health Technology Assessment (HTA) of DHTs?		

Part 2 – Currents status of assessed DHTs

Question	Answer	Reference (link)
Which digital health technologies have been evaluated by your agency so far? Please provide us with a link where we can access these documents or send us the evaluation documents by e-mail.		
Which digital health technologies are currently evaluated by your agency? If possible, please provide us with a link to a listing of these technologies, or mention them directly.		

Part 3 – Current gaps and weaknesses in assessing DHTs

Question	Answer	Reference (link)
Do you see any gaps and weaknesses in the methods available to HTA bodies for assessing DHTs?		
How does your agency approach these challenges of assessing DHT?		
Which possible future approaches to overcome challenges in assessing DHTs do you suggest?		
Do different methods should be used at each stage of the lifecycle of a DHT? While we concentrate on the health technology assessment stage, there may be different methods for market access or post-marketing surveillance. Please shortly explain.		
Does your agency already use different methodological requirements for an HTA depending on the life cycle?		

Part 4 – Request for an expert specialized in AI

The Big Data Unit of the Andalusian public Progress and Health Foundation (Big Data-FPS) requests a nomination of an expert specialized in AI from your agency to participate in the following research.

Big Data-FPS will circulate questionnaire/s (as part of an online Delphi approach) to HTA experts specialized in AI. Questions included will pertain to the development of validation methods for AI-based decision support systems. The inquiries will focus on guidance for the validation of these systems, optimization of algorithms, and strategies for estimating predictive abilities using real-world data.

- Not-applicable: 'The scope of the questions is outside of our agency remit'
- Contact details: Name and e-mail address

Appendix 3 Included frameworks

Study Abbreviation	Author (et al.)	Published Year	Title
Agarwal 2016	Agarwal, S. et al.	2016	Guidelines for reporting of health interventions using mobile phones: mobile health (mHealth) evidence reporting and assessment (mERA) checklist
Agency for Healthcare Research and Quality 2022	Agency for Healthcare Research and Quality	2022	Evaluation of Mental Health Mobile Applications
American Psychiatric Association 2019	American Psychiatric Association	2019	App Evaluation Model
Anxiety and Depression Association of America 2022	Anxiety and Depression Association of America	2022	Mental Health Apps Assessment Model
AQuAS 2023	Segur-Ferrer, J. et al.	2023	Health Technology Assessment Framework: Adaptation for Digital Health Technology Assessment.
Baumel 2017	Baumel, A. et al.	2017	Enlight: A Comprehensive Quality and Therapeutic Potential Evaluation Tool for Mobile and Web-Based eHealth Interventions
Bertl 2023	Bertl, M. et al.	2023	Systematic AI Support for Decision-Making in the Healthcare Sector: Obstacles and Success Factors
Betton 2017	Betton, V et al.	2017	Framework for the effectiveness evaluation of mobile (mental) health tools
BfArM 2020	Bundesinstitut für Arzneimittel und Medizinprodukte (BfArM)	2020	The Fast-Track Process for Digital Health Applications (DiGA) according to Section 139e SGB V A Guide for Manufacturers, Service Providers and Users
Biswas 2021	Biswas, M. et al.	2021	ACCU3RATE: A mobile health application rating scale based on user reviews
Bongiovanni-Delarozière 2017	Bongiovanni-Delarozière, I. et al.	2017	Economic evaluation methods applied to telemedicine: From a literature review to a standardized framework
British Standards Institution 2015	British Standards Institution	2015	Health and wellness apps “Quality criteria across the life cycle” Code of practice
Camacho 2020	Camacho, E. et al.	2020	Technology Evaluation and Assessment Criteria for Health Apps (TEACH-Apps): Pilot Study.

Study Abbreviation	Author (et al.)	Published Year	Title
Chan 2015	Chan, S. et al.	2015	Towards a Framework for Evaluating Mobile Mental Health Apps
Coravos 2020	Coravos, A. et al.	2020	Modernizing and designing evaluation frameworks for connected sensor technologies in medicine
Dawson 2020	Dawson, R.M. et al.	2020	What makes a good health 'app'? Identifying the strengths and limitations of existing mobile application evaluation tools
Defense Health Agency 2018	Defense Health Agency	2018	U.S. Department of Defense Mobile Health Practice Guide
Digital Health Assessment Framework, ORCHA, 2022	ORCHA	2022	Digital Health Assessment Framework, ORCHA
Digital Therapeutics Alliance 2022	Digital Therapeutics Alliance	2022	DTx Value Assessment & Integration Guide
Dulude 2023	Dulude, C. et al.	2023	A pediatric virtual care evaluation framework and its evolution using consensus methods
Haute Autorité de Santé 2016	Haute Autorité de Santé	2016	Good Practice Guidelines on Health Apps and Smart Devices (Mobile Health or mHealth)
Haverinen 2019	Haverinen, J. et al.	2019	Digi-HTA: Health technology assessment framework for digital healthcare services
Henson 2019	Henson, P. et al.	2019	Deriving a practical framework for the evaluation of health apps
Hussain 2021	Hussain, MS.et al	2021	Technology assessment framework for precision health applications.
ISO 2021	ISO	2021	ISO/TS 82304-2:2021(en) Health software "Part 2: Health and wellness apps" Quality and reliability
KNMG 2016	KNMG	2016	Medical App Checker: Evaluation of Mobile Medical Apps
Kowatsch 2019	Kowatsch, T. et al.	2019	A design and evaluation framework for digital health interventions
Lagan 2021a	Lagan, S. et al.	2021a	Evaluating evaluation frameworks: A scoping review of frameworks for assessing health apps
Lagan 2021b	Lagan, S. et al.	2021b	Mental Health App Evaluation: Updating the American Psychiatric Association's Framework Through a Stakeholder-Engaged Workshop.

Study Abbreviation	Author (et al.)	Published Year	Title
Lantzsch 2022	Lantzsch, H. et al.	2022	Benefit Assessment and Reimbursement of Digital Health Applications: Concepts for Setting Up a New System for Public Coverage
Leigh 2017	Leigh, S. et al.	2017	Effective? Engaging? Secure? Applying the ORCHA-24 framework to evaluate apps for chronic insomnia disorder
Levine 2020	Levine, D. et al.	2020	Design and testing of a mobile health application rating tool
Mackey 2022	Mackey, R. et al.	2022	A Novel Method for Evaluating Mobile Apps (App Rating Inventory): Development Study
Mathews 2019	Mathews, S. et al.	2019	Digital health: a path to validation
McMillan 2016	McMillan, B. et al.	2016	Quality assessment of a sample of mobile app-based health behavior change interventions using a tool based on the National Institute of Health and Care Excellence behavior change guidance
Mental Health Commission 2018	Mental Health Commission	2018	Mental Health Apps: How to Make an Informed Choice
mhealth Belgium 2024	mhealth Belgium	2024	mHealthBELGIUM Validation pyramid
Moshi 2020	Moshi MR. et al.	2020	Development of a health technology assessment module for evaluating mobile medical applications.
Murray 2016	Murray, E. et al.	2016	Evaluating Digital Health Interventions
National Institute for Health and Care Excellence 2022	National Institute for Health and Care Excellence	2022	Evidence standards framework (ESF) for digital health technologies
National Library of Medicine 2022	National Library of Medicine	2022	Evaluating Mobile Apps
Nebeker 2020	Nebeker, C. et al.	2020	Development of a decision-making checklist tool to support technology selection in digital health research
NHS Digital 2019	NHS Digital	2019	Digital Assessment Questions V2.2
NHS England 2021	NHS England	2021	Digital Technology Assessment Criteria (DTAC)
NordDEC 2024	NordDEC	2024	NORDIC DIGITAL HEALTH EVALUATION CRITERIA ONE ASSESSMENT TO MEET THE DIGITAL HEALTH EVALUATION REQUIREMENTS IN DENMARK, FINLAND, ICELAND, NORWAY, AND SWEDEN.

Study Abbreviation	Author (et al.)	Published Year	Title
Nouri 2018	Nouri, R. et al.	2018	Criteria for assessing the quality of mHealth apps: a systematic review
O'Rourke 2020	O'Rourke, T. et al.	2020	Development of a Multidimensional App-Quality Assessment Tool for Health-Related Apps (AQUA)
Pearson 2023	Pearson, SD. et al.	2023	Institute for Clinical and Economic Review, Peterson Health Technology Institute value assessment framework for digital health technologies
Quintana 2020	Quintana, Y. & Torous, J.	2020	A Framework for Evaluation of Mobile Apps for Youth Mental Health
Roberts 2021	Roberts, AE. Et al.	2021	Evaluating the quality and safety of health-related apps and e-tools: Adapting the Mobile App Rating Scale and developing a quality assurance protocol
Silberman 2023	Silberman, J. et al.	2023	Rigorous and rapid evidence assessment in digital health with the evidence DEFINED framework
Stoyanov 2015	Stoyanov, SR. et al.	2015	Mobile App Rating Scale: A New Tool for Assessing the Quality of Health Mobile Apps
Tarricone 2022	Tarricone R. et al.	2022	Recommendations for developing a lifecycle, multidimensional assessment framework for mobile medical apps.
Vokinger 2020	Vokinger, KN. et al.	2020	Digital health and the COVID-19 epidemic: an assessment framework for apps from an epidemiological and legal perspective
Wagneur 2022	Wagneur, N. et al.	2022	Assessing a New Prescreening Score for the Simplified Evaluation of the Clinical Quality and Relevance of eHealth Apps: Instrument Validation Study
Wu 2021	Wu, K-L. et al.	2021	Characteristics and Quality of Mobile Apps Containing Prenatal Genetic Testing Information: Systematic App Store Search and Assessment
Wyatt 2015	Wyatt, J. et al.	2015	What makes a good clinical app? Introducing the RCP Health Informatics Unit checklist
Wykes 2019	Wykes, T. & Schueller, S.	2019	Why Reviewing Apps Is Not Enough: Transparency for Trust (T4T) Principles of Responsible Health App Marketplaces
Xcertia 2019	Xcertia	2019	Xcertia mHealth App Guidelines
Zelmer 2018	Zelmer, J. et al.	2018	An Assessment Framework for e-Mental Health Apps in Canada: Results of a Modified Delphi Process

Appendix 4 Summary of the coverage of the HTA domains for each framework

Framework	Health problem and current use of technology (CUR)	Description and technical characteristics of technology (TEC)	Safety (SAF)	Clinical effectiveness (EFF)	Cost and economic evaluation (ECO)	Ethical analysis (ETH)	Organisational aspects (ORG)	Patients and Social aspects (SOC)	Legal aspects (LEG)
Agarwal 2016		x	x		x			x	
Agency for Healthcare Research and Quality 2022		x	x	x	x			x	x
American Psychiatric Association 2019		x	x	x	x	x		x	x
Anxiety and Depression Association of America 2022		x		x				x	
AQuAS 2023	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
Baumel 2017		x		x				x	
Bertl 2023		x							
Betton 2017	x	x		x	x				
BfArM 2020		x	x	x		x	x		
Biswas 2021		x						x	
Bongiovanni-Delarozière 2017	x				x		x	x	
British Standards Institution 2015		x							

Framework	Health problem and current use of technology (CUR)	Description and technical characteristics of technology (TEC)	Safety (SAF)	Clinical effectiveness (EFF)	Cost and economic evaluation (ECO)	Ethical analysis (ETH)	Organisational aspects (ORG)	Patients and Social aspects (SOC)	Legal aspects (LEG)
Camacho 2020		x			x				
Chan 2015		x		x				x	
Coravos 2020		x	x	x	x			x	
Dawson 2020				x				x	
Defense Health Agency 2018		x						x	
Digital Health Assessment Framework, ORCHA, 2022		x						x	
Digital Therapeutics Alliance 2022		x		x	x			x	
Dulude 2023	x			x					
Haute Autorité de Santé 2016		x	x	x	x		x	x	x
Haverinen 2019	x	x	x	x	x			x	
Henson 2019		x		x	x			x	x
Hussain 2021		x		x				x	
ISO 2021	x	x	x	x		x		x	
KNMG 2016		x	x	x				x	
Kowatsch 2019		x	x	x		x		x	

Framework	Health problem and current use of technology (CUR)	Description and technical characteristics of technology (TEC)	Safety (SAF)	Clinical effectiveness (EFF)	Cost and economic evaluation (ECO)	Ethical analysis (ETH)	Organisational aspects (ORG)	Patients and Social aspects (SOC)	Legal aspects (LEG)
Lagan 2021a		x						x	
Lagan 2021b		x		x	x				
Lantzsch 2022				x					
Leigh 2017		x		x				x	
Levine 2020		x	x		x		x	x	
Mackey 2022		x		x				x	
Mathews 2019		x		x	x		x	x	
McMillan 2016	x	x	x	x				x	
Mental Health Commission 2018	x	x	x	x	x	x		x	x
mHealthBELGIUM	x	x	x	x	x		x		
Moshi 2020	x	x		x	x	x	x	x	x
Murray 2016	x	x	x	x	x		x	x	
National Institute for Health and Care Excellence 2022	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	
National Library of Medicine 2022		x		x	x	x		x	
Nebeker 2020		x	x	x		x		x	
NHS Digital 2019		x	x	x	x			x	

Framework	Health problem and current use of technology (CUR)	Description and technical characteristics of technology (TEC)	Safety (SAF)	Clinical effectiveness (EFF)	Cost and economic evaluation (ECO)	Ethical analysis (ETH)	Organisational aspects (ORG)	Patients and Social aspects (SOC)	Legal aspects (LEG)
NHS England 2021		x	x					x	
NordDEC 2024		x	x					x	x
Nouri 2018		x	x					x	x
O'Rourke 2020	x	x		x	x			x	x
Pearson 2023			x	x	x				
Quintana 2020	x	x		x	x	x		x	x
Roberts 2021	x	x						x	
Silberman 2023 ³									
Stoyanov 2015		x		x	x			x	
Tarricone 2022				x	x	x	x	x	
Vokinger 2020	x	x	x	x	x	x		x	x
Wagneur 2022	x	x			x		x	x	
Wu 2021		x	x	x	x				
Wyatt 2015	x	x	x	x	x				
Wykes 2019	x	x		x					
Xcertia 2019	x	x	x			x		x	x

³ Framework of Silbermann et al. does not contain any crosses, as it could not be assigned to any HTA domains after review. However, it was included as a framework because it contains the “Checklist of Evidence Quality Criteria for Digital Health Interventions” and data was extracted for “evidence requirements”.

Framework	Health problem and current use of technology (CUR)	Description and technical characteristics of technology (TEC)	Safety (SAF)	Clinical effectiveness (EFF)	Cost and economic evaluation (ECO)	Ethical analysis (ETH)	Organisational aspects (ORG)	Patients and Social aspects (SOC)	Legal aspects (LEG)
Zelmer 2018	x	x		x	x	x		x	x

Note: x=Coverage

Appendix 5 Frequency analysis of the HTA domains and associated items, derived from included frameworks

HTA Domain	Main	Subcategory (if available)	No. of frameworks the categorisation is based on	No. of items assigned to domain
Health problem and current use (CUR)	Target user			13
	Intended use			14
	Product purpose & credibility			14
Total			21	41
Description and technical characteristics (TEC)	Features	Purpose		11
		Function		16
		Performance		2
		Description & product information		18
		Layout		13
	Implementation	Access control		2
		Infrastructure		14
		User engagement		6
	Technical aspects	Data protection		10
		Data security & privacy		50
		Interoperability, Connectivity & Data sharing		22
		Transparency & Control		7
		Technical stability & service		6
		Updates & maintenance		14
	Data management		17	
Total			45	208
Safety (SAF)	Clinical safety	Harm consideration		14
		Risk assessment		10
		Professional assurance		5
		Risk preventive measures		3
		Company's measures		5
	Technical safety	User protection		7
		Quality of information		6
	Regulatory aspects	Compliance with requirements		11

HTA Domain	Main	Subcategory (if available)	No. of frameworks the categorisation is based on	No. of items assigned to domain
		Documentation		6
		3rd-party connection		1
		Recall system		1
		Non-medical device declaration		2
	Total		27	71
Clinical Effectiveness (EFF)	Clinical impact	Medical focus		10
		Content quality		16
		Clinical benefit		15
	Evidence requirements	Evidence base		28
		Validity		10
		Comparator		3
	Total		43	81
Cost and economic evaluation (ECO)	Cost	Business model		8
		Cost to organization		10
		Cost to users (direct and indirect)		5
		Price of DHT		4
		Transparency		20
		Reimbursement		10
	Economic Assessment	Economic benefit		6
		Economic evaluation		2
	Total		32	65
Ethical analysis (ETH)	Transparency			8
	Justice & Equity			8
	Legal obligations			3
	Conflict of interest			4
	Advertising			1
	Total		15	24
Organisational aspects (ORG)	Impact on organization			13
	Uptake of DHT			4
	Health delivery process			7
	Digital literacy & Guidance			5

HTA Domain	Main	Subcategory (if available)	No. of frameworks the categorisation is based on	No. of items assigned to domain
Total			12	29
Patient and social aspects (SOC)	User experience	Usability		32
		Ease of Use		12
		User engagement		9
		User inclusion		11
		User feedback		18
		Patient empowerment		2
		Social aspects		2
		Support		2
	Accessibility			16
Cultural appropriateness			3	
Total			46	107
Legal aspects (LEG)	Data and Privacy			15
	Security			4
	Transparency & Disclosure			9
	Autonomy			3
	Responsibility			7
Total			14	38

Appendix 6 HTA domains, categories and associated items, derived from included frameworks

Health Problem and Current Use of the Technology (CUR)

Category	Subcategory	Item	Reference
Target User		Who is the intended audience for the app? Is it clear who should or should not be using it?	Mental Health Commission 2018
Target User		11. Audience Is it clear who the intended consumer group(s) is and what issues the app aims to address?	Zelmer 2018
Target User		1-a) Is it clear who this app is for and how it should be used? Yes / No / Don't know	Wyatt 2015
Target User		Age of targeted population: <18 (pediatrics) or 18-64 or >65	Wagneuer 2022
Target User		Intended Use: The app clearly identifies the target condition and target audience.	Quintana 2020
Target User		Is the DHI likely to reach this population, and if so, is the population likely to use it?	Murray 2016
Target User		Is the app aimed at the right level for the target population?	McMillan 2016
Target User		Who are the intended users of the health app?	ISO 2021
Target User		What is the intended use of the product? — What are the intended user groups?	Haverinen 2019
Target User		> Will there be a demand for your tool? -Q2. Describe the problem or unmet need that your digital product addresses -Q3. How do you know this is a problem/need (link to research evidence, work with users etc)? -...	Betton 2017
Target User		Is the app for individual use or to be used in collaboration with a provider?	Roberts 2021
Target User		Level 3 (1) description of the target group Methods: Checklist for the application Evidence requirements: systematic research and clinical studies, epidemiological studies	mHealthBELGIUM
Target User		Tier A + B + C (1) Intended purpose and target population [ED] Methods: The size of the target population should be calculated using appropriate and current national or local sources (for example, accurate epidemiological data of prevalence and incidence of the relevant health problem), or expert estimates if this is not available. Note that NICE's resource impact assessment manual describes an approach to calculating population size Tier A: Evidence requirements: Description of intended purpose, group that benefits from using the DHT (e.g., service users, clinical staff, etc.) including any subgroups, size of target group based on national and local sources or expert estimates, expected uptake profile (proportion of people in target group who are expected to use DHT and usage rates) Tier B: Evidence requirements: Description of intended purpose, group that benefits from using the DHT, size of target population based on national and local sources or expert estimates, expected uptake profile (proportion of people in target population who are expected to use DHT and usage rates) Tier C: Evidence requirements: Description of intended purpose, target population (defined by health condition and place in care pathway - intended population will be defined in information on device), size of target population based on national and local sources or expert estimates, expected uptake profile (proportion of people in target population who are expected to use DHT and usage rates)	National Institute for Health and Care Excellence 2022
Intended use		> How does your tool solve the unmet need: who will use your tool and what will be the impact? -Q17. Who will be primarily using your digital product? This can be more than one group. (e.g. the young person) -...	Betton 2017
Intended use		Demand: Will relevant stakeholders use it?	Roberts 2021

Intended use		Specialty concerned by the solution (2 items maximum per solution) Oncology, Cardiology [...]	Wagneuer 2022
Intended use		Multiple health issues/symptoms (Section F): Does it address more than one symptom or health issue? 1 No - addresses one symptom/health issue only 3 Some -addresses some symptoms/health issues; or considers many but only partly address them 5 Yes - considers multiple symptoms/health issues and related ones, and sufficiently addresses them	Roberts 2021
Intended use		Intended Use: The app clearly identifies the target condition and target audience.	Quintana 2020
Intended use		Is there a clear health need which this DHI is intended to address?	Murray 2016
Intended use		Is the target behaviour clearly specified? Does the app focus on initiation of behaviour change? Does the app assess capability to change?	McMillan 2016
Intended use		For which health issue(s) and/or health need(s) is the health app intended?	ISO 2021
Intended use		Rationale for use: -The intended purpose of the MMA (i.e. diagnose, treat, inform clinical management, clinical management) -The healthcare condition or situation that the MMA addresses - MMA input (i.e. image, physiological status, symptoms, etc.) - MMA algorithm (i.e. equations, analysis engine model logic, algorithm, etc.) - MMA output (i.e. inform, treat, diagnose)	Moshi 2020
Intended use		Health Outcome -Physical -Mental & Behavioural -Quality of life	Dulude 2023
Intended use		Level 3 (2) description of the pathology, incl. Incidence, prevalence, morbidity and mortality Methods: Checklist for the application Evidence requirements: systematic research and clinical studies, epidemiological studies	mHealthBELGIUM
Intended use		Description of health problem (2) Current pathway or system process [ED] Methods: Map out existing care pathway or system processes for intended purpose and population. Use stepwise approach Evidence requirements: National clinical guidelines, guidance or academic literature, and consultation with healthcare professionals and service users	AQuAS 2023
Intended use		(3) Proposed pathway or system process using DHT [ED] Methods: None stated Evidence requirements: How proposed care pathway or system process using DHT will be different to current one, including if it replaces or complements standard care, changes to infrastructure, implementation and training needs, barriers to implementation	National Institute for Health and Care Excellence 2023
Product Purpose & Credibility		Who developed the app, and what's inside it? 1-b) Is it clear which problem the app is designed to alleviate or what outcome it helps to promote? Yes / No / Don't know	Wyatt 2015
Product Purpose & Credibility		Is there a credible causal explanation for the DHI to achieve the desired impact?	Murray 2016
Product Purpose & Credibility		Is the DHI likely to reach this population, and if so, is the population likely to use it? Is the purpose of the app clear? Are the likely outcomes clearly specified?	McMillan 2016

Product Purpose & Credibility		Are age restrictions of the intended users or subjects of care made clear to potential customers and users? What is the intended use or purpose of the health app?	ISO 2021
Product Purpose & Credibility		Is the aim of the product to replace any existing healthcare services? — Does the introduction of the product cause any changes to the premises, information systems, or care processes? — Is the product already in use elsewhere in Finland or worldwide? Where, and for how long?	Haverinen 2019
Product Purpose & Credibility		Goals (Section D): Does app/e-tool have specific, measurable and achievable goals (are these goals specified/obvious within the app/e-tool)? N/A Description does not list goals, or app/e-tool goals are irrelevant to research goal (e.g. using a game for educational purposes) 1 App/e-tool has no chance of achieving its stated goals 2 Description lists some goals, but app/e-tool has very little chance of achieving them 3 OK. App/e-tool has clear goals, which may be achievable. 4 App/e-tool has clearly specified goals, which are measurable and achievable 5 App/e-tool has specific and measurable goals, which are highly likely to be achieved	Roberts 2021
Product Purpose & Credibility		Credibility of source (Section D): does the information within the app/e-tool seem to come from a credible source? 1 Source identified but legitimacy/trustworthiness of source is questionable (e.g. commercial business with vested interest) 2 Appears to come from a legitimate source, but it cannot be verified (e.g. has no webpage) 3 Developed by small NGO/institution (hospital/centre, etc.) /specialised commercial business, funding body 4 Developed by government, university or as above but larger in scale 5 Developed using nationally competitive government or research funding (e.g. Australian Research Council, NHMRC)	Roberts 2021
Product Purpose & Credibility		[C1 Credible Information Sources] - C1.01 The app should specify the source of content with documentation. Is it based on content from a recognized source (e.g., guidelines from a public or private entity) with, and documentation (e.g., link to journal article, medical textbook citation) about the information source and copyright compliance is provided. The source should point to current and accepted protocols and guidelines. Additionally, the content within the application should align and not deviate from the referenced source. - C1.02 If the app is based on content other than from a recognized source, documentation about how and when the content was formulated is provided, including information regarding its relevancy and reliability. - C1.03 If a previous version of an app or its content becomes medically dangerous due to updated current medical guidelines, the app publisher has a documented process and annual review period or mechanism to update or retract the outdated content version and notify users. [C2 Current Information] - C2.01 Documentation about the source of the apps content and explanation as to why it is deemed to be up-to-date is provided. - C2.02 The date(s)/source(s) of the apps content is provided through an About section (tab, button or equivalent). - C2.03 The app publisher has a method or protocol for determining if an apps content requires updating to remain up-to-date. The app publisher will provide an annual review schedule to ensure that content contained in the app is up to date. - C2.04 The app publisher has a method or protocol for updating the apps content when new or changing information warrants. Updates should include a description of and documentation for each change and be made readily available for app users to identify the timing up these updates. - C2.05 Any significant deviations in an apps content from the original source (e.g., excerpts, abbreviated versions) are indicated and explained [C3 Information Accuracy] - C3.01 documentation is provided to substantiate any claims made in the description and/or content. - C3.02 Disclosures are provided, as needed, to prevent deception. Such disclosures shall be presented in a clear and	Xcertia 2019

		conspicuous manner. - C3.03 Disclosures are provided, as needed, if the app requires an additional fee(s) (e.g., subscription fee) in order to fully access the app, its associated functionality, and/or content.	
Product Purpose & Credibility		11) Does the app create accurate measurements? (Information accuracy) 12) Does the app ensure that personalised data tailored to end-users are precise? (Information accuracy) 13) Is the information gathered and/or provided by the app backed by robust research? (Information accuracy) 14) Does the app provide regular updates to contents based on improved research and recommendations? (Information accuracy)	Vokinger 2020
Product Purpose & Credibility		Content Review: The app clearly indicates who reviewed the content and when the content was last updated. Any relevant conflict of interest of contributing authors must be disclosed.	Quintana 2020
Product Purpose & Credibility		3. Content Information: The information is depicted in a coherent way (complexity, grammar, etc.). Completeness & Conciseness The content is complete, but not redundant or irrelevant. Goal & Purpose: The goal and purpose of the app is clear. Sequence: The sequence of elements (features, images, exercises, etc.) is reasonable. 6. Security (expert-specific) Credibility: The app was developed by a credible source (existing website, contact information, etc.).	O'Rourke 2020
Product Purpose & Credibility		1) Does the app have a clearly stated, understandable purpose for data collection and analysis? (Purpose)	Vokinger 2020
Product Purpose & Credibility		Were the target users involved in the development and testing of the app to ensure it responds to their needs and expectations? How diverse was the user input? Were people from a variety of populations with unique mental health challenges involved (e.g. immigrant, refugee, ethnocultural and racialized communities, First Nations, Inuit, Māori, LGBTQ2+, people who are homeless, seniors, youth)? Are health professionals involved in the development of the health app?	Bongiovanni-Delarozière 2017
Product Purpose & Credibility		Development Characteristics (1) how were target users involved in the initial design? (2) how were target users involved in usability evaluations? (3) has usability been independently evaluated?	Wykes 2019

Description and Technical Characteristics of technology (TEC)

Category	Subcategory	Item	Reference
Features	Purpose	Is the postulated purpose backed by scientific research? (Purpose)	Vokinger 2020
Features	Purpose	Are the intended goals achievable, measurable? (Purpose)	Vokinger 2020
Features	Purpose	Is regular feedback provided on the achievement of goals? (Purpose)	Vokinger 2020
Features	Purpose	First impressions > What does it claim to do vs. what does it actually do?	Henson 2019
Features	Purpose	What does the app do? What is its use case?	Zelmer 2018
Features	Purpose	What is the app's intended purpose? Can it actually do what it says it will? Is there proof?	Mental Health Commission 2018
Features	Purpose	Does the app appear to do what it claims to do?	American Psychiatric Association 2019
Features	Purpose	>Goals: Does app have specific, measurable and achievable goals (specified in app store description or within the app itself)?	Stoyanov 2015
Features	Purpose	Does the app claim to be medical?	American Psychiatric Association 2019
Features	Purpose	Level 2 +3 (2) Identification of the person in need of care	mHealthBELGIUM

		Methods: Checklist for the application Evidence requirements: using a Social Security Identification Number (SSIN)	
Features	Function	Level 2 +3 (3) App user authentication Methods: Checklist for the application Evidence requirements: either by using (I) a method integrated within the Federal Authentication Service (FAS) of a level equal to or higher than the level determined by the Board of Directors of the eHealth platform ; (II) or by an authentication system specific to the provider, provided that the three following conditions are met: (a) a registration of the identity takes place on the basis of a one-off use of an authentication method integrated in the FAS of a level that is equal to or higher than the level determined by the Board of Directors of the eHealth platform and (b) the allocation of the authentication method used in the authentication system specific to the provider after registration meets the conditions for an assurance level of 'substantial' in the eIDAS Regulation as stated in sections 2.1., 2.2.1. element 2, 2.3. and 2.4. of the annex of the Commission Implementing Regulation (EU) 2015/1502 of the eIDAS Regulation and © the authentication method used in the authentication system specific to the provider meets the requirements for an assurance level 'low' in the sections 2.2.1 element 1, 2.2.2., 2.2.3. and 2.2.4. of the annex of the Commission Implementing Regulation (EU) 2015/1502 of the eIDAS Regulation, and is designed in such a way that it can be assumed to be used only by the person to whom it belongs."	mHealthBELGIUM
Features	Function	[U6 Notifications, Alerts & Alarms] U6.01 Safety-critical alarms should utilize redundant signals to the user (e.g., visual, audible, tactile). U6.02 Users should be forced to acknowledge alarms before moving forward with other tasks. U6.03 Users should be given the choice to opt out of non-critical notifications and alerts. U6.04 Volume for audible notifications and vibration strength of tactile notifications should be customizable. U6.05 Notifications, alerts, and alarms should be stored as historical data so they are available for reference. This also provides a secondary resource for the user if a notification is dismissed in error. If an app allows the user to dismiss alerts and requires the user to select a reason for dismissal, this data should	Xcertia 2019
Features	Function	Text search function Absent (score: 0)/ Present (score: 1)	Wu 2021
Features	Function	DTx Product Technical Considerations -DTx products ability to function -Products use of the following to generate therapeutic interventions -DTx manufacturer process to prevent biases in therapeutic algorithms -Product notification, recovery, and resolution plans in the event	Digital Therapeutics Alliance 2022
Features	Function	Functionality -Alert/warning -Connectivity -Documentation -Performance -Record -Ease of use	Biswas 2021
Features	Function	>Are there indications that your idea/tool is going to work?	Betton 2017
Features	Function	Engagement Style -What features does the app have?	Anxiety and Depression Association of America 2022

Features	Function	Features - Advertisements - Features	Camacho 2020
Features	Function	App Origin and Functionality -Accessibility Feature(s)	Lagan 2021a
Features	Function	Features & Engagement -gamification -collaboration with provider	Lagan 2021a
Features	Function	How does the technology work?	Nebeker 2020
Features	Function	Does it work offline and with accessibility features?	Anxiety and Depression Association of America 2022
Features	Function	App-specific added items: - Awareness: This app is likely to increase awareness of the importance of addressing [insert target health behaviour] - Knowledge: This app is likely to increase knowledge/understanding of [insert target health behaviour] - Attitudes: This app is likely to change attitudes toward improving [insert target health behaviour] - Intention to change: This app is likely to increase intentions/motivation to address [insert target health behaviour] - Help seeking: Use of this app is likely to encourage further help seeking for [insert target health behaviour] (if its required) - Behaviour change: Use of this app is likely increase/decrease [insert target health behaviour]	Stoyanov 2015
Features	Function	Additional resources available: Does the app/e-tool provide up to date relevant offline/online resources to support the information presented? 1 "No" provides no further resources 2 Provides few online OR offline resources 3 "Somewhat" provides some offline and/or online resources, may be outdated 4 Provides adequate online and/or offline resources 5 "Yes" provides abundant and up to date offline and online resources	Roberts 2021
Features	Function	Strategies: Does the app/e-tool recommend strategies that are non-tech based and linked to the problems you have reported? 1 No: none 3 Somewhat: some information; may be too much, or too little resources 5 Yes: adequate/plentiful but not overbearing	Roberts 2021
Features	Function	Functionality -Performance -Health Warnings -Feedback -Connectivity and interoperability -Record -Display -Guide -Remind/alert -Communicate	Nouri 2018
Features	Function	What are the key components of the DHI? Which ones impact on the predicted outcome, and how do they interact	Murray 2016
Features	Performance	Performance: How accurately/fast does the app/e-tool run (functions) and do all components with the app/e-tool (buttons/menus) work? Are there any error messages, glitches, crashes?	Roberts 2021

		<p>1 App/e-tool is broken; no/insufficient/inaccurate response (e.g. crashes/bugs/broken features, etc.)</p> <p>2 Some functions work, but lagging or contains major technical problems</p> <p>3 App/e-tool works overall. Some technical problems need fixing, or is slow at times</p> <p>4 Mostly functional with minor/negligible problems</p> <p>5 Perfect/timely response; no technical bugs found, or contains a “loading time left” indicator (if relevant)</p>	
Features	Performance	Assessment of performance when compared to technical gold standard (e.g. manual blood pressure cuff reading)	Mathews 2019
Features	Description & product information	>Accuracy of app description (in app store): Does app contain what is described?	Stoyanov 2015
Features	Description & product information	<p>Targeted search for a suitable mobile medical app:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Is it clear who the app is intended for? - Is it clear who the app provider is? - Does the app have the functions you are looking for (e.g. providing information, taking measurements, making a diagnosis, monitoring, behavioural change?) - Is the app available for the operating system of your mobile device or the patient's mobile device? 	KNMG 2016
Features	Description & product information	<p>[U4 Onboarding]</p> <p>U4.01 The app provides a launch screen that clearly identifies the name and purpose of the app, and gives the user intuitive options for initiating use.</p> <p>U4.02 Provide the user with opportunities either to access detailed instructions and product information or to bypass this and immediately begin app setup.</p> <p>U4.03 Users should be allowed to bypass entry of personal data if it is not critical for app functionality. Data that is needed for the app to work as intended (e.g., alert and notification parameters) should be mandatory to avoid inaccurate app behaviour.</p> <p>U4.04 For apps with complex onboarding processes, entered data should be stored so that users can recover and avoid re entry if they are disconnected during the onboarding process.</p> <p>U4.05 When setup is complete, provide options for a walkthrough or tutorial on app use.</p> <p>U4.06 Apps should bypass onboarding for returning users, but allow users to update the data entered during onboarding at any time through intuitively named menu selections (e.g., Profile, Settings).</p>	Xcertia 2019
Features	Description & product information	<p>>Solution type</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Nonmedical device (nonexecutive) Nonmedical device (but theoretically should be) Class I medical device Class II medical device Other CEa markings (eg, Class III medical device) <p>>Type of algorithm used in the solution</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> No artificial intelligence (Boolean, common rules, and logistic regression, etc) No algorithm Intelligible artificial intelligence Nonintelligible artificial intelligence Algorithm more than 5 years old that were not reassessed with new support standards 	Wagneur 2022
Features	Description & product information	<p>App Name</p> <p>Rating (current version)</p> <p>Rating (all versions)</p> <p>Developer</p> <p>N ratings (current version)</p> <p>N ratings (all versions)</p>	Stoyanov 2015

		<p>Version, last update Cost - basic version Cost - upgrade version Platform: iPhone, iPad, Android Brief description</p> <p>Focus (what the app targets), e.g. increase happiness/well-being, mindfulness/meditation/relaxation; reduce negative emotions</p> <p>Theoretical background/strategies, e.g. assessment, feedback, information/education, monitoring/tracking, goal setting</p> <p>Affiliations (unknown, commercial, government, NGO, university)</p> <p>Age group (children, adolescents, young adults, adults, general)</p> <p>Technical aspects of app (allows sharing, has an app community, allows password-protection, requires login, sends reminders)</p>	
Features	Description & product information	<p>Product information:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Which operating systems or platforms does the health app support? - What is the name of the health app? - Provide the health app icon, if available. - In which languages is the health app available? - Provide instructions for access to the health app for assessment. <p>App manufacturer:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - What is the name of the health app manufacturer? - Provide e-mail address and telephone number of the person who is authorized to represent the health app manufacturer 	ISO 2021
Features	Description & product information	<p>Product information:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The name of the product. - Short description of the product. - What is the product's readiness level (TRL levels 1-9)? - Which platforms and platform versions of the product are available? - Does the product have CE and/or FDA approval? - Is the product a medical device, and what classification does it have? - Is the product classified according to MDD or MDR requirements? - Does the product meet the electrical safety requirements for medical devices (if applicable)? - Does the use of the product require registration or login? - Does the use of the product require strong identification? - Does the company have any plans for post-market surveillance of the product? - What kind of product support does the company offer? - Does the company have instructions (e.g., a project plan) for healthcare service providers to ensure fluent introduction 	Haverinen 2019
Features	Description & product information	<p>Category Informing Users:</p> <p>Subcategory: Description</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Product name - Product definition (version and environment) - Price and any subscriptions or in-app purchases - Sources of funding 	Haute Autorit de Sant 2016

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Assessment -Author credits -Contact details (publisher) Category: Health Content Subcategory: Generated content -Relevance of data collected - Minimisation of data collected -Number of interfaces/peripherals/applications -Relevance of information in context - Discussion forums -User support, hotline Category: Health Content Subcategory: Interpreted content -Algorithm types -Human interpretation of health content -Automated interpretation of health content 	
Features	Description & product information	<p>App Information</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Does the app work on Apple(iOS)? -What are the number of reviews on the iOS App Store? -What is the app rating (number of stars) on Apple Store? -Does the app work on Android? -What are the number of reviews on Google Play Store? -What is the app rating (number of stars) on Google Play Store? 	Agency for Healthcare Research and Quality 2022
Features	Description & product information	Content (evidence-based content, quality of information provision, complete and concise, clarity about program	Baumel 2017
Features	Description & product information	<p>Intervention content</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Details of the content of the intervention are described. Source and any modifications of the intervention content is described 	Agarwal 2016
Features	Description & product information	<p>Data</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -data type -data availability -data quality <p>Technology</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -decision -data collection -interaction 	Bertl 2023
Features	Description & product information	Detailed description of the app publicly available?	McMillan 2016
Features	Description & product information	<p>Documentation:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Publicly available manual? - Is the mechanism of action described? - Is it clear which BCT was employed? - Description how the app addresses maintenance? 	McMillan 2016

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Documentation updated along with app updates? - Clear rationale for the BCT employed? 	
Features	Description & product information	Description of the technology >Credibility and reputation >Scientific basis >Technical evaluation and validation >Adoption >Information management >Novelty	AQuAS 2023
Features	Description & product information	Technical aspects >Usability >Adaptability (interoperability scalability, integration of data, transferability) >Quality >Design(persuasive design) >Technical stability >Aesthetics >Ease of use >Accessibility >Technical effectiveness or performance (Reliability, validity, accuracy, sensitivity, feasibility)	AQuAS 2023
Features	Description & product information	Who is the developer of the app?	Agency for Health care Research and Quality 2022
Features	Description & product information	Are assessments done to establish whether the health app is a medical device or in vitro diagnostic medical device, and if applicable is regulatory approval obtained before the app is made available in each country? -Regulatory compliance (e.g., certification provided by a regulator, such as TGA and FDA)	Hussain 2021
Features	Layout	1-d) Have they located sound, relevant, up-to-date evidence, images, video etc to use in their app? Yes / No / Don't know 1-e) Do the app screens look well designed, is text clear? Not applicable / Yes / No / Don't know	Wyatt 2015
Features	Layout	Navigation ease Hard to navigate (score: 0)/ Easy to navigate (score: 1) Layout of the app - Inappropriate, unclear, and/or some options difficult to select, locate, find, or read (score: 0) - Appropriate, clear, and able to select, locate, find, or read items (score: 1) Visual appeal - Unprofessional or unappealing (score: 0) - Professional and appealing (score: 1)	Wu 2021
Features	Layout	Ui Design -Aesthetics -User Context -Consistency	Biswas 2021
Features	Layout	Visual design (aesthetics, layout, size)	Baumel 2017
Features	Layout	Readability - Not applicable (score: 0) - >6th grade (score: 1) - ≈6th grade (score: 2) Visual information	Wu 2021

		Absent (score: 0)/ Present (score: 1) Customization Absent (score: 0)/ Present (score: 1) Interactivity Absent (score: 0)/ Present (score: 1)	
Features	Layout	[U1 Visual Design] - U1.01 App layout should be adaptable such that usability and functionality do not differ between landscape or portrait mode. Ideally, interfaces should be flexible to operate in both orientations. - U1.02 Readability and meaning of content within the app should be consistent across a variety of mobile screen sizes and operating systems. - U1.03 Contrasting colours should be utilized to help users distinguish between the different elements on the screen, with an emphasis on contrast between the screen background and content (i.e., text and graphics). - U1.04 Multiple redundant identifiers should be used to indicate critical or safety-related information. Cues can include colour, iconography, labeling, or other text. - U1.05 Extraneous text, graphics, and animation should be used sparingly. Information that is actively populating should serve a purpose and avoid distracting the user or cluttering the screen if only for aesthetic purposes. - U1.06 Elements critical to app functionality and content understandability should be positioned above the scroll line to minimize the opportunity for missed information. Users should be able to clearly identify when screens extend beyond the scroll line. - U1.07 App design should provide clear indications that elements are actionable. Interactive elements can be differentiated from non-selectable content through design choices that should be used consistently throughout the app (i.e., color, text style). - U1.08 App design should support recognition over recall by keeping relevant information on screen rather than forcing users to remember it. - U1.09 When possible, reduce the probability of data entry error by providing users with selectable options rather than requiring text entry.	Xcertia 2019
Features	Layout	[U3 App Navigation] - U3.01 Users should be able to easily identify where they are in the app and how to navigate to different destinations. The navigational path should be logical, predictable, and easy to follow. For screens that users may need to access in succession, providing shortcuts may improve ease of navigation. - U3.02 Minimize the number of taps, swipes, or screens required to navigate from one area of the app to another. - U3.03 App design should facilitate reversible actions by allowing the user to navigate back to previous pages. - U3.04 Menu options should be labeled intuitively such that users can easily locate information within the app. Users should not have to locate information by trial and error. - U3.05 The apps main menu should be easily located and identified. Standard app design conventions would likely lead most users to look for a menu on the top, left-hand side of the screen. A collapsed menu is often associated with the three-bar hamburger icon that frequent app users are expected to be familiar with.	Xcertia 2019
Features	Layout	(c) Multimedia can be customized (graphical backgrounds can be varied, background music selections can be selected from an array, audio can be paused/ turned on/off).	Mackey 2022
Features	Layout	Communication and display - The design of the MMA user interface (i.e. level of complexity, type of platform, how information is displayed, etc.) - The appropriateness of the MMA interface as a means of information display (i.e. language translation, units displayed, clarity, etc.) - The MMAs ability to communicate the relevant information (i.e. data quality, network availability, correct installation, etc.	Moshi 2020

Features	Layout	Design -Suitability of design -Aesthetics -appearance -Design consistency	Nouri 2018
Features	Layout	Aesthetics: The degree to which the DHI interface applies design elements, colors and fonts in a logical way (e.g., consistent use of colors, figures and fonts).	Kowatsch 2019
Features	Layout	4. Visual Design Aesthetic: The apps visual design is appealing (colors, images, fonts, etc.). Graphics: The quality of the graphics is good. Format: The app is well structured. Size: The size of the elements is appropriate and can be customized if necessary.	O'Rourke 2020
Implementation	Access Control	[S5 Access Control and Authentication] S5.01 The app provides a method for securely authenticating the user at a session level (e.g., password, pass phrase, PIN, challenge phrase) and utilizes additional methods or techniques to further secure the identity of the users whenever the system is initially establishing identity, or the system has indications that the identity might have been compromised (e.g., multiple password failures). S5.02 Unique user IDs should be used for access to all functions within the application. S5.03 Access within the application should be limited to what is needed for that individuals specific role. S5.04 A process for provisioning and deprovisioning access in a timely fashion should be documented. S5.05 For remote access or privileged access should require two factor authentication to reduce the risk of unauthorized	Xcertia 2019
Implementation	Access Control	DTx Product Authorization and Distribution -Patient access to the product that may be provided -Ability and/or necessity of DTx therapy to be reauthorized or terminated following the first use cycle -Patient receipt of a product access code, if necessary, following authorization of a non-prescription or prescription product and any necessary product components (i.e., hardware, wearables) -Entities involved in product distribution -DTx hardware product components (i.e., sensors, wearables)	Digital Therapeutics Alliance 2022
Implementation	Infrastructure	[OP1 On-Boarding] OP1.01 The app downloads and installs on the target device(s) and target operating system(s) as confirmed by user notification. OP1.02 The app launches and runs on the target device(s) that it is installed upon and, if it does not, the user is notified of the potential problem (e.g., to restart the app, Bluetooth, OS, etc.). OP1.03 The app runs on a defined & current version of the intended OS. The app documentation must state clearly what versions are supported. (e.g. Android versions). OP1.04 If the app requires that it be connected to a network, the app can connect and operates on the intended domestic Network (PAN) and informs the user that the app is connected to a network and which network they are connected. OP1.05 The app functions as intended when not connected to a network. The user shall be informed of any differences between the apps functioning when connected or not connected to a network. [OP2 Connectivity] OP2.01 The app connects to the peripheral device(s) and operates consistently. OP2.02 The app has a mechanism to notify the user if the app fails to connect to any and all peripheral or accessory devices. The app needs to notify when data has been collected and not transmitted, if required. OP2.03 The app connects consistently to all third party mobile applications, software, and online user accounts, but such connection shall only occur after: (i) notifying user; (ii) requesting permission; and (iii) receiving consent from the user.	Xcertia 2019

		<p>OP2.04 The app has a mechanism to notify user of all updates applicable or necessary for the app to connect to any such device, application, software or online user accounts.</p> <p>[OP5 Operability with EHR]</p> <p>OP5.01 The app operates in accordance with the documented functionality provided by the Certified EHR.</p> <p>OP5.02 Documentation is provided regarding any relevant EHR certification received.</p> <p>OP5.03 The EHR systems with which the app connects are specifically enumerated and documentation of the interoperability with each specified EHR is provided.</p> <p>OP5.04 The details and description of the data fields that the app saves, sends to, and/or receives from each specified EHR system regarding patient information is provided.</p> <p>OP5.05 The app maintains (at rest) and transmits (in motion) patient information in a secure, HIPAA-compliant manner, as applicable (see Guidelines S2, S3, and S4).</p>	
Implementation	Infrastructure	<p>Does the app work offline?</p> <p>On which platforms/operating systems does it work?</p> <p>Does it work on a desktop computer?</p> <p>Does the app work with accessibility features of the iPhone/android?</p>	American Psychiatric Association 2019
Implementation	Infrastructure	<p>Navigation: Does moving between screens make sense; Is it easy to move from one section of the app/e-tool to another?</p> <p>Does the app/e-tool provide all necessary links between screens?</p> <p>1 No logical connection between screens at all/navigation is difficult</p> <p>2 Understandable after a lot of time/effort</p> <p>3 Understandable after some time/effort</p> <p>4 Easy to understand/navigate</p> <p>5 Perfectly logical, easy, clear and intuitive screen flow throughout, and/or has shortcuts</p>	Roberts 2021
Implementation	Infrastructure	Infrastructure: The app identifies any infrastructure needed to use the app.	Quintana 2020
Implementation	Infrastructure	<p>Technology platform</p> <p>-Describes and provides justification for the technology architecture. This includes a description of software and hardware</p>	Agarwal 2016
Implementation	Infrastructure	<p>Operating system(s) for MMA</p> <p>- Operating systems of the MMA (i.e. Android, iOS, etc.)</p> <p>- Operating platform(s) for MMA</p> <p>- Operating platforms of the MMA (i.e. smartphone, tablet, smartwatch</p>	Moshi 2020
Implementation	Infrastructure	<p>[S4 Compliance]</p> <p>S4.04 The app publisher has a mechanism to notify end users about apps that are banned or recalled by the app publisher or any regulatory entity (e.g., FDA, FTC, FCC, UL).</p> <p>S4.05 In the event that an app is banned or recalled, a mechanism or process is in place to notify all users about the ban or recall and render the app inoperable.</p> <p>S4.06 If the app constitutes a medical device (e.g., 510(k)) or is regulated by the FDA in any other capacity, the app publisher has a policy and a mechanism in place to comply with all applicable rules and regulations for purposes of handling all aspects of a product notification or recall, including all corrections and removals.</p>	Xcertia 2019
Implementation	Infrastructure	<p>Supported platforms:</p> <p>- Is the app exclusive to one platform, which may create accessibility barriers? Or is it available to many users across Android, iOS and other devices?</p>	Mental Health Commission 2018
Implementation	Infrastructure	Are the app's functionalities available for offline use?	KNMG 2016
Implementation	Infrastructure	<p>Other</p> <p>[P3 Access Mechanisms]</p> <p>-P3.01 If the app accesses any of the mobile device's native hardware (camera, microphone, GPS/location, Calendar, Address Book, etc.) the express reason for requiring such access shall be disclosed to the user, separate from any</p>	Xcertia 2019

		<p>warning/consent present in the mobile operating system.</p> <p>-P3.02 If the app accesses or uses any Wi-Fi, LAN, or mobile network data connections, an estimate of the amount of data consumed shall be provided to the user along with a notice that carrier data charges may apply.</p> <p>-P3.03 If the app accesses social networking sites (such as Facebook, Instagram, or like social media), the reason why such sites are being accessed is disclosed to the user.</p>	
Implementation	Infrastructure	<p>[U9 Accessibility]</p> <p>-U9.01 App content should be adaptable and accessible for a variety of users. For example, provide text alternatives for multimedia (e.g., descriptions of images) or captions for video content and other alternatives. Content should be tailored such that it is presentable in either an audio or visual format without losing meaning.</p> <p>-U9.02 Content layout should consider screen reader accessibility. This includes providing screen reader accessible alt text for images, and labels for buttons, icons, and loading states.</p> <p>-U9.03 Apps should aim to accommodate a variety of input modalities, including gestures or use of an external keyboard. The content should not limit the users interaction to any specific input unless it is essential or to ensure security of content.</p> <p>-U9.04 To the extent possible, app design should facilitate one-handed use.</p> <p>-U9.05 Alternative input modalities, such as speech recognition, gestures, and handwriting recognition, may produce results that are less exact than standard input methods. These input modalities should require the user to validate inputs (e.g., through use of confirmation screens or providing undo/redo options) so that unwanted actions are avoided.</p> <p>-U9.06 Display of information and color choice should consider the most common visual impairments. For example, avoid using red and green in close proximity to accommodate users with red-green colorblindness.</p> <p>-U9.07 Content should retain functionality and readability when adjustments are made to accommodate accessibility.</p>	Xcertia 2019
Implementation	Infrastructure	<p>Bandwidth:</p> <p>>Does the app require significant bandwidth to run?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - App does not require the use of cellular data; very few graphics used in the app - Main function of the app does not require the internet or cellular data, however there is a decent number of images or animations used in the app - App uses large images and animations, and only a few of its functions require the use of internet or cellular data - Many of the apps function use the internet or need cellular service, however the user can use the app offline - The main functions of the app require significant use of cellular data, access to the internet and/or location services; app includes a large amount of images, animations, and/or videos. User cannot use app without internet (no offline version). <p>Application size:</p> <p>>Does the app require significant storage capacity?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <10 MB, between 10 to 20 MB, between 20-30 MB, between 30-40 MB, >40 MB 	Levine 2020
Implementation	Infrastructure	<p>Authentication:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Is the authentication procedure optimal? 	Levine 2020
Implementation	Infrastructure	<p>Category Security/Reliability:</p> <p>Subcategory: Reliability:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Reliability and maintainability of hardware (sensors) and software - Infrastructure availability - Technical support, hotline - Materials quality, device safety - Media file optimisation 	Haute Autorit de Sant 2016

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Contraindications, potential risks, limitations of use - Availability level - Preventive maintenance - Functioning with other apps/SDs 	
Implementation	User engagement	<p>[U5 App Feedback]</p> <p>U5.01 Feedback messages should appear in an expected and consistent location within the interface so that they are noticeable to the user (e.g., near the input location).</p> <p>U5.02 Feedback messages that are not urgent or associated with a safety risk should be unobtrusive to app operation.</p> <p>U5.03 Ongoing processes (e.g., loading) should utilize ongoing feedback to communicate status to the user. For longer processes such as downloading, inform the user of time remaining until the process is complete.</p> <p>U5.04 Feedback should occur quickly such that users can detect that their actions were successful. Avoid excessive lag between the action and the result (e.g., the user selects a menu option and the app takes several seconds to open the new page).</p> <p>U5.05 Error messages must, in clear and concise language understandable to the user, explain the problem and inform the user of the required corrective actions.</p> <p>U5.06 Users should be informed of data entry requirements. For example, if a user needs to choose a password during the setup process that requires both letters and numbers, this information should be stated at the point of data entry rather than only in the form of an error message.</p>	Xcertia 2019
Implementation	User engagement	2-d) Is there a way to feed back user comments to the app developer? Yes / No / Do not know	Wyatt 2015
Implementation	User engagement	<p>>Possibility of interaction with the user</p> <p>Yes, with remote monitoring with a health professional</p> <p>Yes, alerts to the patient who then manages themselves</p> <p>Yes, information not personalized according to the answers</p> <p>Yes, patient alert with teleconsultation possible via the solution</p> <p>Solution not affected</p> <p>None, no user information</p>	Wagneur 2022
Implementation	User engagement	<p>Patient-Facing Technical Considerations</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Components required for the software to deliver its therapeutic value -DTx product use on the following host technology(ies) -Hardware components that may be required for, or to enhance, product use -Hardware components -Level of network connection required for product use -Product software compatibility with -Form(s) of technical assistance available to patients and clinicians 	Digital Therapeutics Alliance 2022
Implementation	User engagement	How does a user engage with the app?	Anxiety and Depression Association of America 2022
Implementation	User engagement	<p>3. Customisation (Section A): Does the app/e-tool need to be customised to make it more user friendly for you to use? Can you change settings such as sound, content, notifications, email/SMS reminders, display more to your liking?</p> <p>1 App/e-tool is not user friendly; has no customisation options or requires setting to be input every time</p> <p>2 App/e-tool allows little customisation; App/e-tool could be improved with more customisation options</p> <p>3 Basic customisation to function adequately and/or can use app/e-tool without customization</p> <p>4 Allows numerous options for customisation and/or easy to use app/e-tool; customisation somewhat unnecessary</p> <p>5 Does not need any customisation for me to use the app/e-tool effectively; Allows complete tailoring the user's characteristics</p>	Roberts 2021

<p>Technical aspects</p>	<p>Data protection</p>	<p>[S3 Systems & Communication Protection] S3.01 Passwords are stored using a random length, , one-way salted hash, or current accepted guideline. S3.02 Usernames and passwords are collected and transmitted only when using encryption between the client app and the server. S3.03 Other personal information while at rest and/or in motion is encrypted using a generally recognized, industry-accepted encryption method (e.g., FIPS 140-2, ISO/IEC) for such information and the encryption level is disclosed. S3.04 App contains security safeguards to verify the identity of intended user in the event of forgotten, lost or unknown user name, password and/or passcode (unique identifiers), for purposes of reminders, re-linking, or creation of new unique identifiers. S3.06 Information systems related to the app should have antivirus software and mechanism to keep application environment up to date with security patches. S3.07 Application data should be backed up regularly. S3.08 Firewalls should be used for internal and external connections. S3.09 Vulnerability assessments should be conducted on the application and organizational network on a regular basis. S3.10 If removable media is used for the storage of personal data, the media should be encrypted to protect the data from unauthorized access. S3.12 Installed App and respective infrastructure should have the capability to log and audit activity within the system, e.g. who did what, when and how. S3.13 Installed App Audit logs should be maintained for a minimum of 90 days.B10</p>	<p>Xcertia 2019</p>
<p>Technical aspects</p>	<p>Data protection</p>	<p>[P6 General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR)] P6.09 Best practice is to conduct audits to see what personal information the app maintains and conduct user testing to see if the privacy notice is easily understandable.</p>	<p>Xcertia 2019</p>
<p>Technical aspects</p>	<p>Data protection</p>	<p>Data protection and information security -Permitted Purposes of Data Processing -Permitted Data Processing according to Section 4 paragraph 2 Clause 1 and 2 DiGAV -Data Processing Outside of Germany</p>	<p>BfArM 2020</p>
<p>Technical aspects</p>	<p>Data protection</p>	<p>[Data Protection] C2.1 If you are required to register with the Information Commissioner, please attach evidence of a current registration. If you are not required to register, please attach a completed self-assessment showing the outcome from the Information Commissioner and your responses which support this determination. (Provided / Not provided) C2.2 Do you have a nominated Data Protection Officer (DPO)? (Yes / No / We do not need one) C2.2.1 If you are required to have a nominated Data Protection Officer, please provide their name. If you are not required to have a DPO please attach a completed self-assessment showing the outcome from the Information Commissioner and your responses which support this determination. (Free text / Provide) C2.3 Does your product have access to any personally identifiable data or NHS held patient data? (Yes / No) C2.3.1 Please confirm you are compliant (having standards met or exceeded status) with the annual Data Security and Protection Toolkit Assessment. If you have not completed the current year's assessment and the deadline has not yet passed, please confirm that you intend to complete this ahead of the deadline and that there are no material changes from your previous years submission that would affect your compliance. (Confirmed / Unable to confirm) C2.3.2 Please attach the Data Protection Impact Assessment (DPIA) relating to the product. (Provided / Not Provided)</p>	<p>NHS England 2021</p>

		<p>C2.4 Please confirm your risk assessments and mitigations / access controls / system level security policies have been signed-off by your Data Protection Officer (if one is in place) or an accountable officer where exempt in question C2.2. (Confirm / Cannot confirm)</p> <p>C2.5 Please confirm where you store and process data (including any third-party products your product uses) (UK only / In EU / Outside of EU)</p> <p>C2.5.1 If you process store or process data outside of the UK, please name the country and set out how the arrangements are compliant with current legislation (Free text) [Interoperability criteria]</p> <p>C4.1 Does your product expose any Application Programme Interfaces (API) or integration channels for other consumers? (Yes / No)</p> <p>C4.1.1 If yes (to C4.1), please provide detail and evidence: -The APIs (e.g., what they connect to) set out the healthcare standards of data interoperability e.g., Health Level Seven International (HL7) / Fast Healthcare Interoperability Resources (FHIR) — Confirm that they follow Government Digital Services Open API Best Practice — Confirm they are documented and freely available — Third parties have reasonable access to connect If no (to C4.1), please set out why your product does not have APIs.</p> <p>C4.2 Do you use NHS number to identify patient record data? (Yes / No / No because product does not identify patient record data)</p> <p>C4.2.1 If yes, please confirm whether it uses NHS Login to establish a user’s verified NHS number. If no, please set out the rationale, how your product established NHS number and the associated security measures in place. (Free text)</p> <p>C4.3 Does your product have the capability for read/write operations with electronic health records (EHRs) using industry standards for secure interoperability (e.g. OAuth 2.0, TLS 1.2) (Yes / No / No because product does not read/ write into EHRs)</p> <p>C4.3.1 If yes (to C4.3), please detail the standard (Free text)</p> <p>C4.3.2 If no (to C4.3), please state the reasons and mitigations, methodology and security measures. (Free text)</p> <p>C4.4 Is your product a wearable or device, or does it integrate with them? (Yes / No)</p> <p>C4.4.1 If yes, provide evidence of how it complies with ISO/IEEE 11073 Personal Health Data (PHD) Standards. (Provided / No evidence available)</p> <p>D1.7 Iterate and improve frequently Do you continuously develop your product? (Yes / No / Working towards on it)</p>	
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Technical aspects	Data protection	<p>True / False: Using your product causes sensitive personal data to be processed (e.g. collected/used/stored/analysed/transmitted). This could be processing carried out by you/your organisation, another organisation on your behalf or the users themselves. The definition of sensitive personal data can be found on the ICO's website and examples are listed in the supporting information. This includes any processing of sensitive personal data that is: -Carried out by a third party e.g. user analytics, user surveys, bulk emailers, tracker software (meant to collect data about the user or their online actions whether used for marketing or not - Caused by allowing 'permissions' your product requests to access or perform actions on existing sensitive personal data (e.g. the user's mobile phone photo library, contact lists, address books) This includes: 1. Physical / mental health or condition (past, current or future status) including: a. "Medical data" data that are inherently/clearly medical data b. "Raw sensor data" data that can be used in itself or in combination with other data to draw a conclusion about the actual health status or health risk of a person c. "Conclusions data" data where conclusions are drawn about a persons health status or health risk, irrespective of whether these conclusions are accurate, or otherwise adequate 2. Sexual life / orientation 3. Family / lifestyle / social circumstance 4. Political opinion 5. Offences committed / alleged to have committed / criminal proceedings / outcomes / sentence* 6. Financial data (that might be used for payment fraud) 7. Religion or other beliefs 8. Trade Union membership 9. Racial / ethnic origin 10. Biometric data (e.g. fingerprints / facial recognition) for the purpose of uniquely identifying a person 11. Genetic data for the purpose of uniquely identifying a person 12. Other sensitive personal data</p> <p>True / False: The personal data (and/or sensitive personal data) includes NHS or Social Care Data e.g. patient or client information).</p> <p>True / False: You have indicated that the use of your product will not cause any personal or sensitive personal data to be processed. Please confirm that: You have read and fully understood the definitions of personal sensitive personal data provided by the Information Commissioners Office; You have read and fully understood the supporting information and examples; You have fully considered all the data including that processed by placing and retrieving information through a cookie or similar technology; Should there be an intention to process such data, you accept that a reassessment will be required before the data processing begins in order to remain on the NHS Apps Library</p>	NHS Digital 2019
Technical aspects	Data protection	<p>Yes / No: You/your organisation processes personal data on behalf of another organisation and the other organisation (the 'Controller') makes the decisions described above. If your answer to this is 'Yes', then you / your organisation is a 'Processor'.</p> <p>Yes / No: You/your organisation is developing, or has developed, a product but you will not control or process the personal data because: the individual user who downloads your product controls their own data entirely OR the client (organisation) which buys your product is the >Controller< and will make the decisions described earlier regarding what personal data is processed when using your product). If your answer to this is 'Yes', then you/your organisation is a manufacturer or designer (neither a 'Controller' nor 'Processor'). Your app must be designed and configurable to meet the potential clients' (the 'Controller') legal requirements or safeguard the privacy rights of users who individually download the product you make available.</p>	NHS Digital 2019

		<p>True / False: You/your organisation is subject to European/UK Data Protection laws. You/your organisation has a registration number in the Data Protection Register</p> <p>Free Text: What is your registration number in the appropriate European/UK Data Protection Register? If you do not have a registration number in the Data Protection Register, explain why</p>	
Technical aspects	Data protection	<p>Data protection Is there a privacy policy stating information will be encrypted and not shared with third parties? Is there a clear requirement for parental/guardian permission for apps directed at children and adolescents?</p>	National Library of Medicine 2022
Technical aspects	Data protection	<p>Data Protection: – Does the app comply with data protection standards? – Does the app collect behavioural data?</p>	McMillan 2016
Technical aspects	Data protection	<p>Level 1,2, 3 (1) General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) Methods: Checklist for the application Evidence requirements: Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data, and repealing Directive 95/46/EC (General Data Protection Regulation)</p>	mHealthBELGIUM
Technical aspects	Data protection	<p>(2) Relevant safety and quality standards [ED] Methods: None stated Evidence requirements: UKCA/CE marking, CQC regulation, NHS Digital Technology Assessment Criteria (DTAC), Data protection act 2018, UK implementation of GDPR, local IG including data protection impact assessments, other non-mandated standards</p>	National Institute for Health and Care Excellence 2023
Technical aspects	Data security & privacy	<p>Data and Privacy: The NordDEC looks for specific and secure storage techniques, such as encryption or firewalls. Security + Technical Stability: The questions within form a comprehensive security and functionality assessment for a health app, covering various aspects such as connectivity, data handling, security measures, and testing practices. The emphasis is on ensuring compliance with regulatory and data privacy obligations, addressing potential risks, and implementing robust security measures throughout the development lifecycle.</p>	NordDEC 2024
Technical aspects	Data security & privacy	<p>Security and privacy: -Does the app clearly state how it will collect, store, use and protect personal health information? Is this information easy to find or hidden deep within the app? Does the app meet all applicable federal and provincial/territorial legislative standards and requirements regarding personal health information?</p>	Mental Health Commission 2018
Technical aspects	Data security & privacy	<p>Does the app include a clear, easy-to-read privacy statement? Does the privacy statement do any of the following: ask permission to collect data? ask to access data on your mobile device? use any data (entered or released)? modify the data entered? delete the data entered, including account data?</p> <p>Security: - Has security of the app been subject to testing by a third party? - If not: Does the app include a security policy? - Does the security policy include information on: setting up secure access? securing electronic communications via the app if the app uses a portal, for instance, by using https in the URL?</p>	KNMG 2016
Technical aspects	Data security & privacy	<p>Data security [S1 Security Operations]</p>	Xcertia 2019

		<p>S1.01 Administrative, physical, and technical safeguards to protect users information from unauthorized disclosure or access are provided and employed.</p> <p>S1.02 Access to users information is limited to those authorized employees or contractors who need to know the information in order to operate, maintain, develop, or improve the app.</p> <p>S1.03 If the app utilizes unique identifiers, the identifier is linked to the correct user and is not shared with third parties.</p> <p>S1.04 If any third-party vendor services are utilized as part of the app, an information security risk assessment should be conducted of the respective third parties.</p> <p>S1.05 If your organization is subject to HIPAA or other Information Security and/or Privacy regulations, an internal risk assessment for any systems related to PHI/PII should be conducted.</p> <p>S1.06 App publisher should create and maintain a baseline configuration document for potential risks to be identified.</p> <p>S1.07 Risk-appropriate authentication methods are used to authenticate users.</p> <p>S1.08 A written description of security procedures is provided in a section of the app (tab, button, or equivalent) or through an active link. The security procedures are written in clear, easy-to-understand language and terms and are affirmatively agreed to by the user. Such components include, but are not limited to, how personal information is safeguarded, how unique identifiers are linked to the correct user, and authentication methods used.</p> <p>S1.09 App publisher should designate someone to be responsible for information security.</p> <p>S1.10 App publisher staff designated for information security should have a baseline of information security knowledge.</p> <p>S1.11 Responsibilities for information security staff should be clearly documented.</p> <p>S1.12 Any staff members handling PHI/PII should be required to take Information Security Awareness training, highlighting HIPAA.</p> <p>S1.13 The app publisher has a mechanism in place to review security procedures on an ongoing basis and update security procedures, as necessary, to ensure that they comply at all times with applicable rules and regulations for jurisdiction(s) in which the app is intended to be sold or used.</p> <p>S1.14 Cloud-based apps meet Statement on Guidelines for Attestation Engagements (SSAE) No. 16 requirements and a SSAE No. 16 audit report is provided. (http://ssae16.com/SSAE16_overview.html)</p> <p>S1.15 If the app uses Short Messaging Service (SMS) or Multi-Media Message Service (MMS), the user is informed whether messages are encrypted and, if so, the level of encryption.</p> <p>S1.16 Any app that collects, stores and/or transmits user financial data for any purpose, including payment processing, or the app directs to any website for the purpose of collecting and/or processing of financial information, including any third-party website, shall comply with all applicable Federal and state laws, rules and regulations, and private sector regulatory best practices guidelines and initiatives regarding data security requirements.</p> <p>[S2 Vulnerability Management]</p> <p>S2.01 A scan of the app by the app developer using scanning software does not reveal any known malicious code or software objects prior to release.</p> <p>S2.02 A scan of any third-party code, including advertising networks, incorporated into app for purposes of displaying or supporting advertisements (e.g., banner, interstitial) does not reveal any known malicious code or software.</p> <p>S2.03 If ongoing scanning does produce evidence of malicious code or software objects, proactively work to update the app and notify end users.</p>	
<p>Technical aspects</p>	<p>Data security & privacy</p>	<p>[P5 Children’s Online Privacy Protection Act (COPPA)]</p> <p>P5.03 The app provides for an age verification process either automatic or self-reported to control access to age-restricted content and to minimize the inappropriate collection, use, or disclosure of personal information from a child.</p> <p>P5.07 Apps that are intended for children must have a location default setting that enables parents/legal guardians to prevent the app from automatically publishing their child’s location.</p> <p>P5.08 Apps that are directed at children under the age of 13 will have a default setting that prevents in-app purchases.</p>	<p>Xcertia 2019</p>

		P5.09 Apps that are directed at children under the age of 13 will have a default setting that prevents usage of camera and microphone.	
Technical aspects	Data security & privacy	Privacy and Data Security (1) what data leave the device? (2) how are those data stored? (eg, de-identified, encrypted) (3) who will have access to those data?	Wykes 2019
Technical aspects	Data security & privacy	1-h) Does it seem to keep user and patient data secure and private? Yes / No / Don not know	Wykes 2019
Technical aspects	Data security & privacy	29) Is the data generated from the app secured by end-to-end-encryption? (Privacy) 30) How is the data generated from the app stored: a. locally on the device?, b. encrypted? (Privacy) 31) Is the data generated from the app anonymised for storage or analysis so that individuals are non-identifiable? (Privacy) 32) How is the data anonymized? (Privacy) 33) How long is the generated data stored? (Privacy)	Vokinger 2020
Technical aspects	Data security & privacy	Security and Privacy With Mobile Health in Clinical Care - Source: Is the app coming from a trusted source? - Permissions: What permissions is the app asking for? - Data protection: How can I help patients protect their health data on their device? - Data transmission: How will data be shared with providers?	Defense Health Agency 2018
Technical aspects	Data security & privacy	Information Security -Management System for Information Security -Security as a Process -BSI-Grundschtz-Components and Technical Guides -Requirements in Case of an Increased Need for Protection	BfArM 2020
Technical aspects	Data security & privacy	Privacy and Security: - Is there a transparent privacy policy that is clear and accessible before use? - Does the app declare data use and purpose? - Does the app describe use of PHI? Deidentified vs. anonymous? - Can you opt out of data collection or delete data? -Are data maintained in the device or on the web? - Does the app explain security systems used? -Does the app collect, use, and/or transmit sensitive data? If yes, does it claim to do so securely? - What third parties does the app share data with?	American Psychiatric Association 2019
Technical aspects	Data security & privacy	Security: Any transfer of data must be done using secure methods, and access to the site must be secure.	Quintana 2020
Technical aspects	Data security & privacy	6. Security (expert-specific) Data Protection: The app undertakes relevant data protection measures.	O'Rourke 2020
Technical aspects	Data security & privacy	Security and Privacy -Security -Privacy	Nouri 2018
Technical aspects	Data security & privacy	Privacy and Confidentiality -Are data encrypted? - Who has data access? - Is data security sound?	Nebeker 2020

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Does HIPAA apply? - What data are shared? - Is there a privacy agreement? 	
Technical aspects	Data security & privacy	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Data security - Are consumers notified in the event of a breach of privacy and health information? 	National Library of Medicine 2022
Technical aspects	Data security & privacy	(b) The app includes privacy settings and allows the encryption of user information and/or password protection.	Mackey 2022
Technical aspects	Data security & privacy	<p>Security/privacy: Protection against theft, viruses, etc:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Does the app follow best practices in security with optimal anti-virus and safeguards against breaches? 	Levine 2020
Technical aspects	Data security & privacy	<p>Anonymisation:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Does the app appropriately anonymize individuals? 	Levine 2020
Technical aspects	Data security & privacy	<p>Privacy & security: The degree to which the DHI considers legal requirements and aspects with respect to privacy and security aspects (e.g., a DHI is compliant with the General Data Protection Regulation).</p>	Kowatsch 2019
Technical aspects	Data security & privacy	<p>Privacy:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Does the health app process Personally Identifiable Information (PII)? - Does the health app process health related PII? - Is data minimization applied in the health app? - Is an appropriate retention policy established to erase or review the data stored? - Is a privacy statement readily available to potential customers and users of the health app? - Does the privacy statement start with an accessible overview in less than 150 words? - Are contracts in place with all processors and controllers of PII of the health app and associated services to ensure the level of security controls and privacy protection are as communicated to the user? - Is opt-in the default setting for sharing PII with third parties? - Does the app manufacturer have a person responsible for legal and regulatory compliance of processing of PII? - Are security-incident response procedures in place that include reporting PII breaches to the user and relevant authorities? <p>Security:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Have the health app manufacturer and all organizations providing associated services implemented and documented the implementation of ISO/IEC 27001? - Is an Information Security Risk Assessment documented? - Is a secure by design process followed? - Are measures in place to ensure that all third-party software libraries and other software components for the health app are reliable and maintained? - Is a process to prevent unauthorized access and modifications to the health app source code in place and documented? - Are organizational measures in place to ensure PII is processed in a manner that is compatible with the explicit, legitimate purposes specified in the privacy statement? - Is user authentication, authorization and session management implemented to secure access to the health app? - Does the health app transmit and store all PII with adequate encryption? - Are security vulnerabilities reported, identified, assessed, logged, responded to, disclosed, and quickly and effectively resolved? - Are the security of the health app and associated services tested on a regular basis and at major changes? - Is the information security policy readily available to potential customers and users? 	ISO 2021

Technical aspects	Data security & privacy	Data and Privacy -Need for HIPAA Compliance -Privacy Policy	Kowatsch 2019
Technical aspects	Data security & privacy	>Does the privacy policy clearly state that user data will not be used or shared with other parties except as described in the privacy policy, without express consent of the user? >Does the privacy policy inform the user of where the data is stored and how it is protected in storage and transmission? >Is the user given the option to withdraw consent at any time?	Digital Health Assessment Framework, ORCHA
Technical aspects	Data security & privacy	>Data Security and Protection Preliminary Task >Information Security and Data Protection Requirements	Haverinen 2019
Technical aspects	Data security & privacy	Data security/reliability: The requirements on collecting and processing data apply whenever the data processed by apps/SDs relate to a physical person who is identified or could be identified, directly or indirectly. The following specific principles must be respected when personal data is processed: - Principle of purpose: Before any personal data is collected or used, the data controller must tell the individuals concerned precisely what the data will be used for; - Principle of data relevance: Only data that is strictly necessary for achieving the objective may be collected. This is the principle of minimising collection. Data controllers must not collect more data than they actually need. They must also be conscious of the sensitive nature of some data; - Principle of limited-duration data storage: Also known as the right to be forgotten. Once the objective behind collecting the data is achieved, there is no longer any reason to store them and they must be deleted. The duration of storage must be defined in advance by the data controller, taking into account any obligations to keep certain data; - Principle of data security and confidentiality: Data controllers must take all measures necessary to guarantee that data they collect are secure and confidential, in other words to ensure that only authorised people access them. These measures must be based on the risks relating to the file (sensitive data, objective of processing, etc.); - Principle of respecting peoples rights: Data about people may only be collected on the essential condition that they have been informed of this operation. People also have certain rights that can be exercised with the organisation that holds their data: the right to access these data; the right to correct them; the right to oppose their use; the right to be forgotten (have personal data deleted); the right to data portability, allowing individuals to easily send their data to another data controller; the right to be informed if their data are hacked; - Health data, which are particularly sensitive, are subject to stricter control. In addition, apps/SDs that can exchange or share information must guarantee data security. Furthermore, sharing or exchanging a person’s health data requires their express consent, obtained in advance. Individuals must be able to change or withdraw their consent at any time. CNIL, the French authority responsible for overseeing data protection, helps professionals to comply with the law and offers several guides on the collection and use of personal data, particularly by healthcare professionals.	Haute Autorité de Santé 2016
Technical aspects	Data security & privacy	Privacy and Security -Does the app claim it meets HIPAA [or analogous national standard for protected health information (PHI)]? -Does the app claim it meets COPPA [or analogous national standard for protected health information (PHI) for minors younger than 13 years of age]? -Does the app report sharing or selling of data for research or commercial purposes? -If the app reports sharing or selling for research or commercial purposes, are the data de-identified?	Agency for Healthcare Research and Quality 2022

		-If the app has the capability to read/write to an electronic health record management system (EHRs) or other healthcare systems, does it use industry standards for secure interoperability (e.g., FHIR, SMART, OAuth 2.0, TLS 1.2)?	
Technical aspects	Data security & privacy	What is the format of the data privacy and security consent process followed in the app?	Xcertia 2019
Technical aspects	Data security & privacy	<p>Security Best Practices</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Manufacturer information security risk management and governance frameworks to account for information security controls, risk management, etc. -Cybersecurity certifications and/or accreditations the manufacturer and/or product maintains -Product cybersecurity credentials -Whether the scope of the certified company and/or product components are appropriate to their purpose -How the DTx product verifies -Protocols in place to address a data breach or other privacy/data security crisis -Manufacturer engagement in vulnerability testing -Other measures the manufacturer uses to ensure security <p>Data Privacy and Governance</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -DTx product provides end user with a privacy notice -Patient may be able to consent and authorize how personal digital health data are -Types of personally identifiable and sensitive data the product gathers -Types of internal company policies and procedures to determine how information is collected, protected, and used -Product insurance liability coverage -Whether other entities involved in DTx product deployment processes, particularly where patient data might be accessible, are held to same standards as the DTx manufacturer -Policies that govern third-party access and utilization of data -Types of data that may be shared from the DTx product with third-parties -DTx manufacturer procedures in case of a potential data privacy breach 	Digital Therapeutics Alliance 2022
Technical aspects	Data security & privacy	Privacy and security (terms of use, information on social platforms, security of data and transmission, documentation of data exposure, compliance, third-party endorsement)	Baumel 2017
Technical aspects	Data security & privacy	<p>Privacy and Security</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Is there a privacy policy? -What security measures are in place? -What kind of user data does the app collect and is that data shared? 	Anxiety and Depression Association of America 2022
Technical aspects	Data security & privacy	<p>Data security</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Describes the data security procedures/ confidentiality protocols 	Agarwal 2016
Technical aspects	Data security & privacy	the framework mentions the need to consider privacy and data security requirements for handling patient data, and suggests using architecture standards for encryption and user authentication.	Mathews 2019
Technical aspects	Data security & privacy	<p>Level 2 Privacy and security</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Data collected -Data storage -Deleting personal data -Privacy policy 	Henson 2019
Technical aspects	Data security & privacy	<p>Privacy</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Privacy policy, - Data type, - Disclaimer, 	Camacho 2020

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Delete data, - Data protection, - Data location, - Data sharing, - Trusted developer 	
Technical aspects	Data security & privacy	<p>Safety and security</p> <p>-The assessment of the risks related to data privacy, cyber security and misinformation and their potential impact are emphasized issues for MMAs</p>	Moshi 2020
Technical aspects	Data security & privacy	<p>Integration and infrastructure dimension</p> <p>-Security: Are the apps data encrypted on the device and/or in transmission? Are they anonymized, or do they contain personal health information? If so, what do they do?</p> <p>-Privacy: Does the app contain a robust privacy policy addressing the type of information collected, rationale for collecting information, sharing of information, and user controls?</p>	Chan 2015
Technical aspects	Data security & privacy	<p>(2) Does the app outline a process for managing data confidentiality breaches?</p> <p>(3) Is there a data privacy policy, either within the app itself or on a website?</p> <p>(4) Does the data privacy policy, or statement, provide detail about what data is collected by the app?</p> <p>(5) Does the data privacy policy, or statement, provide detail about what that data is used for by the app?</p> <p>(6) Does the data privacy policy, or statement, state whether personal data are stored using recognised secure data storage technologies?</p> <p>(7) Does the data privacy policy, or statement, state that all personally identifiable data will be encrypted in transit between the device and any developer host storage? (eg, using FTP protocol)</p> <p>(8) Does the data privacy policy state that only the minimum data items necessary for the app to function will be collected?</p>	Leigh 2017
Technical aspects	Data security & privacy	<p>Privacy/Security</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Privacy policy -Data storage -data collected -Security measures -HIPAA compatibility 	Lagan 2021a
Technical aspects	Data security & privacy	<p>Cybersecurity and connectivity</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Formalised and safe methods have been implemented to convert, transmit, and/or store MMA data (i.e. results of fuzzing or fuzz testing) - Users can safely implement information security updates - System supports ensure protection of MMA system information - MMA software adheres to robust programming principles (i.e. paranoia, stupidity, dangerous implements, cannot happen) - Balances the availability of timely information and against privacy and security (i.e. results of fuzzing or fuzz testing) - How MMA integrates with other software (i.e. results of fuzzing or fuzz testing) - The need for MMA security software to be updated so that it can be used alongside other systems, applications or in operating environments (i.e. results of fuzzing or fuzz testing) 	Moshi 2020 (repeated)
Technical aspects	Data security & privacy	<p>24) Does the app require only minimal personal data of end-users? (Transparency)</p> <p>25) Does the app require only minimal access permissions for using mobile phone functionalities (e.g. location, address book, camera)? (Transparency)</p>	Vokinger 2020
Technical aspects	Data security & privacy	<p>[Technical security]</p> <p>C3.1 Please attach your Cyber Essentials Certificate. (Provided / No evidence available)</p>	NHS England 2021

		<p>C3.2 Please provide the summary report of an external penetration test of the product that included Open Web Application Security Project (OWASP) Top 10 vulnerabilities from within the previous 12-month period. (Provided / No evidence available)</p> <p>C3.3 Please confirm whether all custom code had a security review. (Yes - Internal code review / Yes - External code review / No / No because there is no custom code)</p> <p>C3.4 Please confirm whether all privileged accounts have appropriate Multi-Factor Authentication (MFA)? (Yes / No)</p> <p>C3.5 Please confirm whether logging and reporting requirements have been clearly defined. (Yes / No)</p> <p>C3.6 Please confirm whether the product has been load tested</p>	
Technical aspects	Data security & privacy	<p>Technical Security & Stability</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -technical architecture and related level of connectivity -data footprint -functional risk profile 	Digital Health Assessment Framework, ORCHA, 2022
Technical aspects	Data security & privacy	Criteria for data protection, data security and updates	National Library of Medicine 2022
Technical aspects	Data security & privacy	Has the app/SD been developed with due regard to transparency, quality, confidentiality and data security?	Haute Autorité de Santé 2016
Technical aspects	Data security & privacy	34) Do end-users act as the proprietors of the data generated from the app? (34) Do end-users act as the proprietors of the data generated from the app?)	Vokinger 2020
Technical aspects	Data security & privacy	How is privacy managed?	Nebeker 2020
Technical aspects	Data security & privacy	<p>Level 2 Privacy and security:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Data collected, -Personal health information, -Data storage, -Security measures in place, -Deleting personal data -Privacy policy 	Lagan 2021b
Technical aspects	Data security & privacy	<p>Patient privacy and confidentiality:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -The presence of a privacy policy, -The contents of a privacy policy 	Moshi 2020
Technical aspects	Data security & privacy	<p>[S7 Physical & Environmental Security]</p> <p>S7.01 Organization should have a physical security program.</p> <p>S7.02 Physical security program should include security and environmental controls for the building/data center which contains information assets and system.</p>	Xcertia 2021
Technical aspects	Data security & privacy	<p>[S8 Incident Response]</p> <p>S8.01 Organization should have an incident response plan in the event of an information security incident.</p>	Xcertia 2022
Technical aspects	Interoperability & Connectivity & Data Sharing	Interoperability: To provide a seamless care journey, it is important that relevant technologies in the health and social care system are interoperable, in terms of hardware, software and the data contained within. Where there are Application Programme Interfaces (APIs), these should follow the relevant best practices, be documented and freely available, and third parties should have reasonable access in order to integrate technologies.	NHS England 2021
Technical aspects	Interoperability & Connectivity & Data Sharing	Does the app use open standards allowing it to exchange data with other health apps or tools (if applicable)?	Mental Health Commission 2018

Technical aspects	Interoperability & Connectivity & Data Sharing	To what extent do users have the ability to move across different platforms (mobile and desktop) while maintaining profile preferences and information?	Zelmer 2018
Technical aspects	Interoperability & Connectivity & Data Sharing	[OP6 Connectivity with PHR] OP6.02 The details and description of the data fields that the app saves, sends to, and/or receives from each specified PHR system regarding patient information (e.g., medical history, diagnoses, treatment plan, medications, laboratory results, radiology images, etc.) is provided.	Xcertia 2019
Technical aspects	Interoperability & Connectivity & Data Sharing	Quality, especially interoperability -Use of Standards and Profiles -The Cascade of Section 6 DiGAV -Interoperability Requirements for DiGA	BfArM 2020
Technical aspects	Interoperability & Connectivity & Data Sharing	> Can data be easily shared and interpreted in a way that's consistent with the stated purpose of the app? > Can the app share data with EMR and other data tools (apple Healthkit, FitBit)? > If intended to be used with a provider, does the app have the ability to export or transfer data?	American Psychiatric Association 2019
Technical aspects	Interoperability & Connectivity & Data Sharing	4. Interactivity/Interoperability (Section A): Does it allow user input, provide feedback, contain prompts (reminders, sharing options, notifications, etc.)? Does the app/e-tool adapt based on user input? Does it allow exchange of data with other apps, e-tools or wearable devices (if applicable)? 1 No interactive and features and/or no response to user input; does not adapt based off user information; has no function for exchange of data with other apps, e-tools or wearables (if applicable) 2 Some, but not enough interactive and/or interoperability features which limits app/e-tool functions; some adaptability 3 Basic interactive features to function adequately; has some capacity for exchanging data with other apps, e-tools or wearables (if applicable) 4 Offers a variety of interactive features, feedback and user input options, app/e-tool adapts somewhat to user input; with some effort can exchange data with multiple different apps, e-tools and wearables (if applicable) 5 Very high level of responsiveness through interactive features, feedback and user input options; app/e-tool adapts as user inputs; allows easy exchange of data with apps, e-tools or wearable devices (if applicable) 27. Real time tracking (Section F): Can you use the app/e-tool in real time, as you're experiencing a health issue? 1 No the app/e-tool is mainly useful for prevention or recovery 3 The app/e-tool is useful for prevention, management and/or recovery of the health issue(s) 5 Yes the app/e-tool is useful for prevention, management and recovery of the health issue(s)	Roberts 2021
Technical aspects	Interoperability & Connectivity & Data Sharing	Data Sharing: Any sharing of user data with external third parties must be clearly disclosed to users and only done with the prior consent of the user. Interoperability: The app should have a way to extract user data from the app or send the data to external systems.	Quintana 2020
Technical aspects	Interoperability & Connectivity & Data Sharing	Interoperability / Data Sharing - Is data available for post research access and sharing? - Is there interoperability into electronic health record?	Nebeker 2020
Technical aspects	Interoperability & Connectivity & Data Sharing	Interoperability: - Is the app able to exchange information with EHRs and other apps?	Levine 2020
Technical aspects	Interoperability & Connectivity & Data Sharing	Data sharing: - When sharing information, does the app use best practices?	Levine 2020

Technical aspects	Interoperability & Connectivity & Data Sharing	Interoperability: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Are potential customers and users of the health app able to access the specifications and implementation guides for all the APIs? - Are potential customers and users of the health app able to access the specifications and implementation guides for the terminology or terminologies used? - Does the health app validate all data for the health app transferred via APIs? - Can users obtain their PII by a data export to another platform? 	ISO 2021
Technical aspects	Interoperability & Connectivity & Data Sharing	Interoperability: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Does the product have interfaces into the website or other software? - Does the product have interfaces into the following healthcare services? Electronic patient records (which ones?) Finnish Kanta PHR Other (what?) - Are proprietary formats used to store and transfer data? - Are the definitions of the original proprietary formats openly available? - Does the product have interfaces for other companies services? - Can the data contained in the product be exported in a commonly used or standard format? - Does the product use data from other systems via interfaces? If yes, can the data produced by others be separated in the system? - Does the product connect with health or wellness devices? If yes, is it compatible with ISO/IEEE 11073 Personal Health Data (PHD) Standards? 	Haverinen 2019
Technical aspects	Interoperability & Connectivity & Data Sharing	Interoperability: semantic standards, standard terminologies	Haute Autorité de Santé 2016
Technical aspects	Interoperability & Connectivity & Data Sharing	Interoperability & Sharing <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Is the app able to share data with external parties, like family and providers? 	Anxiety and Depression Association of America 2022
Technical aspects	Interoperability & Connectivity & Data Sharing	Interoperability/Health information systems (HIS) context <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Describes how mHealth intervention can integrate into existing health information systems. Refers to whether the potential of technical and structural integration into existing HIS or programme has been described irrespective of whether such integration has been achieved by the existing system 	Agarwal 2016
Technical aspects	Interoperability & Connectivity & Data Sharing	Interoperability/data sharing <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Data ownership/Export 	Lagan 2021a
Technical aspects	Interoperability & Connectivity & Data Sharing	[OP6 Connectivity with PHR] OP6.01 The PHR systems with which the app connects (e.g. Microsoft HealthVault, Blue Button etc.) are specifically enumerated and documentation of the interoperability with each specified PHR is provided.	Xcertia 2019
Technical aspects	Interoperability & Connectivity & Data Sharing	Interdevice compatibility <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - iPhone or Android phone (score: 0) - iPhone and Android phone (score: 1) Connectivity <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Internet not required (score: 0) - Internet required (score: 1) 	Wu 2021

Technical aspects	Interoperability & Connectivity & Data Sharing	<p>Category: Technical Content</p> <p>Subcategory: Data flow:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Interface with electronic patient record - Backward compatibility - Data import, export and reversibility - Data model - Data hosting arrangements - Data hosting and backup procedure 	Haute Autorité de Santé 2016
Technical aspects	Interoperability & Connectivity & Data Sharing	<p>Technical</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> > Does it need an active connection to the Internet to work? > On which platforms does it work (e.g., iOS, Android)? -Stability > Has the app been updated in the last 180 days? " 	Henson 2019
Technical aspects	Interoperability & Connectivity & Data Sharing	<p>Level 1 + 2 +3</p> <p>(2) Interoperability</p> <p>Methods: Checklist for the application</p> <p>Evidence requirements: exchange takes place via open standards, and preferably via the standards set by the eHealth platform</p>	mHealthBELGIUM
Technical aspects	Transparency & Control	<p>26) Is the source code publicly available? (Transparency)</p> <p>27) Does the app integrate third-party software or use third-party APIs? (Transparency)</p>	Vokinger 2020
Technical aspects	Transparency & Control	<p>Configuration</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The MMAs ability to withstand user configuration in an unintended way (i.e. results of fuzzing or fuzz testing) - Limitations of the MMA (i.e. assumptions, data quality, algorithms) 	Moshi 2020
Technical aspects	Transparency & Control	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> > Testing of security features > Testing of interoperability features 	Mathews 2019
Technical aspects	Transparency & Control	<p>Level 2 +3</p> <p>(4) Verification</p> <p>Methods: Checklist for the application</p> <p>Evidence requirements: This consultation is done (1) either via the eHealth platform user and access management system (2) or through up-to-date user information provided by the app provider, originating from an authentic source accessible via the eHealth platform.</p>	mHealthBELGIUM
Technical aspects	Transparency & Control	<p>Tier B + C</p> <p>(1)+ (2)</p> <p>and (3) Reliable health information [ED]</p> <p>Methods: None stated</p> <p>Evidence requirements: Company should show processes to maintain valid, accurate and comprehensive health information, including regular review and updates by experts</p>	National Institute for Health and Care Excellence 2024
Technical aspects	Transparency & Control	<p>[C4 Accuracy of Results]</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - C4.01 When operated, the app produces consistent and accurate results that are independently verifiable. - C4.02 The app publisher will provide the accuracy and reliability of any calculations in product documentation. Product documentation will also include appropriate sources that support the validity of calculations, measures and other functions. 	Xcertia 2019
Technical aspects	Transparency & Control	<p>2. Transparency of Information Security</p> <p>Are the apps security and privacy policies transparent and easy to find?</p>	Zelmer 2018

Technical aspects	Technical stability & Service	[U7 Help Resources and Troubleshooting] U7.01 Apps should have an easy-to-locate help section that consolidates all information intended to assist the user. U7.02 Help features and informational links should be imbedded in the app when users may be likely to need them. Pop-ups are more appropriate for simple information such as terminology definitions, while links to the help section can be used for more complex troubleshooting. U7.03 Step-by-step walkthroughs should not be required for each completion of a task. Experienced users should be allowed to bypass detailed instructions. U7.04 Instructional information should avoid text-heavy paragraphs and give users easy-to-follow lists of task steps. For more complex processes, incorporate graphics or videos to supplement and/or replace text.	Xcertia 2019
Technical aspects	Technical stability & Service	Software performance/stability: - Does the app run well with zero interface crashes or bugs?	Levine 2020
Technical aspects	Technical stability & Service	Service quality: The extent to which support of a DHI is provided (e.g., a technical support line is made available).	Kowatsch 2019
Technical aspects	Technical stability & Service	Technical robustness: - Are all the health app product requirements documented? - Is the health app developed with a software development process that covers the standards, methods and tools to be used? - Is a secure coding standard followed and documented? - Is a configuration management plan established for the health app? - Are processes in place to deal with a significant increase or spike in demand? - Is a validation and verification plan documented and used for the health app? - Is a release and deployment process established? - Is a maintenance process established?	ISO 2021
Technical aspects	Technical stability & Service	Technical stability: - What is the company's testing process? - What is the company's process for handling error messages? - Does the company have the capacity to roll back to previous versions of the product? - Does the company have a process to proactively monitor the running of systems and system components to automatically identify faults and technical issues? - Does the company have a plan for decommissioning the product? - Has there been any downtime or impairment time in the use of the product during the last six months?	Haverinen 2019
Technical aspects	Technical stability & Service	[S9 Disaster Recovery & Business Continuity] S9.01 Organization should have a documented DR/BC plan in the event that the application, data, or its infrastructure is not available for use. S9.02 Tests from data back-up should happen on a regular basis. S9.03 Tests of the DR/BC plan should happen on a regular basis.	Xcertia 2023
Technical aspects	Updates & maintenance	Are the app and its contents regularly updated?	KNMG 2016
Technical aspects	Updates & maintenance	Can problems with use of the app be reported to the app provider (phone number, email address, help function)?	KNMG 2016
Technical aspects	Updates & maintenance	Updates Is the app functional over time with recent updates?	National Library of Medicine 2022
Technical aspects	Updates & maintenance	Maintenance: Does the app have regular cycles to update and patch its security? - last update occurred during the month of rating or during the month before; also, if the update schedule is very	Levine 2020

		<p>consistent</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - last update occurred 2 months before the time of rating; update schedule is generally consistent - last update occurred between 3-5 months before the time of rating; update schedule is a little inconsistent - last update occurred between 6 months to a year before time of rating; update schedule is completely inconsistent - last update was occurred more than 1 year ago <p>Signaling of breaches:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - If a breach occurs, does the app have a method to notify its users? 	
Technical aspects	Updates & maintenance	How often must devices or software versions related to the product be renewed?	Haverinen 2019
Technical aspects	Updates & maintenance	<p>Potential software changes (i.e. updates)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Adaptive software changes (i.e. maintains software with dynamic environment) - Perfective software changes (i.e. recoding to improve performance) - Corrective software changes (i.e. corrects problems) - Preventive software changes (i.e. corrects latent faults before they cause operational problems) 	Moshi 2020
Technical aspects	Updates & maintenance	<p>Updates</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> >Instruction manual: how should people use it and why? >Are people following these instructions and are you reaching the target group? >Did you build/test your prototype according to best practise? >Possible barriers to adoption of your tool >Possible harms or unintended consequences 	Betton 2017
Technical aspects	Updates & maintenance	Has the app been updated in the last 180 days?	American Psychiatric Association 2019
Technical aspects	Updates & maintenance	Update cycle: The app shows the date of the last update, and there must not be more than two years between updates	Quintana 2020
Technical aspects	Updates & maintenance	<p>Category: Technical Content</p> <p>Subcategory: Technical design:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Device configuration and performance - Software development methodology - Update tracking 	Haute Autorité de Santé 2016
Technical aspects	Updates & maintenance	Maintainability	British Standards Institution 2015
Technical aspects	Updates & maintenance	<p>[S3 Systems & Communication Protection]</p> <p>S3.05 Organization should have a change management process when changes are made to the app or critical systems in operability check there and if okay delete from here.</p> <p>S3.11 Organization should have a documented patch management process for systems and app.</p>	Xcertia 2020
Technical aspects	Updates & maintenance	<p>[OP4 Documenting & Detailing Releases]</p> <p>OP4.01 The app should have a history of updates including details of changes over time.</p>	Xcertia 2025
Technical aspects	Updates & maintenance	<p>Potential software changes (i.e. updates)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Post-market software changes, that do not require the re-evaluation of an MMA and are corrective, preventive, adaptive, and/or perfective (see Effectiveness for more information) 	Moshi 2020
Technical aspects	Data Management	<p>1-f) Is it clear what data the app needs from the user with units defined, out of range detection and a clear last patient button?</p> <p>Not applicable / Yes / No</p> <p>1-g) Does the app collect any identifiable patient information? Yes / No / Unclear</p>	Wyatt 2015

Technical aspects	Data Management	Do you own your data?	American Psychiatric Association 2019
Technical aspects	Data Management	User Data Ownership and Control: Users must be able to delete their data from the app and any servers that back up that data.	Quintana 2020
Technical aspects	Data Management	True / False: You/your organisation (does not need to actually possess the data) but STILL, alone or jointly with another organisation, decides: to collect the data in the first place and the legal basis for doing so; which items of data to collect (e.g. the content of the data); the purpose or purposes the data are to be used for; which individuals to collect data about; whether to disclose the data, and if so, who to; whether subject access and other individuals rights apply (e.g. the application of exemptions); and how long to retain the data or whether to make non-routine amendments to the data. If your answer to these statements is 'True', this indicates that your organisation is a 'Controller' (you may also be the designer/manufacture, but your role as a 'Controller' dictates your data protection liabilities).	NHS Digital 2019
Technical aspects	Data Management	User-Generated Data: (a)The user can input responses to questionnaires/ self-assessments; (b)The user can input information into behavioral tracking systems (moods, activities, nutrition, glucose measures, etc.); (c)The user can input situational triggers/ characteristics concomitant with medical/ behavioral conditions; (d)The app prompts the user to input specific characteristics (age, gender, height, weight, etc.) and provides the user with tailored information; (e)The app can sync with user personal contact information (f)User-inputted information is storable and available from one use session to the next Editing: (a)User-generated data can be systematically edited, removed/ disabled, cleared, or re-set, to include personal contact information, self-report scales, calendars, reminders/ notifications, start-up tips, and settings;	Mackey 2022
Technical aspects	Data Management	Data use -Data Storage and Transit/Transfer -Data Standards and Management -Other Data Questions	Digital Health Assessment Framework, ORCHA
Technical aspects	Data Management	Hosting the data collected: Apps/SDs that require personal health data to be hosted on behalf of the natural or legal persons responsible for producing or collecting this data or on behalf of patients themselves must comply with article L. 1111-8 of the French Public Health Code. The French Agency for Shared Health Information Systems (ASIP), whose remit includes developing a range of products and services for structuring eHealth, publishes guides and information on these matters on its website	Haute Autorité de Santé 2016
Technical aspects	Data Management	Data precision and reproducibility Data granularity Information loss (through aggregation, compression, etc.) Measurement performance in the environment of use Possibility of synching data	Haute Autorité de Santé 2016
Technical aspects	Data Management	Informed Consent -Please assess the level of Consent enabled by the app.	Agency for Healthcare Research and Quality 2022
Technical aspects	Data Management	Data storage Data storage in various geographic location(s)	Digital Therapeutics Alliance 2022
Technical aspects	Data Management	Workflow integration: Does the app work within its users workflow? Data integration: Does the app share data with other apps, networks, and medical record systems?	Chan 2015

Technical aspects	Data Management	Data governance -(1) Does the app state that no data will be shared with other parties without explicit user consent?	Leigh 2017
Technical aspects	Data Management	Data collected (Beneficence) > Prior to its download and installation, does the app declares what user data is collected and for what purpose, its policies on data access and processing, as well as possible trade agreements with third parties -Data storage (Beneficence) > Are data maintained on the device or the web (i.e., the cloud)? Both? -Deleting personal data (Respect for Persons) > Can you opt out of data collection and/or delete your data?	Henson 2019
Technical aspects	Data Management	Data Rights and Governance - Who has access to the data and when? Is the privacy policy publicly accessible?	Coravos 2020
Technical aspects	Data Management	15) Does the company curating the app have clear policies on how to handle end-user data? (Organizational attributes / Reputation)	Vokinger 2020
Technical aspects	Data Management	Tier A + B + C (1) Good data practices [ED] Methods: None stated Evidence requirements: Information from company on datasets used for training and validating DHT (including size, how data was labelled and ground-truth established, why and how datasets were collected, diversity, synthetic data) Tier A + B + C	National Institute for Health and Care Excellence 2022
Technical aspects	Data Management	[U8 Historical Data] U8.01 For large data repositories, historical data should be sortable and filterable. Data sets for clinical-use apps that contain historical data for multiple patients should clearly identify patient name or ID. U8.02 Users should be informed if apps have a limited amount of data storage. Notifications may be used if an app will delete data after a specified amount of time. U8.03 Historical data should be displayed in a manner intuitive to the user and customized depending on the type of data (e.g., chronological, alphabetical). For example, an app that collects daily data from a user might present historical data in reverse chronological order so that a user has easy access to the most recent data collected.	Xcertia 2024

Safety (SAF)

Category	Subcategory	Item	Reference
Clinical safety	harm consideration	If appropriate, is the app equipped to respond to potential harms or safety concerns?	American Psychiatric Association 2019
Clinical safety	harm consideration	Is it possible for users to experience adverse effects as a result of using your product? For example, think about what may happen if the information displayed within your product is missing, incorrect or displayed in a confusing manner. Could this have an effect on the user or the care/treatment they receive?	NHS Digital 2019
Clinical safety	harm consideration	List any adverse events associated with your product reported to a notified body, regulatory authority, or known to you from other sources.	NHS Digital 2019
Clinical safety	harm consideration	Is the app likely to cause harm?	McMillan 2016
Clinical safety	harm consideration	Potential for harm: Is the potential for harm minimized?	Levine 2020
Clinical safety	harm consideration	Safety: The extent to which the usage of a DHI is safe with respect to side effects (e.g., interactions with a DHI are limited to account for addiction behaviour).	Kowatsch 2019
Clinical safety	harm consideration	Are there any risks, possible side effects, or other undesirable effects associated with using the product?	Haverinen 2019
Clinical safety	harm consideration	Are there any undesirable effects associated with misuse of the product?	Haverinen 2019

Clinical safety	harm consideration	Has the possibility of harm been adequately considered? And the likelihood of risks or adverse outcomes assessed? All developers of DHI should actively consider the possibility of harm and include evaluations that look for potential harms including breaches of privacy and information governance. Identification and quantification of expected harms (such as increased anxiety) can be undertaken as part of an RCT, but unexpected harms will require alternative strategies for identification and quantification. Some may emerge during the development and optimisation work, while others may require long-term observational studies during widespread implementation.	Murray 2016
Clinical safety	harm consideration	Have any product-related adverse events been reported or identified?	Haverinen 2019
Clinical safety	harm consideration	Patient safety (categorised by level and type of risk, based on the intended use and main target user of the app/SD): Have any risks or threats been identified, addressed and monitored?	Haute Autorité de Santé© 2016
Clinical safety	harm consideration	Does the app highlight potential risks or side effects resulting from its use? (Transparency)	Vokinger 2020
Clinical safety	harm consideration	Are potential customers and users of the health app made aware of the health risks, contra-indications, and limitations of use?	ISO 2021
Clinical safety	harm consideration	Is there any research evidence available related to clinical safety?	Haverinen 2019
Clinical safety	Risk Assessment	What is the risk category for the app? (Risk Level 1-3)	Agency for Healthcare Research and Quality 2022
Clinical safety	Risk Assessment	Low risk; Self-directed health Management (Personalized health information for use by the end-user not intended for professional consideration) Low risk to moderate risk; Professionally directed preventative and therapeutic health management. (Preventative health behaviour management with professional involvement) Moderate risk to high risk; Professionally directed diagnostic and prognostic health management (Diagnoses a specific clinical condition and/or guides diagnosis or management decisions through diagnosis or prognosis. DHT use is directed by a medical professional or provides information that would be utilized in consultation with a medical professional.) Moderate risk to high risk; Professionally directed preventative and therapeutic health management (Therapeutic. Directly provides treatment or acts as an adjunct to other interventions for a diagnosed clinical condition)	Pearson 2023
Clinical safety	Risk Assessment	Are the health risks of the health app analysed?	ISO 2021
Clinical safety	Risk Assessment	Are the residual risks of using the health app found to be acceptable?	ISO 2021
Clinical safety	Risk Assessment	Has the product undergone a risk analysis?	Haverinen 2019
Clinical safety	Risk Assessment	Favourable risk/benefit analysis?	Nebeker 2020
Clinical safety	Risk Assessment	Summary of known risks?	Nebeker 2020
Clinical safety	Risk Assessment	Potential of unknown risks?	Nebeker 2020
Clinical safety	Risk Assessment	Clinical Safety: Identification and evaluation of risk, undesired collateral consequences and/or physical and psychological harm that may be derived from the use of technology, in either patients, family members and healthcare professionals	AQuAS 2023
Clinical safety	Risk Assessment	risk-based: The level of risk to a person's health must be taken into account. An interventional app like a drug-dosing calculator, for example, has more risk and needs a more detailed assessment than a fitness tracker.	Mental Health Commission 2018
Clinical safety	Risk preventive measures	Provide details of the measures that have been put in place to prevent a recurrence of any reported events, including any proof of their effectiveness.	NHS Digital 2019
Clinical safety	Risk preventive measures	Describe when the health app requires approval from a health professional before use.	ISO 2021

Clinical safety	Risk preventive measures	Does the app facilitate remote monitoring of the patient or send alerts to a clinician/clinical care team or caregiver? If Yes, please specify who can monitor the health of the patients, either through alerts or by other means (Healthcare provider only / Caregiver only / Both healthcare provider and caregiver / Other / Not applicable)	Agency for Healthcare Research and Quality 2022
Clinical safety	Risk preventive measures	Does the app provide users with information about resources that can be reached in case of an emergency? This information should be available on the mobile app. Reviewers should not look for this information on the website. (Yes (e.g., a crisis hotline, 911, nearest emergency room services, etc.) / No, the app provides no information on emergency services / Unable to assess)	Agency for Healthcare Research and Quality 2022
Clinical safety	Risk preventive measures	Can the user be reached by the app provider in case of problems (such as erroneous measurements?)	KNMG 2016
Clinical safety	Professional Assurance	C1.2: Please provide the name of your Clinical Safety Officer (CSO), their profession and registration details (Free text) The CSO must: Be a suitably qualified and experienced clinician, Hold a current registration with an appropriate professional body relevant to their training and experience, Be knowledgeable in risk management and its application to clinical domains, Be suitably trained and qualified in risk management or have an understanding in principles of risk and safety as applied to Health IT, Have completed appropriate training The work of the CSO can be undertaken by an outsourced third party. C1.2: To pass, the developer must have a named CSO which can be through an outsourced arrangement. They must be a suitably qualified and experienced clinician and hold a current registration with an appropriate professional body relevant to their training and experience.	NHS England 2021
Clinical safety	Professional Assurance	Has the safety assessment for your product and its impact on interfacing systems been reviewed and approved by a suitably qualified clinician or other healthcare professional?	NHS Digital 2019
Clinical safety	Professional Assurance	Professional Assurance and Clinical Safety: The Clinical Safety Assessment looks into whether the DHT developer put in place appropriate measures to assess and mitigate any potential clinical risks which may arise from the use of the DHT. This relies on looking at risk management documentation which the developer may have and assessing whether it covers the key areas. The assessment is undertaken in conjunction with a trained Clinical Safety Officer, who is able to comment and evaluate on both the risks recorded, and the suitability of the developers whole process.	NordDEC 2024
Clinical safety	Company's measures	Are measures used to control the health risks of the health app?	ISO 2021
Clinical safety	Company's measures	What is the company's process to handle adverse events?	Haverinen 2019
Clinical safety	Company's measures	Does the manufacturer build with safety by design? Is there a Disclosure Policy? Software Bill of Materials?	Coravos 20202
Clinical safety	Company's measures	Is a process to collect and review safety concerns and incidents for the health app maintained?	ISO 2021
Clinical safety	Company's measures	Sound risk management plan?	Nebeker 2020
Technical Safety	User protection	Does the app claim to provide standalone treatment for any mental health condition?	Agency for Healthcare Research and Quality 2022
Technical Safety	User protection	Does the app claim that it is intended for use by minors?	Agency for Healthcare Research and Quality 2022
Technical Safety	User protection	If the app can be used by individuals that require substituted consent OR by minors, then is consent sought from either a caregiver/parent/ legal guardian?	Agency for Healthcare Research and Quality 2022
Technical Safety	User protection	Is the app intended for use by adults who may have an illness or disability that impacts their decision making ability?	Agency for Healthcare Research and Quality 2022
Technical Safety	User protection	Tier B Safeguarding for DHTs for vulnerable groups or with peer to peer interaction [ED] Evidence requirements: Appropriate safeguarding measures for peer support or other communication through DHT, including who has access to platform (suitability and qualifications) and measures to ensure safety (e.g., user agreements or moderation)	National Institute for Health and Care Excellence 2022

Technical Safety	User protection	Level 3 (1) Enhanced protection of patient data through technical measures Methods: Checklist for the application Evidence requirements: For each of the reported incidents, please provide the following data: type of reported incident, source of the reported incident, number of reported incidents, measures taken for the reported incidents, number of incidents out of the total number of devices used	mhealth Belgium
Technical Safety	User protection	Technical safety: Identification and evaluation of the risk and undesirable collateral consequences that may arise from the use of the technology, for patients, their families and healthcare professionals in terms of privacy	AQuAS 2023
Technical Safety	Quality of information	Rigorous study design?	Nebeker 2020
Technical Safety	Quality of information	Is the app based on or does it use an evidence-based strategy, such as Cognitive Behavioural Therapy (CBT), Dialectical Behaviour Therapy (DBT), or evidence-based guidelines?	Agency for Healthcare Research and Quality 2022
Technical Safety	Quality of information	Reliable information sources: No reference identified (score: 0), Questionable/unreliable source(s) (score: 1), Source from hospitals, specific obstetricians-gynaecologists, or peer reviewed articles (score: 2), Source from authoritative organizations, such as the American College of Obstetricians and Gynaecologists (score: 3)	Wu 2021
Technical Safety	Quality of information	Quality of information: Information too general to assess quality (score: 0), Most information is incorrect (score: 1), Some incorrect and/or out-of-date information (score: 2) Correct and up-to-date information (score: 3)	Wu 2021
Technical Safety	Quality of information	Information/Content -credibility -accuracy -Quality of information -Quantity of information	Nouri 2018
Technical Safety	Quality of information	Technical safety: Identification and evaluation of the risk and undesirable collateral consequences that may arise from the use of the technology, for patients, their families and healthcare professionals in terms of quality of information (e.g., bias or loss of clinical data)	AQuAS 2023
Regulatory Aspects	Compliance with requirements	Professional Assurance and Clinical Safety: With relation to medical devices, we first assess if the DHT is likely to be a medical device under Regulation (EU) 2017/745 (Medical Device Regulation). We then evaluate if the DHT displays the relevant CE mark.	NordDEC 2024
Regulatory Aspects	Compliance with requirements	OP7.01 The app publisher has ascertained that the app, including any and all peripheral devices required or intended for operation and/or marketed for use in conjunction with such peripheral devices, is an MDDS, Class I, II or III medical device.	Xcertia 2019
Regulatory Aspects	Compliance with requirements	OP7.02 The app publisher provides documentation demonstrating that the app complies with all applicable FDA requirements, including but not limited to: Establishment registration; Medical Device Listing; Premarket Notification 510(k), unless exempt, or Premarket Approval (PMA); Investigational Device Exemption (IDE) for clinical studies; Quality System (QS) regulation; Labelling requirements; and Medical Device Reporting (MDR).	Xcertia 2019
Regulatory Aspects	Compliance with requirements	1-i) If the app is designed to support any medical task— is it CE marked? Not applicable / Yes / No / Unclear	Wyatt 2015
Regulatory Aspects	Compliance with requirements	C1.1: Have you undertaken Clinical Risk Management activities for this product which comply with DCB0129? (Yes / No) C1.1: To pass, the developer is required to confirm that they have undertaken Clinical Risk Management activities in compliance with DCB0129.	NHS England 2021
Regulatory Aspects	Compliance with requirements	C1.1.1: Please detail your clinical risk management system (Provided / No evidence available) C1.1.1: To pass, the developer is required to evidence that a clinical risk management system is in place and that it is	NHS England 2021

		compliant with the requirements set out in DCB0129. This should include: The clinical risk management governance arrangements that are in place , The clinical risk management activities, Clinical safety competence and training , Audits	
Regulatory Aspects	Compliance with requirements	C1.3 If your product falls within the UK Medical Devices Regulations 2002, is it registered with the Medicines and Healthcare products Regulatory Agency (MHRA)? (Yes / No / Not applicable) C1.3 To pass, if the product falls within the UK Medical Device Regulations 2002 and is required to be registered with the MHRA, the product must have a valid registration. It is currently possible that products do fall within the UK Medical Devices Regulations 2002 but are not yet required to be registered with the MHRA.	NHS England 2021
Regulatory Aspects	Compliance with requirements	C1.3.1 If yes (to C1.3), please provide your MHRA registration number (Free text) C1.3.1 To pass, the registration number must be valid.	NHS England 2021
Regulatory Aspects	Compliance with requirements	Does your product fall within the scope of the NHS England mandated Safety Standard DCB0129?	NHS Digital 2019
Regulatory Aspects	Compliance with requirements	Level 3 (1) Materials vigilance Methods: Checklist for the application Evidence requirements: For each of the reported incidents, please provide the following data: type of reported incident, source of the reported incident, number of reported incidents, measures taken for the reported incidents, number of incidents out of the total number of devices used	mhealth Belgium
Regulatory Aspects	Compliance with requirements	Level 1 (1) only CE Methods: Checklist Evidence requirements: CE mark	mhealth Belgium
Regulatory Aspects	Documentation	Safety and suitability for use-valid certificate of conformity / EG Certificate respectively the declaration of conformity of the manufacturer	BfArM 2020
Regulatory Aspects	Documentation	C1.1.2: Please supply your Clinical Safety Case Report and Hazard Log (Provided / No evidence available) C1.1.2: To pass, the developer is required to submit the Clinical Safety Case Report and Hazard Log that is compliant with the requirements set out in DCB0129. This should be commensurate with the scale and clinical functionality of the product and address the clinical risk management activities specified with the standard. The Clinical Safety Case Report should present the arguments and supporting evidence that provides a compelling, comprehensible and valid case that a system is safe for a given application in a given environment at the defined point in the products lifecycle. It should provide the reader with a summary of all the relevant knowledge that has been acquired relating to the clinical risks associated with the product at that point in the life cycle: - A clear and concise record of the process that has been applied to determine the clinical safety of the product - A summary of the outcomes of the assessment procedures applied - A clear listing of any residual clinical risks that have been identified and the related operational constraints and limitations that are applicable - A clear listing of any hazards and associated clinical risks that have been transferred, together with any declared risk control measures, that are to be addressed as part of the clinical risk management process in the organisation where the product is being deployed - A listing of outstanding test issues / defects associated with the product which may have a clinical safety impact. The Hazard Log should record and communicate the on-going identification and resolution of hazards associated with the product. All foreseeable hazards should be identified, and the risk of such hazards should be reduced to acceptable	NHS England 2021

		levels. - A summary should also be provided to the assessor of identified hazards that the developer has been unable to mitigate to as low as it is reasonably practicable. It should also clearly identify the hazards which will require user or commissioner action to reach acceptable mitigation.	
Regulatory Aspects	Documentation	C1.3.2 If the UK Medical Device Regulations 2002 are applicable, please provide your Declaration of Conformity and, if applicable, certificate of conformity issued by a Notified Body / UK Approved Body (Provided / No evidence available) C1.3.2 To pass, valid documentation appropriate to the risk classification of the device must be provided.	NHS England 2021
Regulatory Aspects	Documentation	Is the company aware of the product register and Manufacturer Incident Report supervised by the National Supervisory Authority of Welfare and Health?	Haverinen 2019
Regulatory Aspects	Documentation	Who is the responsible person in the company for handling Manufacturer Incident Reports?	Haverinen 2019
Regulatory Aspects	Documentation	Compliance with national guidelines or regulatory statutes -Mechanism used to assure that content or other guidance/information provided by the intervention is in alignment with existing national/regulatory guidelines and is described	Agarwal 2016
Regulatory Aspects	Recall	OP7.03 The app publisher has a mechanism to immediately notify all users about an FDA-approved app that is recalled, the subject of an FDA advisory, or similar status that calls the app's safety and/or effectiveness into question.	Xcertia 2019
Regulatory Aspects	Non medical device declaration	OP7.04 If the app does not constitute a medical device as defined by the FDA, the App publisher certifies that the app is not a medical device by written attestation on the Alliance Submission Form.	Xcertia 2019
Regulatory Aspects	3 rd party product connection	C1.4 Do you use or connect to any third-party products? (Yes / No)	NHS England 2021
Regulatory Aspects	3 rd party product connection	C1.4.1 If yes, please attach relevant Clinical Risk Management documentation and conformity certificate (Provided / No evidence available) C1.4.1 To pass, a valid conformity certificate must be provided. The Clinical Risk Management documentation must meet the requirements detailed in question C1.1.	NHS England 2021

Clinical Effectiveness (EFF)

Category	Subcategory	Item	Reference
Clinical impact	Medical focus	Medical/ Behavioural Focus: (a)App content focuses on a behavioural or medical concern; (b)Content reflects actual diagnostic nomenclature for the indicated problem; (c)Content is consistent with clinical recommendations/ practice guidelines.	Mackey 2022
Clinical impact	Medical focus	Treatment-Focus: (a)The app provides information regarding types of treatment(s) that are commonly administered to reduce or prevent the problem's occurrence; (b)The app identifies treatments that lack empirical support and should be avoided; (c)The app provides skills-learning features to help ameliorate symptoms (such as a deep-breathing exercise to manage stress or low-back exercises to manage pain).	Mackey 2022
Clinical impact	Medical focus	Behavioural Model: The app uses a validated cognitive and behavioural model.	Quintana 2020
Clinical impact	Medical focus	The degree to which the DHI contributes to the enhancement of an individual's health behaviour/condition (e.g., significant reduction of fat mass).	Kowatsch 2019
Clinical impact	Medical focus	Does the app lead to any positive behaviour change or skill acquisition?	American Psychiatric Association 2019
Clinical impact	Medical focus	Does the app have a clinical/recovery foundation relevant to your intended use?	American Psychiatric Association 2019

Clinical impact	Medical focus	<p>5. Therapeutic Quality</p> <p>Call to action: The app offers actions that can be successfully completed with little effort.</p> <p>Therapeutic Principle: The underlying therapeutic principle is clear.</p> <p>Expectations: It is clear what is expected of the user.</p> <p>Adaptive Content: The app content adapts to the users progress.</p> <p>Therapeutic Alliance: The app establishes a therapeutic alliance with the user (e.g. by chatting) through a human factor (doctor, therapist, avatar).</p>	O'Rourke 2020
Clinical impact	Medical focus	<p>Maintenance & relapse prevention:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Includes focus on maintenance of behaviour? - Includes techniques to address relapse? - Consider achievement and future goals and plans? - Regular feedback and monitoring for at least 1 year? - Encourage development of routines? 	McMillan 2016
Clinical impact	Medical focus	<p>Health Delivery</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Efficiency - Effectiveness 	Dulude 2023
Clinical impact	Medical focus	<p>The products ability to directly impact patient needs and clinical Outcomes</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Types of clinical measures the DTx product uses - DTx products relationship to other therapies - Whether the DTx has a comparator therapy - How the DTx therapy relates to the current standard of care - How the intervention aligns with evidence-based clinical Guidelines - Data sets that may be used to determine patient progress in therapy 	Digital Therapeutics Alliance 2022
Clinical impact	Content quality	<p>Content quality</p> <p>The degree to which the content of a DHI is accurate, timely, complete, relevant, and consistent (e.g., real-time location-based pollen warnings for asthmatics).</p>	Kowatsch 2019
Clinical impact	Content quality	<p>Impressions after using</p> <p>>Quality of information: Is app content correct, well written, and relevant to the goal/topic of the app?</p>	Henson 2019
Clinical impact	Content quality	<p>Is the app content correct, well-written, and relevant?</p>	American Psychiatric Association 2019
Clinical impact	Content quality	<p>What are the relevant sources or references supporting the app use cases?</p>	American Psychiatric Association 2019
Clinical impact	Content quality	<p>>Quality of information: Is app content correct, well written, and relevant to the goal/topic of the app?</p> <p>>Quantity of information: Is the extent coverage within the scope of the app; and comprehensive but concise?</p> <p>>Visual information: Is visual explanation of concepts “ through charts/graphs/images/videos, etc. “ clear, logical, correct?</p> <p>>Credibility: Does the app come from a legitimate source (specified in app store description or within the app itself)?</p>	Stoyanov 2015
Clinical impact	Content quality	<p>Quality of information:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - How optimal is the quality of information? 	Mackey 2022
Clinical impact	Content quality	<p>Content consistency</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Is the content consistent with evidence-based medical literature or current best practice/standard of care? 	National Library of Medicine 2022
Clinical impact	Content quality	<p>Quality assurance</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Precision and specificity, accuracy, and sensitivity of interventions/assessments 	Hussain 2021
Clinical impact	Content quality	<p>End-to-end intervention</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Health information and assessment -Patient outcome measures -Lifestyle assessment -Clinical intervention 	Hussain 2021

		-Intended use in practice -Multi-stakeholder involvement	
Clinical impact	Content quality	Comprehensiveness of information - Only mentioned the name of the prenatal genetic test (score: 0) - Having information in 1 or 2 of the following 5 categories: test procedures, timing of the tests, reliability or accuracy of the tests, interpretation of test results, and specific diseases or conditions to be tested for (score: 1) - Having information in 3 or 4 of the following 5 categories: test procedures, timing of the tests, reliability or accuracy of the tests, interpretation of test results, and specific diseases or conditions to be tested for (score: 2) - Having information in all of the following categories: test procedures, timing of the tests, reliability or accuracy of the tests, interpretation of test results, and specific diseases or conditions to be tested for (score: 3)	Wu 2021
Clinical impact	Clinical benefit	Health benefit: - Describe the health benefit of using the app - Are potential customers or users made aware of the health interventions applied to achieve the health benefit? - Are potential customers or users made aware of all financial costs to achieve the health benefit? - Are potential customers or users made aware of the need for support of a health professional to achieve the health benefit?	ISO 2021
Clinical impact	Clinical benefit	Does the product provide clinical benefits? What are they? Does the product provide benefits to the end users by improving their behaviour related to their own health? How so? Does the product provide benefits to the organization (like improving care processes)? How so?	Haverinen 2019
Clinical impact	Clinical benefit	Improvement in the quality of care (clinical benefit, organisation)	Haute Autorité de Santé 2016
Clinical impact	Clinical benefit	Health effects regarding the DiHAs function/purpose	Lantzsch 2022
Clinical impact	Clinical benefit	medical benefit: the improvement of the state of health, the reduction of the duration of a disease, the prolongation of survival, an improvement in the quality of life.	BfArM 2020
Clinical impact	Clinical benefit	Are there any clinical benefits to using your product? For example, will it improve symptom control or clinical outcomes? Are there any behavioural benefits to using your product? For example, will it improve patient reported outcomes or experience measures?	NHS Digital 2019
Clinical impact	Clinical benefit	Health Benefits (1) what is the impact on the health condition? (2) what percentage of users received either no benefit or deteriorated? (3) are there specific benefits that outweigh any costs?	Wykes 2019
Clinical impact	Clinical benefit	Time and number of sessions: What time is required for the user to derive some benefit from the app?	Chan 2015
Clinical impact	Clinical benefit	Clinical impact -Safety and effectiveness	Pearson 2023
Clinical impact	Clinical benefit	On which level are the stated benefits: a. personal level? / b. societal or population level? (Purpose)	Vokinger 2020
Clinical impact	Clinical benefit	Do the stated benefits depend on a certain number of persons using the app? (Purpose)	Vokinger 2020
Clinical impact	Clinical benefit	Level 3 (1) Health benefits = Provide an overview of the existing reimbursements for healthcare providers or healthcare institutions (nomenclature, agreements, etc.) that can be used in the context of this care process, both those provided at the federal level and at the level of the federated entities. If the optimal use of the mHealth application requires new health benefits or an adaptation of the benefits Methods: Checklist for the application Evidence requirements: Study types that can be mentioned include: systematic review, randomized controlled study, cohort study, etc.	mHealthBELGIUM
Clinical impact	Clinical benefit	Level 3 (2) Clinical (added) value includes mortality, morbidity and quality of life, while organizational (added) value includes	mHealthBELGIUM

		<p>elements such as the deployment of healthcare personnel and the reduction of (future) use of healthcare services and other medical devices</p> <p>Methods: Checklist for the application</p> <p>Evidence requirements: Study types that can be mentioned include: systematic review, randomized controlled study, cohort study, etc.</p> <p>The primary outcome should be a clinically or organizationally relevant outcome (e.g. mortality/morbidity, quality of life, reinterventions, health care workforce deployment, etc.). If the available studies did not use one of these outcomes as the primary outcome, but used a "surrogate marker" (e.g. blood pressure, bone density, radiographic measurements, blood test results, ...), the validation of this marker as a relevant outcome should be demonstrated using the literature or by referring to guidelines. Secondary outcomes of a study can also be discussed, but only if the primary outcome yielded a statistically significant and clinically or organizationally relevant result</p>	
Clinical impact	Clinical benefit	<p>Level 3</p> <p>(3) Usefulness of the application in daily clinical practice</p> <p>Methods: Checklist for the application</p> <p>Evidence requirements: pilot project to demonstrate clinical usefulness of your application by referring to healthcare providers or care institutions that use or have used your application in daily clinical practice</p>	mHealthBELGIUM
Clinical impact	Clinical benefit	<p>Tier A</p> <p>(1) Expected health impact compared with current care or system processes [ED]</p> <p>Methods: Quantify uncertainty associated with these figures (e.g., confidence intervals or probability distribution).</p> <p>Evidence synthesis (with sensitivity analysis) can be used if there are several studies</p> <p>Evidence requirements: Description of health benefits and other outcomes (e.g., system efficiency, care outcomes, structural and procedural effects) associated with current practice and anticipated health benefits associated with using DHT. Sources of information should be from most robust evidence available (e.g., clinical studies, real-world evidence, observational studies, expert opinion)</p>	National Institute for Health and Care Excellence 2022
Clinical impact	Clinical benefit	<p>Tier A + B</p> <p>(2) Benefits when used in practice</p> <p>Methods: None stated</p> <p>Tier A: Evidence requirements: Real-world evidence showing DHT has been successfully piloted in UK health and care system showing it is relevant to current service provision in the UK. May include statement from pilot site confirming DHT was acceptable to users, performed intended purpose to expected level, integrated into service provision, caused no unintended negative impacts, showed improvements in outcomes, was used in line with expectations</p> <p>Tier B: Evidence requirements: Real-world evidence showing DHT has been successfully piloted in UK health and care system showing it is relevant to current best practice in the UK. May include statement from pilot site confirming DHT was acceptable to users, performed intended purpose to expected level, integrated into best practice, caused no unintended negative impacts, showed improvements in outcomes, was used in line with expectations.</p>	National Institute for Health and Care Excellence 2022
Clinical impact	Clinical benefit	<p>Tier A</p> <p>(3) Usage and changes in DHT performance over time [ED]</p> <p>Methods: None stated</p> <p>Evidence requirements: Data collection plan on ongoing usage of DHT in target population and anonymised aggregate data showing service user outcomes. For DHTs whose performance is expected to change over time (e.g., AI or machine-learning algorithms or expected updates), report post-deployment changes in performance (e.g., future plans for updates, sources of retraining data, processes for measuring performance over time and detecting decreasing performance, independent overview process of changes in performance). If intended purpose and classification of DHT changes, then new evaluation should be done</p>	National Institute for Health and Care Excellence 2022
Clinical impact	Clinical benefit	<p>For patients or healthy users, could this app/SD be helpful to my health and in what way, compared with products that already exist?</p>	Haute Autorité d eSanté 2016

Clinical impact	Clinical benefit	Societal benefit: Is evidence available of a societal benefit of using the app? Does this evidence include peer reviewed research involving the use of this health app?	ISO 2021
Clinical impact	Clinical benefit	Clinical efficacy and assurance -(9) Is there a statement within the app itself, or the app store, about user feedback during design, development or testing? -(10) Is there a statement either in the app or store about user involvement in testing? -(11) Is there a statement within the app that it has been tested and shown to be beneficial to someone with the relevant condition? -(12) Is there a statement within the app, or app store, about the app having been through a clinical trial, or other form of testing to show real world effectiveness, and has received positive feedback? -(13) Is there a statement about how frequently any advice, guidance or content will be reviewed to ensure accuracy and clinical relevance? -(14) Is there a statement within the app that it has been positively evaluated or validated by a clinical or other relevant expert? -(15) Is there any evidence within the app that the developer has attempted to validate any guidance or recommendations with academic expertise? (16) Is there a statement within the app identifying a list of review or accrediting bodies or individuals?	Leigh 2017
Clinical impact	Clinical benefit	Orientative question: What are the clinical benefits and quality of life impact of the technology, and are the benefits superior to those of existing alternatives?	AQuAS 2023
Evidence requirements	Evidence Base	What is the apps evidence base? Is there evidence of its efficacy?	Zelmer 2018
Evidence requirements	Evidence Base	Is there evidence of effectiveness/efficacy?	American Psychiatric Association 2019
Evidence requirements	Evidence Base	Evidence base: The app offers evidence-based measures to accomplish its intended purpose.	O'Rourke 2020
Evidence requirements	Evidence Base	Is there evidence that the product works?	Nebeker 2020
Evidence requirements	Evidence Base	What kind of evidence is available for effectiveness (case studies, randomized controlled trials, Cochrane reviews, etc.)?	Haverinen 2019
Evidence requirements	Evidence Base	Are there any ongoing studies to investigate the products effectiveness?	Haverinen 2019
Evidence requirements	Evidence Base	Evidence Has the app been evaluated for efficacy/effectiveness through a scientifically validated study?	Agency for Healthcare Research and Quality 2022
Evidence requirements	Evidence Base	>Evidence Is there evidence available to demonstrate the claimed clinical or behavioural effectiveness of the digital service?	Betton 2017
Evidence requirements	Evidence Base	Credibility (evidence-based program)	Baumel 2017
Evidence requirements	Evidence Base	Critical appraisal of evidence supporting whether solution has impact on defined clinical outcome	Mathews 2019
Evidence requirements	Evidence Base	Real world testing or simulation performance in target population	Mathews 2019
Evidence requirements	Evidence Base	Evidence of Efficacy	Lagan 2021b

Evidence requirements	Evidence Base	Evidence base: Has the app been trialled/tested; must be verified by evidence (in published scientific literature)?	Stoyanov 2015
Evidence requirements	Evidence Base	Human factors and implementation Evidence-based -Efficacy and effectiveness (experimental studies, clinical trials, etc.) -Implications for use outside of intended purpose (e.g., if innovation has been adapted or augmented beyond its original purpose) -Implications and impact on health services and users (political, social, and organizational effects, access to care, etc.)	Hussain 2021
Evidence requirements	Evidence Base	Is the content of the app based on recent subject-matter knowledge? Is the content of the app in line with relevant guidelines?	KNMG 2016
Evidence requirements	Evidence Base	Is the app evidence-based? Does it accomplish what it claims to do?	Anxiety and Depression Association of America 2022
Evidence requirements	Evidence Base	Efficacy and effectiveness (experimental studies, clinical trials, etc.) Clinical assessment >Quality assurance Precision and specificity, accuracy, and sensitivity of interventions/assessments	Hussain 2021
Evidence requirements	Evidence Base	Clinical claims: If the app makes certain clinical claims (e.g. reducing stress or anxiety), does it give proof of its efficacy?	Mental Health Commission 2018
Evidence requirements	Evidence Base	Effectiveness: Is the app clinically effective - with demonstrated improved outcomes - for the target population, disease, or disability?	Chan 2015
Evidence requirements	Evidence Base	Is evidence available to support the health benefit of using the app? Does this evidence include peer reviewed research involving the use of this health app? Is the level of the evidence appropriate?	ISO 2021
Evidence requirements	Evidence Base	Category: Health Content Subcategory: Design of initial content -Citing key sources and bibliographic references -Updating key sources and bibliographic references -Level of evidence	Haute Autorité de Santé 2016
Evidence requirements	Evidence Base	Appropriate interpretation of data: - Does the app appropriately interpret what it claims to interpret?	Mackey 2022
Evidence requirements	Evidence Base	Evidence and Clinical Foundation -Does the app appear to do what it claims to do?	Agency for Healthcare Research and Quality 2022
Evidence requirements	Evidence Base	Appropriate measurement: - Does the app appropriately measure what it claims to measure?	Mackey 2022
Evidence requirements	Evidence Base	Tier C (4) Evidence of effectiveness to support claimed benefits Methods: Use checklist to assess risk of bias or quality of study. NICE real-world evidence framework describes how to assess real-world evidence Evidence requirements: Evidence on impact of DHT on clinical management of relevant condition in a setting relevant to UK health and social care system. Note: Outcomes should be relevant to intended purpose and claimed benefits. Choice of study should be guided by intended purpose and claimed benefits. Comparative studies are more informative than non-comparative. Qualitative studies are useful for patient and professional views and experiences of DHT. Less uncertainty in performance is acceptable if intended to be used to avoid death, long term disability or serious deterioration in health On quality of evidence: Studies in setting similar to UK system are more generalisable. Prospective studies are more	National Institute for Health and Care Excellence 2022

		<p>valuable than retrospective because they can be designed to capture most relevant outcomes and have lower risk of selection bias. Peer reviewed papers have independent assessment of quality before publication. Studies should be on DHT in question</p> <p>Evidence requirement for specific classification group</p> <p>(a) Inform clinical management: Evidence to support claimed benefits can include real-world evaluations of clinical utility or test accuracy studies for diagnostics</p> <p>(b) Drive clinical management: Evidence should include 1 or more high-quality studies to support claimed benefits done in a setting relevant to the UK system and showing improvements in relevant outcomes such as clinically relevant outcomes, patient relevant outcomes, test accuracy, time to diagnosis. Could include any following study designs: test accuracy study using appropriate reference standard, concordance study to show agreement with current tests, interventional studies, prospective observational studies including real-world evidence</p> <p>(c) Treat specific condition: 1 or more high-quality interventional studies (experimental or quasi-experimental) to support claimed benefits done in a setting relevant to UK system and showing improvements in relevant outcomes such as clinically relevant outcomes and patient-relevant outcomes. Choice of study design should be appropriate for intended purpose. RCTs are preferable when appropriate, high quality comparative real-world study designs may also be acceptable. Comparator should be care option reflecting current NHS pathway. User acceptability and engagement measures may also be useful</p> <p>(d) Diagnose specific condition: 1 or more high-quality studies using DHT to support claimed benefits of test. May include test accuracy studies using appropriate reference standard or concordance study showing agreement with current practice. Relevant outcomes include test accuracy and time to diagnosis. Test accuracy alone does not demonstrate clinical utility and may need to be linked to studies reporting downstream clinical consequences of diagnosis or test outcome</p>	
Evidence requirements	Evidence Base	Do the app developer and sponsor seem well informed about this problem or outcome, and likely to be unbiased in their approach to it? Yes / No / Don't know	Wyatt 2015
Evidence requirements	Evidence Base	Is appropriate peer reviewed scientific literature used in the development of the health app?	ISO 2021
Evidence requirements	Evidence Base	Information/Evidence-Based Content	Dawson 2020
Evidence requirements	Validity	<p>Accuracy (i.e. constant error)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Closeness of the output to the true value to the MMAs output - Accuracy measures the effect of software errors on the MMA output - Example: In psychometrics, accuracy is the degree to which test scores are supported by evidence and theory 	Moshi 2020
Evidence requirements	Validity	<p>Precision (i.e. variable error)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Under unchanged conditions, the degree to which the recurrent measurements input into the MMA generates the same output (e.g. reproducibility, consistency). - Example: in psychology precision is degree in which two or more of measurement of the same tool consistently arrive at the same result 	Moshi 2020
Evidence requirements	Validity	<p>Analytical validity</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - MMAs ability to reliably and accurately produce the intentional output from the input data - The algorithm used by the MMA is a recognised standard (the current standard of care or described in the literature (i.e. insulin dosing)) - MMA accuracy is relative to reference standard (i.e. International normalisation ratio (INR)) - MMA comparable to another software or device that has an association between the software output and a health outcome 	Moshi 2020
Evidence requirements	Validity	Analytical validity must be determined by the manufacturers and a core set of indicators should be developed that are coherent with the MMA classification	Tarricone 2022

Evidence requirements	Validity	Validity and accuracy: Does the app work as advertised?	Chan 2015
Evidence requirements	Validity	Clinical validity > Are references included with the app that delineate the source of the information from which the app was derived?	Henson 2019
Evidence requirements	Validity	Content quality and (clinical) relevance Has the app been validated by test results?	KNMG 2016
Evidence requirements	Validity	Verification, Analytical Validation and Clinical Validation - Does the tool measure what it claims to measure? Is the measurement appropriate for the target population?	Coravos 2020
Evidence requirements	Validity	Face Validity: Data must be available that shows that the app addresses what the app is trying to treat.	Quintana 2020
Evidence requirements	Validity	Reliability: Will the app consistently function from session to session?	Chan 2015
Evidence requirements	Comparator	What is the likely direction and magnitude of the effect of the DHI or its components compared to a comparator which is meaningful for the stage of the research process?	Murray 2016
Evidence requirements	Comparator	How confident are we about the magnitude of the effect of the DHI or its components compared to a comparator which is meaningful for the stage of the research process?	Murray 2016
Evidence requirements	Comparator	Comparison to existing clinical gold standard	Mathews 2019

Costs and Economic Evaluation (ECO)

Category	Subcategory	Item	Reference
Cost	Business model	Costs and advertising	Lagan 2021b
Cost	Business model	Is the app profit-oriented? (Organizational attributes / Reputation)	Vokinger 2020
Cost	Business model	If the use of the product is free, what is the source of the company's income?	Haverinen 2019
Cost	Business model	What is the business model for the app?	Agency for Healthcare Research and Quality 2022
Cost	Business model	Price: Business model	Camacho 2020
Cost	Business model	>Business model (ambition or reimbursement as a goal) Yes (unless device for collective hospital use) No, no need in the business model (sale of data and user subscription, etc) No, device for collective hospital use > Probability of reimbursement (if an objective of the solution) High Medium Low	Wagneur 2022
Cost	Business model	Company information: What is the company's business model?	Haverinen 2019
Cost	Business model	Business model >Does the health app provides information on sources of funding, promotion and sponsorship, as well as potential conflicts of interest? -Credibility > Where does information in app originate? > Does the app come from a legitimate source (specified in app store description or within the app itself)?	Henson 2019

		-Medical claims > Does the app identify the ownership of the institution and/or the identity of the professional(s) responsible for the health app?	
Cost	Cost to organization	Physicians/allied health professionals: Equipment use and maintenance Training Impact on activities/remuneration Time not included in the activity/remuneration Transport	Bongiovanni-Delarozière 2017
Cost	Cost to organization	Healthcare institutions: Investment Operations, maintenance Training Human resources Transport Impact on activity	Bongiovanni-Delarozière 2017
Cost	Cost to organization	Government/health insurance/local authorities: Allocated funds for telemedicine deployment Training Impact on consumption of care Transport	Bongiovanni-Delarozière 2017
Cost	Cost to organization	Describe any resource costs associated with running your service, any indirect costs of facilitating its use, or any activities assumed to be undertaken by healthcare staff. If directly replacing a process, provide details of the resources needed and the comparative service costs being replaced.	NHS Digital 2019
Cost	Cost to organization	What kind of initial costs (estimated minimum and maximum values in detail) does the introduction of the product impose on the organization, including changes to buildings or facilities, a need for new devices and software, as well as needed training?	Haverinen 2019
Cost	Cost to organization	What are the maintenance costs (estimated minimum and maximum values) to the organization for the use of the product?	Haverinen 2019
Cost	Cost to organization	Considerations of applicability of the system, platform, licensing, attachable hardware, and versions of the MMA to those that would be used in the health system	Moshi 2020
Cost	Cost to organization	Resources including time required for training, set-up, implementation, and management of solution	Mathews 2019
Cost	Cost to organization	Level 3 (2) Costs of related care Methods: Checklist for application Evidence requirements: overview of the costs of the care services required for the proper functioning of the mHealth application. If care services need to be adapted or created, propose a reasoned reimbursement. If possible, provide a justification for the prices (cost structure, expected volumes, personnel, etc.).	mHealthBELGIUM
Cost	Cost to organization	Tier A (1) Expected cost and resource impact compared with current care or system processes [ED] Methods: Quantify uncertainty associated with these figures (e.g., confidence intervals or probability distribution). Evidence synthesis (with sensitivity analysis) can be used if there are several studies Evidence requirements: Description of costs and resource use associated with current practice and expected costs and resource use associated with using DHT. Sources of information should be from most robust evidence available (e.g., clinical studies, real-world evidence, observational studies, expert opinion)	National Institute for Health and Care Excellence 2022
Cost	Cost to users (direct and indirect)	What are the costs of using the product for a healthcare customer?	Haverinen 2019
Cost	Cost to users (direct and indirect)	If the app includes paid service(s), does it provide CPT code(s) for insurance reimbursement?	Agency for Healthcare Research and Quality 2022
Cost	Cost to users (direct and indirect)	Patients/family caregivers: Transport Time Care received by the patient Cost for family caregivers	Bongiovanni-Delarozière 2017

Cost	Cost to users (direct and indirect)	Overall, do the benefits of using this app seem likely to outweigh inconvenience and costs to the user? Yes / No / Don not know	Wyatt 2015
Cost	Cost to users (direct and indirect)	Will the price create accessibility barriers for the intended users?	Mental Health Commission 2018
Economic Assessment	Economic Benefit	Are there any economic benefits to using your product?	NHS Digital 2019
Economic Assessment	Economic Benefit	Based on your business model and associated costs to the NHS or its users, are there resource impact benefits associated with your product?	NHS Digital 2019
Economic Assessment	Economic Benefit	What's the net benefit versus price?	Coravos 2020
Economic Assessment	Economic Benefit	DAQ 1.3.9-15 Are you claiming that there are economic benefits from using the digital service?	Betton 2017
Economic Assessment	Economic Evaluation	Which uncertainties apply to these cost estimates?	Haverinen 2019
Economic Assessment	Economic Evaluation	Has cost been adequately considered and measured?	Murray 2016
Economic Assessment	Economic Evaluation	Anticipated cost impact on clinical outcome of interest	Mathews 2019
Economic Assessment	Economic Evaluation	Is there cost and resource impact data available to demonstrate the claimed economic benefits of your product?	NHS Digital 2019
Economic Assessment	Economic Evaluation	Cost-effectiveness (economic efficiency)	Haute Autorité de Santé 2016
Economic Assessment	Economic Evaluation	Economic impact: budget impact	Pearson 2023
Economic Assessment	Economic Evaluation	Product Evaluation: Economic Assessment: Purpose of conducting a product-specific economic evaluation analysis for a DTx product	Digital Therapeutics Alliance 2022
Economic Assessment	Economic Evaluation	Product Evaluation: Economic Assessment: Steps to be completed in advance of this economic analysis	Digital Therapeutics Alliance 2022
Economic Assessment	Economic Evaluation	Product Evaluation: Economic Assessment: Possible sources of economic data to be included in DTx economic evaluations for the product	Digital Therapeutics Alliance 2022
Economic Assessment	Economic Evaluation	Product Evaluation: Economic Assessment: Cost analysis types HCDMs may use to evaluate DTx product economic impact	Digital Therapeutics Alliance 2022
Economic Assessment	Economic Evaluation	Product Evaluation: Economic Assessment: Potential economic evaluation models HCDMs may consider using for the therapy	Digital Therapeutics Alliance 2022
Economic Assessment	Economic Evaluation	Cost assessment: Presents basic costs assessment of the mHealth intervention from varying perspectives. This criterion broadly refers to the reporting of some cost considerations for the mHealth intervention in lieu of a full economic analysis. If a formal economic evaluation has been undertaken, it should be mentioned with appropriate references. Separate reporting criterion are available to guide economic reporting	Agarwal 2016
Economic Assessment	Economic Evaluation	Cost and economic evaluation: The evaluation of cost and economic impacts of MMAs should require no innovative forms and methodologies (reporting should follow established guidelines for economic evaluations), but rather new metrics for outcomes and different structures for cost	Tarricone 2022
Economic Assessment	Economic Evaluation	Level 3 (4) Budget impact analysis Methods: Checklist for application Evidence requirements: In a budget analysis, you determine the expected costs and savings at the national level for compulsory health insurance, i.e. when treating all expected patients	mHealthBELGIUM

Economic Assessment	Economic Evaluation	<p>Level 3 (5) Cost-effectiveness Methods: Checklist for application Evidence requirements: Conclusions related to the health economic data observed in the studies on the medical device Conclusion covering all the studies included and not a summary of the conclusions of each study</p>	mHealthBELGIUM
Economic Assessment	Economic Evaluation	<p>Tier A + B (2) Benefits when used in practice Methods: None stated Evidence requirements Tier A: Real-world evidence showing DHT has been successfully piloted in UK health and care system showing it is relevant to current service provision in the UK. For DHTs expected to have high costs or system impact, higher levels of real-world evidence may help reduce uncertainty Evidence requirements Tier B: Real-world evidence showing DHT has been successfully piloted in UK health and care system showing it is relevant to current best practice in the UK. For DHTs expected to have high costs or system impact, higher levels of real-world evidence may help reduce uncertainty</p>	National Institute for Health and Care Excellence 2022
Economic Assessment	Economic Evaluation	<p>Tier A + B (3) Budget impact analysis Methods Tier A: Simple analysis including comparison of direct and indirect costs and resource impact between DHT and current practice. Explore uncertainty of estimate by varying assumptions used Evidence requirements Tier A: Budget impact analysis relevant to setting DHT is used in, using information on value proposition and outcomes from studies or real-world evidence. Estimates of resource use should include length of hospital or care home stay, number of hospitalisations, outpatient or primary care consultations, changes in infrastructure, use and maintenance. Cost used should be relevant to the UK health and care system and related to NHS and personal social services resources. Estimates of resource use should be based on clinical practice (e.g., data from clinical study, real-world data, expert opinion). State source of data for cost and resource estimates and include any variation for different groups of users Methods Tier B: Budget impact analysis. Explore uncertainty of estimate by varying assumptions used Evidence requirements Tier B: Budget impact analysis relevant to setting DHT is used in, using information on value proposition and outcomes from studies or real-world evidence. Should include size of target population and uptake estimates, all direct costs associated with DHT (cost of DHT, staffing and training, supportive IT infrastructure), all direct costs of comparator, relevant indirect costs. Estimates of resource use should include length of hospital or care home stay, number of hospitalisations, outpatient or primary care consultations, changes in infrastructure, use and maintenance. Cost used should be relevant to the UK health and care system and related to NHS and personal social services resources. Estimates of resource use should be based on clinical practice (e.g., data from clinical study, real-world data, expert opinion). State source of data for cost and resource estimates and include any variation for different groups of users</p>	National Institute for Health and Care Excellence 2023
Economic Assessment	Economic Evaluation	<p>Tier A (4) Cost-effectiveness analysis for DHTs with higher financial risk Methods: When needed, a cost-utility or cost-consequences analysis should be done to inform the budget impact analysis. Can be done if a DHT provides similar or greater benefits at higher cost or marginally lower benefits for significantly lower costs. For all analysis, explore uncertainty of estimate using sensitivity and scenario analysis Evidence requirements: For cost-utility analysis, use an appropriate standard measure for utility data such as EQ-5D. If cost-utility analysis is not possible (e.g., outcomes cannot be expressed as utility measure like QALY), consider a cost-consequences analysis. NICE uses cost-comparison analysis for guidance on DHTs that are likely to be cost saving.</p>	National Institute for Health and Care Excellence 2024
Economic Assessment	Economic Evaluation	<p>Economic aspects >Costs: Cost analysis oriented to the comparison of acquisition, maintenance and utilisation costs compared to existing</p>	AQuAS 2023

		<p>alternatives</p> <p>>Economic evaluation: Comparative evaluation of costs and health consequences to determine the efficacy of any type of digital health technology intervention and types of analysis: cost minimisation, cost- effectiveness, cost-benefit, cost-opportunity and cost-utility analyses</p> <p>>Use of resources and efficiency: Evaluation of the resources required with indirect economic impact (e.g., space required, human resources, time required, etc.)</p>	
Economic Assessment	Economic Evaluation	How often must devices or software versions related to the product be renewed?	Haverinen 2029
Cost	Price of DHT	13. App Price: How much does it cost to use the app? If it is not free, is it a one-time cost, subscription-based, or other?	Zelmer 2018
Cost	Price of DHT	Cost of basic version, Cost of upgraded version	Stoyanov 2015
Cost	Price of DHT	What is the estimated annual cost of the app for the paid version?	Agency for Healthcare Research and Quality 2022
Cost	Price of DHT	Purchase price	Mathews 2019
Cost	Price of DHT	Unit costs including MMA costs and in-app purchases	Moshi 2020
Cost	Price of DHT	Paid or Free	Wu 2021
Cost	Price of DHT	Is the app free or does it cost?	National Library of Medicine 2022
Cost	Price of DHT	Does the app provide a free or freemium model?	Agency for Healthcare Research and Quality 2022
Cost	Price of DHT	Is it a one-time or subscription model? a one-time or subscription model?	Coravos 2020
Cost	Price of DHT	<p>Level 3</p> <p>(1) Costs of the mHealth application and the accessories required for its use</p> <p>Methods: Checklist for application</p> <p>Evidence requirements: If the cost depends on the duration of the follow-up with the mHealth application, indicate the cost of following up an average patient. In addition, indicate to what extent this cost can vary depending on different patient profiles. If possible, provide a justification for the prices (cost structure, expected volumes, personnel, etc.)</p>	mHealthBELGIUM
Cost	Transparency	<p>Cost of app (purchase price, subscriptions, in-app purchases)</p> <p>Are the prices, subscriptions, and in-app purchases accurately conveyed?</p>	Levine 2020
Cost	Transparency	Is the app upfront about its cost or are there hidden/extra fees?	Mental Health Commission 2018
Cost	Transparency	Are there additional or hidden costs?	American Psychiatric Association 2019
Cost	Transparency	Cost: The app clearly indicates the cost of usage, before and after any trial period, and methods for cancelling service.	Quintana 2020
Cost	Transparency	7. Information: Costs: All costs of the app are transparently disclosed.	O'Rourke 2020
Cost	Transparency	<p>Level 1 Background info</p> <p>-Costs and advertising</p> <p>> Are there additional or hidden costs associated with the use of the app or interpretation of the data? (e.g. w/ ads)</p>	Henson 2019
Cost	Reimbursement	<p>Level 3</p> <p>(3) Reimbursement in other countries</p> <p>Methods: Checklist for application</p> <p>Evidence requirements: Reimbursement in other countries Indicate whether the mHealth application is reimbursed in other countries and what is the nature of this reimbursement. Refer to official sources where possible.</p>	mHealthBELGIUM
Cost	Reimbursement	<p>Level 2</p> <p>(1) reimbursement request has been submitted and is eligible for funding, but has not yet been conclusively checked (see general information)</p> <p>Methods: Checklist for application</p> <p>Evidence requirements: same as level 1</p>	mHealthBELGIUM
No classification	No classification	Other care effects (organizational, social/ethical, economic)	Lantzsch 2022

No classification	No classification	Would you pay for this app?	Stoyanov 2015
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Ethical (ETH)

Category	Subcategory	Item	Reference
Transparency		Does the app inform the end user about the voluntary nature to participate? (Transparency)	Vokinger 2020
Transparency		Ethical principles: The development of the app should follow ethical principles that guide the design of the app.	Quintana 2020
Transparency		Ethics: The degree to which the DHI addresses ethical aspects (e.g., the DHI was designed for individuals with various cultural backgrounds or disabilities).	Kowatsch 2019
Transparency		Developer Transparency -Is there readily available information regarding the individuals and organizations involved in the development of the app? Funding Transparency -Is there readily available information regarding who funded the development of the app?	Zelmer 2018
Transparency		Are ethical challenges of the health app assessed and documented with intended users and health professionals?	ISO 2021
Transparency		Tier A Health and care inequalities and bias mitigation [ED] Methods: None stated Evidence requirements: Description of how company has approached and included health inequalities in DHT design. For data driven DHT, company should describe how design mitigates against algorithmic bias. Tier B Same across all tiers Tier C Same across all tiers	National Institute for Health and Care Excellence 2022
Transparency		>Responsibility: Assessment of the degree to which those responsible for implementing and managing the non-face-to-face care model or technology are explicitly informed	AQuAS 2023
Transparency		>Explainability: Assessment of the degree to which users are informed of how the system works and how their data are used	AQuAS 2023
Justice & Equity		Sample selection is appropriate?	Nebeker 2020
Justice & Equity		Equity concerns: Considerations include user disability (how could users with blindness use the MMA), language (users who have English as a second language), age, literacy, socio-economic status, etc.	Moshi 2020
Justice & Equity		Equity considerations -Given the context of escalating inequalities and persisting technological divide, it is paramount to evaluate the net effect brought by MMAs on equity	Tarricone 2022
Justice & Equity		Possible Healthcare effect: procedural improvements in care: patient autonomy	BfArM 2020
Justice & Equity		Tier A Health and care inequalities and bias mitigation [ED] Methods: None stated Evidence requirements: Evidence of challenging health inequalities, improving access to care in hard to reach populations, promoting equality, eliminating unlawful discrimination. Tier B Same across all tiers	National Institute for Health and Care Excellence 2022

		Tier C Same across all tiers	
Justice & Equity		ethical aspects >Equity: Assessment of the inequalities that can be produced or reduced (e.g., improved access to a given service) due to the non-face-to-face care model or technology	AQuAS 2023
Justice & Equity		>User control and self-determination: Evaluation of the degree of control and autonomy the user has over the technology (e.g., contradicting a given result)	AQuAS 2023
Justice & Equity		>Minimal intervention: use of as little user data as possible for the intended purpose of the intervention.	AQuAS 2023
Legal obligations		[Health Insurance Portability and Accountability Act (HIPAA) Entity or Business Associate] - The user can affirmatively opt in or out (at any time) of information shared with or given access by third parties. [Children’s Online Privacy Protection Act (COPPA)] - The app provides clear notice of the content that will be made available and its suitability for specific age groups.	Xcertia 2019
Legal obligations		Is the health app approved by an independent ethics advisor or ethics advisory board?	ISO 2021
Legal obligations		Consistent with ethical norms: If an app is part of a research study, its necessary to ensure that the guidelines for ethical research involving humans are followed.	Mental Health Commission 2018
Conflict of interest		Technological evolution: -Any possible conflicts of interest (i.e. developer or owner affiliation, sources funding, third-party sponsorship, etc.)	Moshi 2020
Conflict of interest		Does the app identify funding sources and conflicts of interest?	American Psychiatric Association 2019
Conflict of interest		Does advertising within the app contribute to bias or conflict of interest?	National Library of Medicine 2022
Conflict of interest		Funding: The app needs to disclose the funding source of the app.	Quintana 2020
Advertising		[Advertising Within the App] - Information in any app that constitutes advertising is denoted by the message. This is an advertisement or equivalent legibly displayed next to the advertisement or clearly super-imposed on the actual ad or advertorial. - App publisher takes commercially reasonable efforts to clearly and prominently indicate (e.g., in the About section) that any advertisement, which may be perceived as health care or medical advice or treatment, is being displayed for the sole purpose of advertising and should not be construed as a substitute for medical or clinical advice. Advertisements should be placed within the app in such a manner as to not create confusion or uncertainty as to what is advertising vs educational information.	Xcertia 2019

Organisational aspects (ORG)

Category	Subcategory	Item	Reference
Impact on organisation		Impact on hospital organization Simplification Complication without associated act or package Complication with associated act or package for financing the organization No impact	Wagneur 2022
Impact on organisation		How adopting the MMA could alter the current utilisation of services (i.e. workload, workforce, compliance, etc.)	Moshi 2020
Impact on organisation		How adopting the MMA will change treatment location (i.e. home-based, rural, remote, hospital, clinic, etc.)	Moshi 2020
Impact on organisation		The assessment of direct and indirect implications of the adoption of MMAs on the organizational level should focus on process, people, structure, culture or management impacts	Tarricone 2022

Impact on organisation		>Professional practice/care organisation Patients/family caregivers: -Consequences are handled by the care organization	Bongiovanni-Delarozière 2017
Impact on organisation		Healthcare institutions: -Impact on the organization of medical personnels time and professional activities -Coordination between professionals	Bongiovanni-Delarozière 2017
Impact on organisation		The MMA interaction with current health informatics systems (i.e. hospitals and surgeries). Examples of health informatics systems include, but are not limited to, PROCURA and Enterprise patient administration system (EPAS)	Moshi 2020
Impact on organisation		Physicians/allied health professionals: -System setup (equipment, training, etc.) Time spent on (e.g.) coordination and management of telemedicine -Cooperation between health professionals Patient training/education	Bongiovanni-Delarozière 2017
Impact on organisation		Government/health insurance/local authorities: -Impact on new organisations -Cooperation between health professionals -Training of health professionals	Bongiovanni-Delarozière 2017
Impact on organisation		Tier A (1) Level of professional oversight [ED] Methods: None stated Evidence requirements: Clear description of anticipated level of professional oversight when used in practice. Professional oversight should be proportionate to risk associated with failure of DHT to perform as expected	National Institute for Health and Care Excellence 2022
Impact on organisation		Accreditation that may be needed for professionals (i.e. medical practitioners, allied health workers, technicians) to prescribe and/or use the MMA	Moshi 2020
Impact on organisation		Costs of related care Methods: Checklist for application Evidence requirements: overview of the costs of the care services required for the proper functioning of the mHealth application. If care services need to be adapted or created, propose a reasoned reimbursement. If possible, provide a justification for the prices (cost structure, expected volumes, personnel, etc.).	mhealth Belgium 2024
Impact on organisation		Could the implementation of the non-face-to-face care model or technology change the organisational structure? Could it require mobilisation of available resources or the incorporation of new resources? Implementation of the care model or the digital health technology may change care algorithms, workflow, or practitioner workloads? Implementation of digital health care model or technology may result in infrastructure changes?	AQuAS 2023
Uptake of DHT		Tier A (2) Transparency about requirements for deployment [ED] Methods: None stated Evidence requirements: Clear descriptions of data used in deployment, including input data with data dictionary, quantifying level of tolerance for incomplete data or outliers, data flow map for efficient deployment, data requirements (e.g., specific formats, standardisation requirements such as DICOM, completeness, quality), minimum infrastructure for deployment	National Institute for Health and Care Excellence 2023
Uptake of DHT		Tier A (3) Strategies for communication, consent and training to allow DHT to be understood [ED] Methods: None stated Evidence requirements: Appropriate strategies for service users and healthcare professionals describing outputs, key features, benefits and limitations (e.g., model card). Should describe how outputs should be interpreted (e.g., risk scores,	National Institute for Health and Care Excellence 2024

		probabilities of different diagnoses, recommendations for other tests) and plan for training end users. Company should describe process for service user consent when needed	
Uptake of DHT		Tier A (4) Appropriate scalability Methods: None stated Evidence requirements: Company should conduct load testing showing that DHT can perform to the scale needed. Should describe process for load testing and how this relates to expected uptake for DHT	National Institute for Health and Care Excellence 2025
Uptake of DHT		Tier B (5) Credibility with UK professionals [ED] Methods: None stated Evidence requirements: Show that relevant health or care professionals in UK have been involved in designing, developing or testing DHT, or support to UK deployment. Show that DHT is viewed as useful and relevant, e.g., evidence supporting choice of techniques used in DHT	National Institute for Health and Care Excellence 2026
Health delivery process		Medical management by a specialist doctor Medical management by a nonspecialist doctor No medical direction	Wagneur 2022
Health delivery process		Possible Healthcare effect -procedural improvements in care: coordination of treatment procedures, alignment of treatment with guidelines and recognised standards, facilitating access to care	BfArM 2020
Health delivery process		>Solution area (2 items maximum per solution) Prevention Early detection and flagging Decision support Treatment support, compliance, and toxicity reduction Direct therapeutic solution (eg, virtual reality) Patient triage Emergency department decongestion Others	Wagneur 2022
Health delivery process		Practicability: - Can it be delivered with minimal burden?	Murray 2016
Health delivery process		Integration: - Can it be integrated successfully into existing healthcare systems?	Murray 2016
Health delivery process		Will it have high fidelity within real-world use?	Murray 2016
Digital Literacy and Guidance		For healthcare professionals, how can I answer patients' questions about the apps/SDs they are using? Which apps/SDs should I use in my practice and recommend/prescribe to my patients?	Haute Autorité de Santé 2016
Digital Literacy and Guidance		The training/education (i.e. digital literacy) which may be needed for the user(s) (i.e. medical practitioners, patients, caregivers) to effectively utilise the MMA. Examples include: - Continual professional development (CPD) courses for medical practitioner(s) to effectively learn how to utilise and recommend MMAs in clinical practice - Education that patient(s) have to undergo to effectively learn how to utilise MMAs	Moshi 2020
Digital Literacy and Guidance		Literacy level: - How appropriate is the literacy level for the app's intended audience? Presentation of information: - Is information presented in an optimal manner? For example, is scaffolding used? D25	Levine 2020

Digital Literacy and Guidance		Resources including time required for training, set-up, implementation, and management of solution	Mathews 2019
Digital Literacy and Guidance		Does the implementation of the digital health care or technology model involve the training of the professional team?	AQuAS 2023

Patient and Social aspects (SOC)

Category	Subcategory	Item	Reference
User experience	Usability	Usability and Accessibility: The NordDEC considers the design and development of the DHT and whether it considered any recognised DHT design standards, such as WC3, WCAG 2.0 AA, WCAG 2.1 AA, ISO 9241, Apple HIG, or Android App Quality Guidelines.	NordDEC 2024
User experience	Usability	User Desirability Have the intended users expressed a desire for the functionality provided by the app?	Mental Health Commission 2018
User experience	Usability	Usability, Feasibility: - Is it accessible for those with impaired vision or other disabilities? - Was there an attempt to validate app usability and feasibility? - What are the main engagement styles of the app? - Do the app and its features align with Nouri 2018 your needs and priorities? - Is it customizable? - Does the app clearly define functional scope? - Does the app seem easy to use?+[@[Patient & Social Criteria (+ subcriteria)]]	American Psychiatric Association 2019
User experience	Usability	Usability -Ease of use -Operability -Visibility of system status -User control and freedom -Consistency and standards -Error prevention -Completeness -Information needs -Flexibility/ Customizability -Competency -Style -Behaviour -Structure	Nouri 2018
User experience	Usability	Technical Assessment Usability and Accessibility: For full checklists and sub-questions, please refer to the full text.	NHS Digital 2019
User experience	Usability	Usability - Is the technology customizable, sustainable and accessible? - What is needed to use the technology?	Nebeker 2020
User experience	Usability	Acceptability and usability: - Will the target audience (e.g. patients, HCPs) incorporate and sustain the intervention into their lives/ clinical practice? - What strategies should be used to support tailoring the DHI to participants over time?	Murray 2016

User experience	Usability	Usability: - Does the app have special features for specific needs? Is the app "Information Standards" certified?	McMillan 2016
User experience	Usability	Usability: Installation and setup: - How would you rate are installation and setup?	Levine 2020
User experience	Usability	Aesthetics: layout, graphics, visual appeal, image readability: - Quality of layout, graphics, visual appeal, and image readability?	Levine 2020
User experience	Usability	Customization/tailoring: - Ability to customize and tailor to the specific user's needs?	Levine 2020
User experience	Usability	Usability and Accessibility -Design and Development -Accessibility -Usability -Support	Digital Health Assessment Framework, ORCHA
User experience	Usability	Category Usability/Use: Subcategory Usability/design: - Ergonomics - Installation and setup process - User help/instructions - User-friendliness and intuitiveness - Text and image readability - User abilities -Accessibility of content for disabled users - Ease of use - Error prevention - Use cases, business scenarios - Flexibility/customisation - Response times, display time	Haute Autorité de Santé 2016
User experience	Usability	Category Usability/Use: Subcategory Acceptability: - Evaluation by external healthcare professionals - Evaluation by the main target population - Satisfaction survey - Usability (user adherence over time, regularity of use) - User engagement (taking an active role) - Dosage and use (measurement of adherence)	Haute Autorité de Santé 2016
User experience	Usability	Category Usability/Use: Subcategory Integration/import: - Open infrastructure - Search capacity - Capacity to search for a patient - Option to print summaries (selection) - Social elements (private life and social networks)	Haute Autorité de Santé 2016

User experience	Usability	<p>Usability</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Does the app work offline? -Performance: How accurately/fast do the app features (functions) and components (buttons/menus) work? -What languages are supported by the application? -Customization: Does the app allow customization of settings and preferences by the user (e.g., sound, content, notifications)? -Target group: Is the app content (visuals, language, design) appropriate for the target audience? -Layout: Is the arrangement and size of buttons, icons, menus, and content on the screen appropriate? -Graphics: How high is the quality/resolution of graphics used for buttons, icons, menus, and content? -Visual appeal: How good does the app look? -Does the app have advertising? -If app has advertising, is the advertising intrusive and distracting? -Ease of use: How easy is it to learn how to use the app; how clear are the menu labels, icons, and instructions? -Navigation: Does moving between screens make sense? Does the app have all necessary links between screens? -Gestural design: Do taps/swipes/pinches/scrolls make sense? Are they consistent across all components/screens? -Content: Is the app copy well written and relevant to the goal and/or topic of the app? -Is there any evidence to show the average duration of use of the app by users? 	Agency for Healthcare Research and Quality 2022
User experience	Usability	<p>Product Usability</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Product Usability -Patient Protection -End User Support -Product Design Process 	Digital Therapeutics Alliance 2022
User experience	Usability	<p>Usability/content testing</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Describe formative research and/or content and/or usability testing with target group(s) clearly identified, as appropriate 	Agarwal 2016
User experience	Usability	<p>Usability testing</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Usability should be continuously monitored, both in the development phase of the solution and after its implementation in the field 	Tarricone 2022
User experience	Usability	<p>Usability: Can the user easily or with minimal training use and understand the app?</p>	Chan 2015
User experience	Usability	<p>Usability</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Functionality -Navigation - Engagement/Interactivity - Aesthetics/Layout/Animation 	Dawson 2020
User experience	Usability	<p>Visual information (Section D): Is visual explanation of concepts through charts/graphs/images/videos, etc. clear, logical, correct?</p> <p>N/A There is no visual information within the app/e-tool (e.g. it only contains audio, or text)</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1 Completely unclear/confusing/wrong or necessary but missing 2 Mostly unclear/confusing/wrong 3 OK but often unclear/confusing/wrong 4 Mostly clear/logical/correct with negligible issues 5 Perfectly clear/logical/correct 	Roberts 2021
User experience	Usability	<p>Usability (navigation, learnability, ease of use)</p>	Baumel 2017
User experience	Usability	<p>Ease of use/usability</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -layout & graphics 	Lagan 2021

User experience	Usability	Usability: - Assessment using standardized usability framework that evaluates performance across basic characteristics (e.g. helpful; effective; learnable; likeable)	Mathews 2019
User experience	Usability	Utility and Usability - How is the tool worn? Battery life? Available technical support?	Coravos 2020
User experience	Usability	Product Usability: For the final version app, there has been usability testing with existing users.	Quintana 2020
User experience	Usability	usability: - Assessment using standardized usability framework that evaluates performance across basic characteristics (e.g. helpful; effective; learnable; likeable)	Mathews 2019
User experience	Usability	Does the app send out a reasonable number of notifications? (Usability) Does the app allow end-users to opt-in and decide which data can be stored or processed? (User control/ Self-Determination) Does the app allow users to retrieve their data? (User control/ Self-Determination) Does the app allow end-users to easily delete their data? (User control/ Self-Determination)	Vokinger 2020
User experience	Usability	Usability Performance: The app functions without problems (bugs, crashing, etc.). Navigation: It is easy to navigate through the app. Learnability: It is easy to learn how to use the app. Ease of use: It is easy to use the app.	O'Rourke 2020
User experience	Usability	Usability and Accessibility: The evaluation also considers whether there was any user involvement during the development of the DHT, or if any features were based on user feedback.D46	NordDEC 2024
User experience	Usability	Human and sociocultural aspects >Acceptability: Acceptability of patients and professionals to use or be served through a given model of non-face-to-face care or technology	AQuAS 2023
User experience	Ease of Use	What is the evidence that the app is easy to use and has a friendly end-user interface? (Usability) Is the app accessible / understandable by its target audience? (Usability)	Vokinger 2020
User experience	Ease of Use	Ease of use: - Is the use of the app clearly explained? - Is a website available with additional information? - Is the app simple to use?	KNMG 2016
User experience	Ease of Use	Is the app easy to use? Do its intended users find it engaging?	Zelmer 2018
User experience	Ease of Use	Ease-of-Use: (a) There is a main menu on the home screen; (b) The app provides text-based and/or video-demonstrated start-up instructions; (c) There is a help function that indexes and troubleshoots often-asked how-to questions; (d) There is an FAQ feature; (e) The apps buttons are organized, readable, and of sufficient size that touching a button on any given screen does not inadvertently launch an adjacent button and, when activated, the button leads to expected results.	Mackey 2022
User experience	Ease of Use	Ease of use for users with low literacy and numeracy: - Is the app usable by users with low literacy and numeracy? > The medical information provided by the app does not use a significant amount of medical terms; complex conditions are explained using laymen’s terms. The medical information is also supplemented with simple images or short animations. Lastly, if the app allows users to input their symptoms, they can use laymen’s terms, instead using medical terms, and the app will output the possible conditions the patient may have. > Overall, the medical information in the app is sufficiently explained using laymen’s terms, and any graphics used to	Levine 2020

		<p>supplement this information is simple and clear. There are very few instances where medical terms are not explained.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> > Some of the medical information in the app uses medical terms that are not sufficiently explained or supplemented by diagrams or images. Not all the information is complex, patient or their caregiver can still navigate through the app. > Very few laymen’s terms are used to describe medical conditions. Medical terminology is not explained. Any images or graphics meant to help explain medical conditions require some medical familiarity. > The language used in the app is complex, and very difficult to understand if the user does not have any prior medical knowledge. The description of medical conditions does not use any laymen’s terms. No resources such as images or graphics to help explain medical conditions. 	
User experience	Ease of Use	<p>Ease of use for users with low literacy and numeracy:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Is the app usable by users with low literacy and numeracy? > The medical information provided by the app does not use a significant amount of medical terms; complex conditions are explained using laymen’s terms. The medical information is also supplemented with simple images or short animations. Lastly, if the app allows users to input their symptoms, they can use laymen’s terms, instead using medical terms, and the app will output the possible conditions the patient may have. > Overall, the medical information in the app is sufficiently explained using laymen’s terms, and any graphics used to supplement this information is simple and clear. There are very few instances where medical terms are not explained. > Some of the medical information in the app uses medical terms that are not sufficiently explained or supplemented by diagrams or images. Not all the information is complex, patient or their caregiver can still navigate through the app. > Very few laymen’s terms are used to describe medical conditions. Medical terminology is not explained. Any images or graphics meant to help explain medical conditions require some medical familiarity. > The language used in the app is complex, and very difficult to understand if the user does not have any prior medical knowledge. The description of medical conditions does not use any laymen’s terms. No resources such as images or graphics to help explain medical conditions. 	Levine 2020
User experience	Ease of Use	<p>Ease of use: The degree to which effort is required to take advantage of the DHI (e.g., using common interaction paradigms)</p>	Kowatsch 2019
User experience	Ease of Use	<p>Ease of use/usability</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -ease of use -visual appeal -age appropriateness 	Lagan 2021
User experience	Ease of Use	<p>Level 4 Ease of use</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Specificity to users accessibility -Short-term usability -Long-term usability <p>Human factors and implementation</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Registration and compliance -Discoverability (e.g., information can be found about the innovation and compliance) -Specificity to users accessibility <ul style="list-style-type: none"> > Does the health app clearly defines its functional scope and the purpose for which it was developed, identifying the groups to which it is addressed and the objectives pursued with respect to these groups -Short-term usability > What are potential barriers to use of your digital tool? Does your target audience have access, is there potential for stigma, digital exclusion etc? > Can the user easily or with minimal training use and understand the app? -Long-term usability > Would it be easy to use on a long-term basis? <p>Literacy</p>	Henson 2019

		-Cultural Appropriateness Health Delivery - Access	
User experience	Ease of Use	Human factors and implementation >User experience (Ease of use, training, and support)	Hussain 2021
User experience	Ease of Use	Ease of use: How easy is it to learn how to use the app/e-tool; how clear are the menu labels, icons and instructions? Is the sign-up process quick and/or simple? Are there relevant help buttons/FAQ's? 1 No/limited instructions; menu labels, icons are confusing; complicated; sign up process is complicated with no help buttons/FAQ's 2 Takes a lot of time or effort, sign up process is somewhat complicated and/or asks for too much information and/or offers little help 3 Takes some time or effort 4 Easy to learn (or has clear instructions); sign up process relatively simple; some help/FAQ's 5 Able to use app/e-tool immediately; intuitive; simple (no instructions needed); relevant support is obvious and helpful	Roberts 2021
User experience	Ease of use	Human and sociocultural aspects >User experience: Evaluation of subjective perceptions regarding the use of technology (e.g., ease of use, perceived enjoyment)	AQuAS 2023
User experience	User engagement	Usability - Is the app user-friendly and engaging enough to make people want to keep using it? User desirability: - Will the people the app is designed for actually want (or be able) to use it?	Mental Health Commission 2018
User experience	User engagement	Engagement: Is the app/e-tool engaging for the user? Do you feel engaged enough to complete the e-tool program or use the app on multiple occasions? Does it have components that make you want to use it more than similar apps/e-tools? 1 Dull, not engaging, not encouraged to start using app/e-tool 2 Mostly boring, would start program but never finish OR would download app and only use once or twice 3 OK, engaging enough to use app for a brief time (<5 min), would finish up to half an e-tool program 4 Moderately engaging, would use app/e-tool for some time; most likely complete the full program 5 Highly engaging, would stimulate repeat use of app/e-tool or would use for 5-10 min, OR would finish the full program, complete additional programs and/or return to use program again and engaged in tools/strategies given/learnt	Roberts 2021
User experience	User engagement	User engagement (content presentation, interactive, not irritating, targeted/tailored/personalized, captivating)	Baumel 2017
User experience	User engagement	User-Perceived Value D1.1 Understand users and their needs in context of health and social care Do you engage users in the development of the product? (Yes / No / Working towards it) D1.1.1 If yes or working towards it, how frequently do you consider user needs in your product development and what methods do you use to engage users and understand their needs? (Free text) D1.2 Work towards solving a whole problem for users Are all key user journeys mapped to ensure that the whole user problem is solved, or it is clear to users how it fits into their pathway or journey? (Yes / No / Working towards it) D1.2.1 If yes or working towards it, please attach the user journeys and/or how the product fits into a user pathway or journey (Provided / No evidence available) D1.3 Make the service simple to use Do you undertake user acceptance testing to validate usability of the system? (Yes / No / Working towards it) D1.3.1 If yes or working towards it, please attach information that demonstrates that user acceptance testing is in place to validate usability. (Provided / No evidence available)	NHS England 2021
User experience	User engagement	User Engagement: Data must be available to show the level of sustained usage by users after the initial month of usage.	Quintana 2020

User experience	User engagement	Engagement: (a) The user receives extrinsic rewards during use of the app in response to achieving user-defined or app-specified milestones (gamification); (b) The app allows the user to integrate information within the app with the user’s actual, surrounding environment (augmented reality); (c) The app utilizes artificial intelligence (AI chat bot, AI coach, etc.)	Mackey 2022
User experience	User engagement	Behaviour change technique: - Links to complementary activities? - Encourages users to make environmental changes? - Use of one or more recognized BCT? - Does the app facilitate access to social support? - Does the app facilitate access to professional support? - Does the app signpost to relevant services? - Encourage users to agree goals and outcomes? - Encourage users to develop action plans? - Encourage users to prioritize actions in their plans? - Encourage and support self-monitoring? - Provide feedback on behaviour and its outcomes?	McMillan 2016
User experience	User engagement	User Engagement Personalization: Settings (e.g. volume or brightness) can be customized. Interaction: The app has interactive functions (e.g. user input, sharing, reminders, etc.) Gamification: The app uses game-typical elements such as rewards, point systems, badges, etc.	O'Rourke 2020
User experience	User engagement	Human and sociocultural aspects >Engagement: Assessment of adherence to intervention and the ratio of expected to actual use	AQuAS 2023
User experience	User inclusion	User-centred: Apps that are designed with and for the intended end user are more likely to meet their needs and expectations.	Mental Health Commission 2018
User experience	User inclusion	User Inclusion - Were potential users involved in the development of the app?	Zelmer 2018
User experience	User inclusion	Meaningful Inclusion - Is information available on to what extent and how potential end users were involved in the development of the app?	Zelmer 2018
User experience	User inclusion	Number of patients involved in the co-development of the solution >500; 50-499; 1-49; 0	Wagneur 2022
User experience	User inclusion	How do we make sure that users needs are taken into account?	
User experience	User inclusion	Personalization: The degree to which the DHI adapts to the needs of an individual (e.g., the daily step goal of a DHI adapts to the capabilities of an individual).	Kowatsch 2019
User experience	User inclusion	Patient Centricity -To use the product appropriately -Patient financial considerations for the product -Clinical benefits the product provides patients with -Environmental and social benefits the product provides patients with	Digital Therapeutics Alliance 2022
User experience	User inclusion	Does the app consider the needs and preferences of men, women, boys, girls and gender-diverse people?	Mental Health Commission 2018
User experience	User inclusion	Usability: - Is the health app design based on an explicit understanding of users, tasks and environment? - Are intended users involved throughout design and development of the health app?	ISO 2021

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Is the design of the health app driven and refined by user-centred evaluation? - Are measures in place to avoid user error and reasonably foreseeable misuse of the health app? - Are potential customers and users provided with adequate product information about the health app? - Are instructions for use readily available for users? - Are appropriate resources available to adequately help potential customers and users who experience problems with the health app? - Are relevant data on the usability of the health app systematically gathered throughout its entire lifetime, in order to make regular improvements? 	
User experience	User inclusion	<p>Usability:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Is the health app design based on an explicit understanding of users, tasks and environment? - Are intended users involved throughout design and development of the health app? - Is the design of the health app driven and refined by user-centred evaluation? - Are measures in place to avoid user error and reasonably foreseeable misuse of the health app? - Are potential customers and users provided with adequate product information about the health app? - Are instructions for use readily available for users? - Are appropriate resources available to adequately help potential customers and users who experience problems with the health app? - Are relevant data on the usability of the health app systematically gathered throughout its entire lifetime, in order to make regular improvements? 	ISO 2021
User experience	User inclusion	<p>Tier A Intended user group acceptability [ED] Methods: None stated Evidence requirements: Description of how intended user groups were involved in the design, development or testing of DHT. Data on user acceptability, NHS DTAC section D1, ISO IEC 62366-1</p> <p>Tier B Same across all tiers</p> <p>Tier C Same across all tiers</p>	National Institute for Health and Care Excellence 2022
User experience	User feedback	<p>Interest: Is the app/e-tool interesting to use? Does it present information in an interesting way compared to other apps/e-tools or offline/traditional tools?</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1 Not interesting at all, 2 Mostly uninteresting 3 OK, neither interesting nor uninteresting; appears the same as offline/traditional tools/similar apps 4 Moderately interesting; would engage user for some time, somewhat more interesting than offline/traditional tools/similar apps 5 Very interesting, would engage user in repeat use, more engaging than traditional/offline tools/similar apps 	Roberts 2021
User experience	User feedback	<p>Would you recommend this app/e-tool to people who might benefit from it? (Section E)</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1 Not at all - I would not recommend this app/e-tool to anyone 2 There are very few people I would recommend this app/e-tool to 3 Maybe - There are several people whom I would recommend it to 4 There are many people I would recommend this app/e-tool to 5 Definitely - I would recommend this app/e-tool to everyone 	Roberts 2021
User experience	User feedback	<p>How many times do you think you would use this app/e-tool in the next 12 months if it was relevant to you?</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1 None 2 1-2 3 3-10 	Roberts 2021

		4 10-50 5 >50	
User experience	User feedback	Would you pay for this app/e-tool? 1 No 3 Maybe 5 Yes	Roberts 2021
User experience	User feedback	What is your overall star rating of the app/e-tool? 1 One of the worst apps/e-tools I've used 2 3 Average 4 5 One of the best apps/e-tools I've used	Roberts 2021
User experience	User feedback	Access to help : Easy/obvious to access health related help when needed? 1 No Difficult to navigate or find related health information when needed 2 Can find needed information after a lot of time/effort 3 Can find needed information after some time/effort 4 Easy to understand/navigate needed information 5 Perfectly logical, easy, clear and intuitive screen flow throughout, and/or has shortcuts to needed health information. Offline options are available.	Roberts 2021
User experience	User feedback	User Engagement Interest: The app is interesting. Entertainment: It is fun to use the app.	O'Rourke 2020
User experience	User feedback	Initial assessment and tailoring: - Does the app assess users' motivation to change? - Does the app take account of users' environment? - Tailored intervention based on responses? - Considers times when users more open to change? - Carry out relevant baseline health assessment? - Is tailoring based on user progress?	McMillan 2016
User experience	User feedback	User feedback - Describes user feedback about the intervention or user satisfaction with the intervention. User feedback could include user opinions about content or user interface, their perceptions about usability, access, connectivity, etc	Agarwal 2016
User experience	User feedback	Perceived benefit: The degree to which a person believes that using a DHI improves his or her health behaviour/health condition (e.g., a believe that a DHI helps to increase physical activity).	Kowatsch 2019
User experience	User feedback	User Feedback: Users are able to submit feedback for the improvement of the app.	Quintana 2020
User experience	User feedback	General subjective evaluation (appropriate features to meet clinical aim, right mix of ability and motivation, likability)	Baumel 2017
User experience	User feedback	Subjective rating: Recommend app: Would you recommend this app? Overall star rating	Stoyanov 2015
User experience	User feedback	User Star Rating User Text Review	Biswas 2021
User experience	User feedback	Impact (patient-specific) Achievement: I have achieved the apps intended goal.	O'Rourke 2020

		Symptoms: My symptoms have improved using this app. Health behaviour: My health behaviour (mindfulness, habits, etc.) has improved using this app. Recommendation: I would recommend this app.	
User experience	User feedback	Perceived enjoyment: The degree to which an individual believes that using a DHI is engaging (e.g., the use of game elements and level designs in a DHI).	Kowatsch 2019
User experience	User feedback	Satisfaction and reward: Is the app pleasurable and enjoyable to use, or does it discourage repeat use?	Chan 2015
User experience	User feedback	Human and sociocultural aspects >Perceived profit: Evaluation of the degree to which the user considers that the technology in question improves their health status or condition	AQuAS 2023
User experience	Patient empowerment	Can users get information about the results of the data analysis? (User control/ Self-Determination)	Vokinger 2020
User experience	Patient empowerment	Additional outcome domains -Besides conventional outcomes similar to all healthcare technologies, patient empowerment associated with use and potential environmental impact are distinguishing outcome domains of MMAs that, where relevant, should be appropriately measured and valued	Tarricone 2022
User experience	Social aspects	Social aspects - How the use of the MMA may affect the patient’s caregiver(s), including relationships with medical professionals - How the use of the MMA may affect the users relationships (i.e. family dynamics, friends, and other relevant social relations) - How the MMA may benefit patient autonomy	Moshi 2020
User experience	Social aspects	Does the app improve therapeutic alliance between patient and provider?	American Psychiatric Association 2019
User experience	Support	External Links: (a)The app contains links/ recommendations to educational information, aid hotlines, and/or additional referral resources. (b)The app connects the user with social support (peer chat, social media, and/or support group platforms).	Mackey 2022
User experience	Support	Product information: - What kind of support does the end user need to use the product? - If users need training, who organizes it? When? What is the language of training?	Haverinen 2019
Accessibility		Make sure everyone can use the service Are you international Web Content Accessibility Guidelines (WCAG) 2.1 level AA compliant? (Yes / No / Working towards it)	NHS England 2021
Accessibility		Provide a link to your published accessibility statement. (Free text)	NHS England 2021
Accessibility		Accessibility: - Is the health app WCAG 2.1 AA or AAA compliant? - Are reasonable measures taken to ensure that all intended users can perceive all relevant information and user interface components of the health app and related documents? -Are reasonable measures taken to ensure that all intended users can operate all relevant user interface and navigation components of the health app and related documents? - Are reasonable measures taken to ensure that all intended users can understand all relevant information and user interface components of the health app and related documents? - Is the health app age-appropriate?	ISO 2021
Accessibility		Accessibility Features -Which of the phones accessibility features work within the app? -Are there additional accessibility features that are provided by the app?	Anxiety and Depression Association of America 2022

Accessibility		<p>Accessibility</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Who is the app developer? -How much does the app cost -Does it work offline and with accessibility features? 	Anxiety and Depression Association of America 2022
Accessibility		<p>Access of individual participants</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Mentions barriers or facilitators to the adoption of the intervention among study participants. Relates to individual-level structural, economic and social barriers or facilitators to access such as affordability, and other factors that may limit a users ability to adopt the intervention 	Agarwal 2016
Accessibility		<p>Disability accessibility: Is the app usable by those with disabilities (e.g., incorporates screen readers for blind users, closed captions for the hard-of-hearing and deaf communities)?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Cultural accessibility: Does the app work effectively with the users culture (as defined by factors such as ethnicity and language)? -Socioeconomic and generational accessibility: Does the app take into account socioeconomic status and the users age, with potential implications for the users digital health literacy? 	Chan 2015
Accessibility		<p>>Accessibility</p> <p>Patients/family caregivers: Access to medical devices Direct or delegated medical monitoring Quick access to expert medical advice</p> <p>Physicians/allied health professionals: Decision support Continuity of care Ability to set up or streamline patient follow-up</p> <p>Healthcare institutions: Creation/development/ maintenance of activity</p> <p>Government/health insurance/local authorities: Impact on care supply (at regional level) Distribution of supply Access to care</p>	Bongiovanni-Delarozière 2017
Accessibility		<p>App Origin and Functionality</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Availability across platforms 	Lagan 2021
Accessibility		<p>Access concerns: Considerations include the cost of platform, in-app purchases, cost of MMA, geographical location, internet availability etc.</p>	Moshi 2020
Accessibility		<p>Accessibility</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Is the app accessible with respect to language, health literacy, and technology literacy? 	National Library of Medicine 2022
Accessibility		<p>[Access to App Publisher]</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -The app publisher’s contact information including but not limited to, mailing address, email address, or other clearly identified method (e.g. IM, Skype) for support and general inquiries, web address and/or DNS address is provided within the app, or the app provides a link to a webpage that contains the same information. -The app provides a method for users to submit feedback to the app publisher for purposes of improving the user experience, including without limitation, any technical issues, bugs, and errors detected by users. 	Xcertia 2019
Accessibility		<p>Available in multiple languages:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Is the app available in multiple languages? >16, 12-16, 8-12, 4-8, <4 	Levine 2020
Accessibility		<p>Usability and accessibility:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Have all user groups been taken into account in product design, like people with visual or hearing impairments? - Has the product been tested with real user groups? - What kind of accessibility testing has been performed on the product? - Has the functionality of the product been tested with screen readers or other assistive technologies? 	Haverinen 2019

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - How have the products users been taken into account in the products text (clear, concrete language; the avoidance of professional language)? -How have the products users been taken into account in the design of its textual content (headings, lists, and images)? - How does the company continue to collect feedback from users and make changes to the product based on this feedback? - What changes have been made to the product based on user feedback? -How is the company going to continue to evaluate and develop accessibility? - Is the product compatible with the following usability guidelines (if applicable)? WCAG 2.0/ WCAG 2.1 Papunet Design Guide for Websites EN 301 549 section 11-Software Design guidelines for native application Design guidelines for progressive web application Does the application support OS accessibility features? 	
Accessibility		<p>User experience and engagement</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Does the app provide support options for users with visual impairment? Including changing font sizes or colour? - Does the app provide support options for users with hearing difficulties? - Does the app contain a HELP/ABOUT function to aid user understanding? - If clinical or technical terms are used, are they explained clearly to the user? (either within the content of the app or via a glossary) - Is there any statement within the app about how to report issues, bugs or errors to the developers? - Does the app set goals for users or allow them to set goals for themselves? - Is there a statement within the app about the developer’s commitment to addressing problems reported to them? (eg, timescales to respond, commitment to eradicate reported bugs and faults) - Are there opportunities to link with other users of the app, including buddying, forums or group education? 	Leigh 2017
Accessibility		<p>Human and sociocultural aspects</p> <p>>Accessibility: Assessment of whether technology users with functional diversity can access it and whether they have sufficient capacity to be able to use it as expected</p>	AQuAS 2023
Cultural appropriateness		<p>Cultural Considerations With Mobile Health in Clinical</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Step 1: Understand the cultural variables -Step 2: Identify your own potential biases -Step 3: Use a framework to better understand how you experience these differences 	Defense Health Agency 2018
Cultural appropriateness		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Does the app report developing and testing the app for specific cultural group/s? -If the app reports developing and testing the app for specific cultural groups, is there published documentation (e.g., website, papers) of the process taken to incorporate information that is specific to specified cultures? -Is gender-inclusive language employed? When asking the users gender, is there an option to self-describe, an option to decline to answer, use of scientifically correct terms for gender (e.g., man, woman, nonbinary)? -If the app was tested in a study, what was the percentage of non-white participants? 	Agency for Healthcare Research and Quality 2022
Cultural appropriateness		<p>How appropriate is the app for people from a variety of cultures?</p>	Mental Health Commission 2018

Legal (LEG)

Category	Subcategory	Item	Reference
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Data and Privacy		Data and Privacy: the NordDEC identifies the relevant privacy policy for the DHT, which is available to users through the DHT and/or the pp Store or Play Store.	NordDEC 2024
Data and Privacy		Data and Privacy: Once it is established what data is collected by the DHT, the NordDEC looks at how that data is used and shared, and if this is communicated to the user.	NordDEC 2024
Data and Privacy		Data and Privacy: The data privacy policy should inform the user of where their data is stored, how their data is protected in storage, and how it is protected in transit between the users device and the host storage.	NordDEC 2024
Data and Privacy		Data and Privacy: The transparency of the privacy policy should extend to inform the user that any links to third party websites or DHTs are not covered by the developers privacy policy, and users should make themselves aware of such third party policies.	NordDEC 2024
Data and Privacy		Data and Privacy: For DHTs that collect and process personal and/or sensitive data, they will undergo the questions focused on Regulation (EU) 2016/679 (General Data Protection Regulation).	NordDEC 2024
Data and Privacy		Does the app identify ownership?	American Psychiatric Association 2019
Data and Privacy		Does the app come from a trusted source?	American Psychiatric Association 2019
Data and Privacy		Privacy: The app must have an accessible privacy policy that complies with national regulations and is written at a reading level appropriate for the intended users.	Quintana 2020
Data and Privacy		Security (expert-specific) Privacy Policy Declaration: It is explained to the user whether and for what purpose user data is stored and how it is protected.	O'Rourke 2020
Data and Privacy		Are the privacy policies concise, clear and easy to understand? (Privacy)	Vokinger 2020
Data and Privacy		[Children's Online Privacy Protection Act (COPPA)] - The app includes a clear and conspicuous Privacy Notice/Policy that addresses use by any child under the age of 13 and prevents usage without verifiable parental authority (please note state laws may have additional carve out regulations for children). - The app does not, without obtaining verifiable parental/legal guardian consent, collect, use, or disclose data from any child under the age of 13. - The Privacy Policy provides that the app publisher will delete any child's personal information upon notice, or if the App publisher becomes aware or has knowledge, that such information was provided without the consent of a parent/legal guardian, including information that was shared with a third party.	Xcertia 2019
Data and Privacy		[General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR)] - Provide Privacy Notice at the time user is providing information to the app. The Privacy Notice should be available in search feature. - The Privacy Notice must be concise (plain language), transparent and accessible. For the Privacy Notice to be easily readable, key information is at front of notice and in a layered notice approach links are available for additional information in full version. - The Privacy Notice must include the name of the organization, processor, name and contact details of the representative, and contact details of the Data Protection Officer (DPO) if a DPO is required. - The Privacy Notice must state the lawful basis, legitimate purposes, and rights available to individuals in respect of processing. - The user must be informed of the categories/source of personal data obtained if it is obtained from third party sources. This must be provided within a reasonable period of obtaining the personal data and no later than one month. Notice must be provided of the recipients of categories of personal data, whether the individuals are under a statutory or contractual obligation to provide personal data and the details of transfers of personal data to any third countries or international organizations. - The details and existence of automated decision-making including profiling (if applicable) and the retention periods for personal data must be provided.	Xcertia 2019

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Unexpected uses of user data should be posted on the front page of the Privacy Notice and there must be separate consent for different uses. A user must be given a simple way to consent to all types of uses listed (e.g. opt in/opt out boxes for each). If the app is requesting the user to receive direct marketing materials, then there should be a separate opt out box. - The user must be put on notice that they have the right to withdraw from further use of data (if applicable through respective regional data governance laws) and the right to file a complaint with the respective regional supervisory authority. - The app developer must ensure the Privacy Notice is consistent with current use. If a material change is made to the collection or use of data, the Privacy Notice must updated prior to processing. - If the event of a breach of personal data, understand the type of data that has been impacted. Prepare a written report. And, based upon notice requirements of area of operation, Report within 72 hours of becoming aware of the reportable breach to the relevant supervisory authority. - The App Developer shall be responsible for knowing relevant and appropriate regulations for the Regions in which they intend to operate. - The End User Licensing Agreement (EULA) should document how notice shall be provided to individual and appropriate authorities. 	
Data and Privacy		<p>Privacy policy (Justice): Is there a privacy policy?</p>	Henson 2019
Data and Privacy		P5.05 The app enables a parent/legal guardian who becomes aware that the child has provided information without his/her consent to contact the app publisher and eliminate account/delete that data.	Xcertia 2019
Data and Privacy		<p>Legal and regulatory aspects >Privacy: Evaluation of the degree of compliance with current privacy and data protection legislation</p>	AQuAS 2023
Security		<p>Information Security Does the app meet minimal standards for information security and privacy?</p>	Zelmer 2018
Security		<p>Category Security/Reliability: Subcategory: Confidentiality: - Recipient of data collected, personal data confidentiality, and consent for transmission to third parties - Pseudonymisation of data - Anonymisation of data - Deletion time limits and time to implementation - Insurance and legal cover for data loss</p>	Haute Autorité de Santé 2016
Security		non-maleficence	Nouri 2018
Security		<p>[Compliance] - If the app, or through its use, subjects the user or any party to HIPAA, the app publisher has implemented administrative, physical and technical safeguards, and developed policies and procedures, pursuant to the HIPAA Security Rule, as applicable. For purposes of the technical safeguards/security controls, only certain certified encryption technologies are permissible for compliance with HIPAA. - If applicable, the app or the app publisher has safeguards in place or uses requisite efforts to comply with all obligations pursuant to any BAA, including capabilities to assist a covered entity in curing any breach, and address all other requirements of HIPAA in the event of a breach including notifying affected users. - The app publisher has the capabilities to enable compliance, and shall comply with any and all applicable notification requirements to its users in the event that users PHI is or is suspected to be compromised (e.g., Breach Notification Rule pursuant to HIPAA including the capability to support and execute notification requirements).</p>	Xcertia 2019
Transparency & Disclosure		Does the app clearly state the individuals or organizations involved in its development? Does it clearly state who provided the funding for its development?	Mental Health Commission 2018

<p>Transparency & Disclosure</p>	<p>[Notice of Use and Disclosure]</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Access: The identity of any entities that will have access to, collect and/or use of the users personal information, shall be made available and disclosed to the user on an at least an annual basis and shall disclose use by any parties as a part of the use chain. - Usage: The app publisher shall disclose any and all ownership, rights or licenses to any data collected about the app and its usage, including the use of any data for commercial purposes. - Material Changes to Use: The app shall have a section (tab, button or equivalent) or active link to its Privacy Policy, and owner represents that commercially reasonable efforts are used to notify users of any material changes to its Privacy Policy. - User Registration: If registration is required to use all or some of the apps features, the user shall be provided with an explanation as to the uses of the registration information. - Data Collected and Opt Out: User shall be provided (or have access to) a clear list of all data points collected and/or accessed by the app, including by the app publisher and all third parties such as in-app advertisers. This includes personal data pertaining to the usage of the app, including but not limited to browsing history, device (e.g., unique identifiers), operating system, and IP addresses. How and from where such data points are collected shall be disclosed. An Option should exist for user to opt-out of passing data to in-app advertisers. - Data Collected and Disclosed: User shall be provided (or has access to) a clear list of all data points collected and/or accessed by the app pertaining to the specific user, including user-generated data and data that are collected automatically about the user through other means or technologies of the app. This includes data points collected for the purpose of any third-party sharing. How and from where such data points are collected is disclosed. - Affirmative Consent to Use Data: The app publisher shall obtain affirmative express consent before using user data in a materially different manner than was previously disclosed when collecting the data or collecting new data, including for third-party sharing. - Affirmative Consent to Collect Data: The app publisher shall obtain affirmative express consent before collecting personal data, in particular, Personally Identifiable Information (PII), Personal Health Information (PHI), financial data or location data, including obtaining HIPAA authorizations where applicable. - Use and Updates of Information: The privacy policy shall inform users how they can get a copy of their personal information that was collected by the app. A designated individual or toll-free number may be required to be listed depending on domicile of user. The privacy policy shall also inform users how they can correct and update information supplied by, or collected about them, held by or on behalf of the owner, or shared with third parties, including the identity of such third parties, particularly in compliance with the HIPAA Privacy Rule, if applicable, and any other state or international laws, rules, or regulations to the extent applicable. - Do Not Track Mechanism: If not otherwise provided by default, the app shall allow users to control the collection and use of their in-app browsing data by supporting an online Do Not Track mechanism. - Opt Out or Do Not Contact: If not otherwise provided by default, the app shall allow users to control their receipt of commercial messages from the app publisher and third parties through an opt out option, do not contact, or substantially similar feature. - Sharing of Data: The app publisher shall not share any personal data with third parties, unless the app publisher: (i) has an agreement with such third party that addresses safeguarding any and all such user data (BAA); and (ii) takes the necessary measures to anonymize/de-identify all user data in accordance with the Health and Human Services Safe Harbor guidelines for de-identification.(iii) the user provides an affirmative user consent (iv) except when expressly disclaimed by app publisher (v) The app publisher has documented this within the Privacy Policy. 	<p>Xcertia 2019</p>
<p>Transparency & Disclosure</p>	<p>[Retention]</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The Privacy Policy shall disclose the retention policy regarding user information. Such statement shall include policies with respect to data retention under any third-party data sharing arrangement. 	<p>Xcertia 2019</p>

		- P2.02 Retention and deletion time periods, which are based on clearly defined business needs or legal obligations, shall be set. If business needs are defined as in perpetuity, this shall also be disclosed	
Transparency & Disclosure		[Health Insurance Portability and Accountability Act (HIPAA) Entity or Business Associate] - The app publisher certifies that a Business Associate Agreement (BAA) has been executed pursuant to HIPAA with any and all necessary third parties. - The user can access or request any of his/her Protected Health Information (PHI) collected, stored and/or transmitted by the app. - The app publisher uses requisite efforts to limit the use and disclosure of PHI, including ePHI, to the minimum necessary to accomplish the intended purpose (e.g., need-to-know). - The publisher must demonstrate that procedures are in place so that in the event of a breach the app publisher shall notify affected individuals, HHS, and in some cases, the media (news agencies, print, radio, etc.) of a breach of unsecured PHI. Most notifications must be provided without unreasonable delay and no later than 60 days following the discovery of a breach.	Xcertia 2019
Transparency & Disclosure		[Transparency of Data] - The apps public description should accurately state in plain language what type of individual health data is collected by the app, who it is shared with, and what it used for. This description should specify whether this data is sold to app publishers' partners. - App documentation should specify in which types of environments it is designed to operate for all relevant users (e.g. hospital, home, community health center, etc.). This description should explain how the app has been designed to operate in this environment with the minimum burden. For further information and guidance, refer to How to Make Effective Disclosures in Digital Advertising, Federal Trade Commission. (https://www.ftc.gov/sites/default/files/attachments/press-releases/ftc-staff-revises-online-advertising-disclosure-guidelines/130312dotcomdisclosures.pdf) - Legal Owner: The app clearly shows the name of the company, organization, or individual that is legally responsible for the app, not just the developer of the app who may have been hired, but the owner of the app. - Does the app inform the end user what data is being collected? (Transparency)	Quintana 2020
Transparency & Disclosure		[Advertising Within the App] - Information in any app that constitutes advertising will always comply with all applicable regulatory requirements related to the marketing of any product or service, including, but not limited to those of the FDA, FTC, FCC, and any laws, rules, regulations and policies of other regulatory entities in all jurisdictions that apps owner makes its product available.	Xcertia 2019
Transparency & Disclosure		[Incident Response] - If breach is determined, the organization should notify customers and individuals affected in accordance with applicable regulation.	Xcertia 2020
Transparency & Disclosure		Does the app have any consumer bureau complaints or lawsuits pending?	Agency for Healthcare Research and Quality 2022
Transparency & Disclosure		>Transparency: Evaluation of the degree to which technology users are informed about the use of their data, the people who have access to it and the potential risks	AQuAS 2023
Autonomy		Does the app seek explicit end-user permission before sharing data with third-parties? (User control/ Self-Determination)	Vokinger 2020
Autonomy		Do the users have the option to opt-out anytime and, if the case, is it clearly described what happens to the data? (User control/ Self-Determination)	Vokinger 2020
Autonomy		User Consent: Users must actively consent prior to any data sharing with third parties. - Category Informing Users: Subcategory: Consent - Legal formalities - Compulsory information	Haute Autorité de Santé 2016

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Compulsory consent to data use (separate from GTCs) - Consent changed and accessed at any time - Correction and deletion at any time 	
Responsibility		Litigation risks to the relevant person(s) associated with the use or recommendation of the MMA for healthcare practitioners (i.e. GPs, allied health workers, etc.)	Moshi 2020
Responsibility		How insurance(s) (i.e. professional indemnity, life, health, income) for all stakeholders (i.e. patients, medical professionals, developers) could be affected through use or recommendation of the MMA	Moshi 2020
Responsibility		How possible professional registrations could be affected through the use or recommendation of the MMA (e.g. for medical practitioners with AHPRA)	Moshi 2020
Responsibility		Clarify which party owns the data related to the MMA (i.e. patient, third party, medical practitioners)	Moshi 2020
Responsibility		Clarity around which party (i.e. manufacturer, medical practitioner who prescribed it) is responsible for the medical advice provided by the MMA	Moshi 2020
Responsibility		Clarity around which party (i.e. manufacturer, medical practitioner, app developer) is responsible for monitoring and reviewing the patient data entered into the MMA	Moshi 2020
Responsibility		>Accountability: Assessment of the degree to which those responsible for implementing and managing the non-face-to-face care model or technology, and the consequences of its implementation, are explicitly informed	AQuAS 2023